

**Lipid extraction from wet microalgal biomass using
three different pre-treatment techniques for
biodiesel production**

by

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**Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University
of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy**

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Declaration

I hereby confirm that this material, which I now submit for assessment on the programmed of study leading to the award of Doctor of Philosophy is entirely my own work, that I have exercised reasonable care to ensure that the work is original and does not to the best of my knowledge breach any law of copyright and has not been taken from the work of others save and to the extent that such work has been cited and acknowledged within the text of my work.

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Dedications

To my Amma and Daddy for all their sacrifices, patience, contributions, and financial support.

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Abstract

Increased supply of fossil fuels has had significant environmental consequences, including greenhouse gas emissions and global pollution. Addressing the challenges posed by fossil fuel production and usage necessitates the development and adoption of technically advanced, renewable, and cost-effective energy solutions. Biodiesel, derived from various biomass species, has gained popularity due to technological advancements in the biofuel field. However, large-scale production and academic studies on microalgae for biodiesel are still in their early stages, posing significant hurdles in cell disruption, lipid recovery, and biodiesel generation using existing processing methodologies.

This thesis aims to investigate the potential of lipid production in microalgae species, specifically *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis oculata*. The primary focus is on enhancing lipid extraction through different pre-treatment techniques, such as microwave, high-speed homogeniser (HSH), and ultrasonic methods. One of the primary challenges faced in microalgae research is cell disruption, as breaking the algae cells and extracting their lipids efficiently is crucial. In this study, we adopt a wet method for cell disruption, in contrast to most recent and traditional studies that focus on using dry algae. To study the adaptability of the model, experiments were planned using Design of Experiments (DOE) and analysed using Box-Behnken designs (BBD). The research outcomes demonstrate that pre-treatment significantly enhances lipid efficiency in both microalgae under specific input conditions. Extracted lipids were subsequently converted into biodiesel through transesterification, employing solvents like methanol, concentrated sulfuric acid, and hexane. Thorough analysis of the biodiesel characteristics was conducted to assess its quality and suitability for large-scale production as a sustainable feedstock. Correlations between Fatty Acid Methyl Ester (FAME) composition and other fuel characteristics were explored to gain valuable insights into the potential applications of the produced biodiesel. Notably, pre-treatment led to an 14.84% increase in lipid content for *Chlorella vulgaris*, while *Nannochloropsis oculata* exhibited a maximum yield of 40.56%. Among the three employed pre-treatment techniques, the high-speed homogenizer method proved to be the most effective in enhancing lipid extraction from wet microalgae. This research provides an overview of the investigated work, focusing on enhanced lipid extraction in microalgae and the efficacy of different pre-treatment methods.

List of publications

Journal papers

Amarnath Krishnamoorthy, Cristina Rodriguez, Andy Durrant. Sustainable approaches to microalgal pre-treatment techniques for biodiesel production: A review. Sustainability 2022, 14.9953.

Krishnamoorthy, A.; Rodriguez, C.; Durrant, Optimisation of ultrasonication pretreatment on microalgae *Chlorella Vulgaris* & *Nannochloropsis Oculata* for lipid extraction in biodiesel production, Energy (2023).

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Conference

Amarnath Krishnamoorthy, Cristina Rodriguez, Andy Durrant. “Ultrasonication pre-treatment techniques on microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* & *Nannochloropsis oculata* for lipid extraction in biodiesel production” in international conference Sustainable Energy and Environmental Protection 2022. (Paper No: 237 SEEP - 2022)

Amarnath Krishnamoorthy, Cristina Rodriguez, Andy Durrant. “Enhanced lipid production by high-speed homogeniser from microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* in biodiesel production”. GCGW-2022, University of Sharjah – UAE 2022. (Paper No: 103 GCGW – 2022).

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Krishnamoorthy, Amarnath. “Effects of high-speed homogeniser pre-treatment technique in lipid extraction on wet microalgae for biodiesel production”. 6th Global Webinar on Applied Science, Engineering and Technology, Bangalore – India.

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List of Nomenclature

EU	- European union	A	- Significance level
C	- Carbon	DW	- Dry weight
O	- Oxygen	Prob > F	- P-Value
PBR	- Photobioreactors		
Mm	- Microns meter		
DI	- De-ionised water		
g/ml	- Gram per millilitre		
GC	- Gas chromatography		
FID	- Flame ionisation detector		
FAME	- Fatty acid methyl esters		
MPa	- Mega pascal		
RPM	- Revolutions per minute		
OD	- Optical density		
W	- Watts		
kHz	- Kilo hertz		
%	- Percentage		
Kg	- Kilogram		
BBD	- Box-Behnken Design		
RSM	- Response surface methodology		
CCD	Central composite design		
3D	- 3-dimensional		
DOE	- Design of Experiment		
ANOVA	- Analysis of variance		
R ²	- Coefficient of determination (%)		
R ²	- Interaction regression coefficient (%)		

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The energy crisis is one of the most significant concerns to the present world's stability and peace. Natural resources are an essential part of economic construction that meets the requirements of humanity. With the increasing population, economic production is constantly growing, paving the way to research for creating new things and innovating the current materials to overcome the energy crisis. The growing countries with developing economies having limited natural resources are in a situation to secure fuel supplies. Fossil fuels like coal, petrol, natural gas, etc., have been viewed as fundamental energy sources (Chandrasekhar *et al.*, 2015) and are used in massive amounts worldwide. The longer depending on the fossil fuels challenges in lowering greenhouse gases which paves the way for global warming. Also, the increase in the Earth's overall temperature due to various human activities and natural causes leads to global warming. Some data shows that the rise in global temperature may result in high health risks among future generations (Watts *et al.*, 2018). Renewable and eco-friendly biofuels are needed to retain a pristine ecosystem and maintain stability to replace fossil fuels (Schenk *et al.*, 2008). These alternative energy sources align with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDGs) for 2030, which aim to address global challenges and promote sustainable development (Chhandama, Rai and Lalawmpuii, 2023). These replacements are derived from natural resources, and one such resource is microalgae (Kadier *et al.*, 2016). The views on the algae are represented by macroscopic and microscopic organisms where the macroscopic organics grow to a length of 10 meters and microscopic organics to a micrometre.

The earlier research for biofuel production started in mid of the 1980s. To resolve the energy crisis, some German scientists tried generating lipids from diatom during World War II (Cohen, Norman and Heimer, 1995). Current research shows that microalgal biodiesel production is challenging to obtain higher efficiency and eco-friendly fuel. According to scientists, microalgae can replace the traditional methods of biofuel, biofuel feed and various food products (Barkia, Saari and Manning, 2019; Sathasivam *et al.*, 2019; Figueroa-Torres *et al.*, 2020; Lever *et al.*, 2020). Microalgae are considered a fascinating resource in industries as they help produce multitudinous products because of significantly high-level growth rate, greater efficiency in photosynthesis and process optimisation. Their applications have already

been used in commercial industries like animal feed, food, therapeutics, cosmetics and biofuels etc. (Brennan and Owende, 2010a), (Chisti, 2007a), (de Stefano *et al.*, 2011), (Harun and Danquah, 2011), (Hazar and Aydin, 2010). They can reasonably accumulate lipids, proteins, carbohydrates and other biologically active elements (Barkia, Saari and Manning, 2019) (Chisti, 2007b). The main advantages of culturing microalgae are they can be cultured in a minimal region, with fewer nutrients and minimal water (saline or brackish water) (Tsukahara and Sawayama, 2005) (Roberts *et al.*, 2013). Microalgal cells are relatively small and protected inside a cell wall. The globus within them contains the products; in some species, the effects are seen bound to the cell membranes. Due to these complex cell wall structures, cell disruption is said to be challenging (Gerken, Donohoe and Knoshaug, 2013), (Scholz *et al.*, 2014). Some microalgae species easily break down using a gentle and effective cell disruption technique. But this may not support large-scale production, so it is essential to compare and choose the feasible energy-efficient cell disruption method, which will result in high standard extracted products, economical operating cost and high lipid recovery. Therefore, the photosynthetic properties of microalgae output better prospects for the production of lipids or other constituents (Singh *et al.*, 2014). The fatty acids inside the microalgae cells indicate highly efficient energy compounds like triacylglycerols and fatty acids, which are the main requirements for biodiesel (Leite, Abdelaziz and Hallenbeck, 2013). The formation of carbon chains and the C16, C18 and C22 fatty acids show the main differences in lipids produced from the microalgal cells from the plants (Huang *et al.*, 2010). Among the fatty acids and triacylglycerols, oleic acid has a more fabulous significant property to balance the biodiesel characteristics (Singh *et al.*, 2014).

The biological value of the microalgal oil and biomass is due to the variety of elements they synthesise, their growth capacity and the ability to increase the efficiency of the targeted bio compounds using cultivating parameters and extraction methodologies (Sun *et al.*, 2018; Li-Beisson *et al.*, 2019). Today, there is an increasing demand for algal biomass due to the increase in both traditional industries and microalgal applications. Estimates show that *Chlorella* and *Arthrospira* production is 2000 – 5000 tons and 6700 – 12000 tons, respectively (Barkia, Saari and Manning, 2019) (Lever *et al.*, 2020). The higher cost of mass microalgal cultivation and their raw materials are facing an issue in producing biomass, which must be considered necessary. Reducing this cost and enhancing the economic productivity of the microalgal lipids can be archived with different techniques. The use of eco-friendly pre-treatment techniques like mechanical (Halim *et al.*, 2013), microwave (P. Patil *et al.*, 2013),

chemical (Meullemiestre *et al.*, 2016; Patil *et al.*, 2018a), ultrasonic (Passos, Astals and Ferrer, 2014), high pressure homogeniser (Clarke *et al.*, 2010) etc., were studied. The factors during the cultivation using the genetic engineering process to increase the percentage of lipids, proteins and other valuable bioproducts are considered quite challenging (Kateryna Maltseva *et al.*, 2021).

The natural raw material for the third generation of biofuels is obtained in large quantities of microalgal lipids (Sathasivam *et al.*, 2019). According to researchers (Michalak, Chojnacka and Saeid, 2017), lipids are the most commonly extracted compounds from microalgae which have great potential for commercial applications, and their ability of the stored lipids is precious to help cover the increasing demand for raw materials and food. For targeting the biodiesel, the lipids synthesised from the microalgae are determined by the number of fatty acids present. The FAME profile produced by the lipids of microalgae shows thousands of fatty acid profiles. Processing these fatty acids gives a way to study various analyses and innovative research with a fair conclusion. These studies are the significant formulation and generalisation of new methodologies for finding a resource with microorganisms (Jónasdóttir, 2019) (Cañavate, 2019).

1.2 Advancements in Biofuel Technology and FAME Analysis for Biodiesel Production

Transport industries like shipping and aviation rely primarily on petroleum and fossil fuels. Fossil fuel fills two-thirds of the entire world's energy consumption, which might soon lead to diminishing. We will look for a development of an alternative renewable technology (Morweiser *et al.*, 2010). Also, biofuels remain the best alternative to address the world's increasing population and diminishing resources (Qadariyah *et al.*, 2018a). With the growing demand for petroleum products, mainly in the markets of Asia, the requirement for renewable fuel, too, increases, especially biodiesel (Sheehan *et al.*, 1998). In order to enhance climate change, energy security and rural development, biofuels are needed (Rodionova *et al.*, 2017). The physical properties of the biodiesel have sufficient energy, like cold pour point and cetane number, making the biodiesel a target for production. J. Patrick and E. Duffy studied the first vegetable oil for the transesterification process in 1853, where R. Diesel presented the first diesel engine in an International exhibition conducted in 1900 (Yousuf, 2012). Biofuels, especially biodiesel, can fill the energy gap with proper research and favour countries that are still dependent on fossil fuels. This biofuel is required to have some important physical

properties. The significant biofuel targets are looked into three properties: higher energy density, high oil generation and should be compatible with the current fuel combustion model (Fischer, Klein-Marcuschamer and Stephanopoulos, 2008). Biodiesel from plant oils has been seen to have 90% more energy than petroleum diesel and ethanol fuels, and biodiesel obtained from soybean oil has shown 93% energy efficiency (Brennan and Owende, 2010b).

The fuel characteristics of biodiesel are determined by the fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) profile constituents, which include degrees of unsaturation, free fatty acid percentage and fatty acid chain length [64]. The fatty acids (FA) are classified based on their chain length, which is short-chain FA (<C6), medium-chain FA (C6 – C12), long-chain FA (C13 – C21) and very long FA (>C22) (Hewavitharana *et al.*, 2020). Experiment planning is the most crucial step in fatty acid composition analysis. It is possible to achieve this by transforming fatty acids into methyl esters by using gas chromatography (GC) (Niemi, Lage and Gentili, 2019)(Chiu and Kuo, 2020). The majority of the microalgal FAME quantitative measurements and profile characteristic analyses have been carried out using GC-mass spectroscopy (GC - MS) and chromatography-flame ionization detection (GC - FID) identification systems (Niemi, Lage and Gentili, 2019). FIDs are a non-selective detection system, and MS is frequently used to provide a more accurate replacement when greater precision is required (Selvarajan *et al.*, 2015). Commercial biodiesel is often 5 – 9% less effective than conventional diesel, but it has lower carbon emissions, except for a rise in NO_x emissions. Mainly in Europe, diesel typically consists of 5% of biodiesel in their fuel mixture (Allen *et al.*, 1999). The nomenclature used to tag fatty acid methyl esters is C_x(y), where X indicates the ethyl chain length and y indicates the double bonds in the chain, as represented in Figure 1. 1 (Smith-Bädorf *et al.*, 2013). The usage of 'n' for the overall number of carbons from the distal (last) double bonds to the terminal methyl provides extra details for labelling the place of carbon chain double bonds. The position of any additional double bonds is generally calculated by adding three, but in the particular circumstance of conjugated double bonds, it is only two carbons between each bond.

Figure 1. 1: Nomenclature for FAME

The composition of fatty acids in the biodiesel generated can be analysed for adaptability and adherence with the current biodiesel standards. Biodiesel constitutes 15% of aliphatic compounds and 84% of olefinic compounds, whereas diesel consists of 67% of aliphatic and 3% of olefinic compounds. Diesel also contains 20% aromatic and 9% of naphthene compounds and over 300 compounds in its exhaust gas (Balat and Balat, 2010; Feofilova, Sergeeva and Ivashechkin, 2010). The FAME saturation and the chain length depending on the fatty acid alkyl esters (FAAEs) of the extracted products from the algal species, which are used during growth conditions. The algae oil will contain a wide range of lipids, including glycolipids, phospholipids, triglycerides, monoglycerides, diglycerides and phospholipids, which forms an array of FAAEs during transesterification. These compounds highly influence the fatty acid profile and characteristics of biodiesel performance (Gouveia and Oliveira, 2009a; Caldeira *et al.*, 2017). Increasing unsaturated fatty acid levels in traditional biodiesel may be unfavourable because of uncertainties concerning stability, even though adequate antioxidant can compensate for lousy stability.

1.3 Energy security, oil supply and demand

The energy security of biofuel depends on the supply as needed for the global demand, and political, physical and economic factors restrict them. The energy supply relies on border crossing and challenging global market supply systems (*Energy security and global climate change mitigation*. - University of Westminster, no date). Energy security is also concerned with the increasing demand, natural threats and terrorism. Some of the essential factors must be overcome to achieve issues for the energy supply system, like properly utilising the energy as needed and changing the available energy mix in the market (*EconPapers: Conceptualising*

energy security and making explicit its polysemic nature, no date). Most commercial biodiesel will be 5 to 8% less efficient than fossil diesel, but biodiesel can help reduce emissions, including an increase in some amount of NO_x emissions (Heredia-Arroyo *et al.*, 2011).

Liquified fuels are considered the most accessible fuel for transport because of the higher energy level per volume. In 2021, global oil production was 95.57 million Barrels/per day, with a consumption rate of 100.23 million barrels per day. The growing energy consumption demand in 2021 accounted for about 95.35% higher than the production. The highest oil production area is in the United States, followed by Saudi Arabia, Russia, Canada and China. In contrast, the consumption of oil tops in the United States, followed by China and India (*Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) - U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA)*, no date). Oil prices fluctuate daily, leading to price changes in diesel and biodiesel daily. The local government tax and subsidy policies also influence fuel prices.

1.4 Economic limitations for microalgal biodiesel

In theory, microalgae have tremendous potential as a replacement for fossil fuels. In order to compete as a replacement for fossil fuels, the fuel from microalgae must be economically comparable. Current diesel price ranges from US \$0.85 - \$1.40. per litre worldwide, with an average selling price of US \$1.36 per litre [79]. Cost estimates for microalgal biodiesel range from US \$1.42-3.55 per litre ((3) (*PDF*) *Predicting Financial Distress and the Performance of Distressed Stocks*, no date; Chisti, 2007c; Delrue *et al.*, 2012; Slade and Bauen, 2013) Consequently, microalgal oil production costs must be reduced at least 2.4-fold. However, some statistics estimate that reductions of up to 7 times current costs may be required (Chisti, 2007c). Despite the varying overall costs stated, cultivation expenditures, including nutrient content, water and CO₂, are continuously identified as an essential factor to the biodiesel from microalgae. The biodiesel from raceway ponds with nutrients like phosphorus and nitrogen peaks around 10% of the overall expenses. Carbon dioxide is also an essential cost in cultivation, and around 50% of the cost cut can be done if this is avoided. The research should focus on reducing this cost, and flue gas can also be used as an alternative to CO₂ (Slade and Bauen, 2013). Furthermore, nutrient supply enhances 50% of all energy demands involved with microalgal cultivation. As such, a readily available nutrient origin could substantially increase biodiesel's energy investment return (EROI) from microalgae. The biodiesel price of microalgae biomass cultivated using photobioreactors is controlled by capital investment, and

feasibility analysis is nearly impossible even if the nutrients and water are obtained for free. It is also understandable that lipid yield and water and nutrient supply are two of the most critical limitations that influence the economic suitability of microalgal biodiesel.

1.5 Research scope, aims and objectives.

The study represented in this thesis approaches the area to work on a complex problem to produce a sustainable biodiesel feedstock. The research scope of this study encompasses the analysis and optimisation of lipid extraction from microalgal species, specifically focusing on *Chlorella Vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis Oculata*. This research investigates the potential applications of *Chlorella Vulgaris* (*C.Vulgaris*) and *Nannochloropsis oculata* (*N.Oculata*) in biodiesel production. *C.Vulgaris* demonstrates high adaptability, metabolic diversity, and rapid growth even in challenging conditions. It has been proven to enhance lipid recovery and exhibit binding capabilities for metals like nickel, zinc, and copper. Furthermore, *C.Vulgaris* shows promise in removing phosphorus and nitrogen from wastewater. With its rich biochemical composition and pigments, *C.Vulgaris* has broad applicability in biotechnological sectors. On the other hand, *N.Oculata*, a marine algae with high tolerance to environmental conditions, synthesises substantial amounts of triacylglycerols (TAGs) and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs). It has garnered industrial interest due to its exponential growth and potential as a biodiesel feedstock. The research will explore the potential of these algae species for biofuel production. The investigation involves three pre-treatment techniques: microwave, high-speed homogeniser, and ultrasonic. For our study, we have planned to set the microwave parameters within the ranges of MW power (90 - 900 W) and MW time (1.5 to 3 min). Similarly, the high-speed homogeniser (HSH) parameters will be adjusted between HSH speed (6000 - 22000 rpm) and HSH running time (5 - 15 min). The ultrasonic parameters will vary with US frequency (37 and 80 kHz) and US exposure time (10 - 20 min). Additionally, the lipid extraction reaction time will be set between 2 - 4 hrs. To determine these suitable ranges, we conducted a thorough preliminary investigation and extensively reviewed existing research specifically focused on pre-treatment parameters for microalgae. Through this comprehensive analysis, we were able to identify feasible and relevant ranges that would provide valuable insights into the relationship between the pre-treatment process and lipid extraction. Our selection of these specific parameters and their respective targets was also guided by considering the availability of resources and the equipment model used in this research. The extracted lipids will be analysed for their fatty acid composition, particularly fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) content,

which will be compared with traditional biodiesel sources. The optimisation process includes evaluating various operating factors using design of experiments (DOE) and response surface methodology (RSM) to develop regression models and examine the interaction between input and output parameters. Additionally, this research aims to contribute to the environmental benefits of biodiesel research industries by exploring microalgal species as a sustainable biodiesel feedstock, thus promoting a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions.

The main aim of this research is to use three different pre-treatment methods such as microwave, High-Speed homogeniser and Ultrasonic techniques were studied to enhance the lipid extraction from microalgae (*Chlorella Vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis Oculata*) for Biodiesel production.

The objectives of the study is to analyse and optimise the lipid efficiency (%) from pre-treated microalgae are shown below,

1. Evaluate and compare the effectiveness of microwave, high-speed homogeniser, and ultrasonic techniques in enhancing lipid content from microalgae. Optimise these techniques by determining the most effective operating factors.
2. Extract lipids from *Chlorella Vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis Oculata*, two commonly cultured microalgal species, using pre-treatment techniques such as microwave, high-speed homogeniser, and ultrasonic, under specific extraction conditions.
3. To evaluate the effect of extracted lipids using data analysis techniques of design of experiments (DOE) to study about the significant model worked for the lipid extraction process by developing a regression model. The effects of interaction between the input/output parameters are studied using response surface methodology (RSM).
4. To analyse the extracted lipids for their FAME content and evaluate the percentage of fatty acids present in them. This results will be compared with the soya source biodiesel and other diesel source from literature and finding the diesel characteristics to provide a good route to check on the blend ratio for the biodiesel feedstock and conclude with fairy results.

5. To compare and discuss both the results obtained from the pre-treatment techniques and investigate the microalgae reaction in both of them where they can extract enhanced lipids.

Despite the extensive research conducted on microalgae as a potential feedstock for biodiesel production, there is a scarcity of studies that specifically address the process of extracting lipids from microalgae and converting them into biodiesel. This gap in knowledge highlights the need for further investigation and provides a foundation for the present research, which aims to bridge this gap and contribute to the understanding and advancement of microalgal-based biodiesel production.

1.6 Research Contribution

The research conducted in this thesis makes several contributions to the field of biodiesel production from microalgae. The main contributions are as follows:

1. **Evaluation of Pre-treatment Techniques:** The study systematically evaluates three different pre-treatment techniques, namely microwave, high-speed homogeniser, and ultrasonic, for enhancing lipid extraction from microalgal species. The effectiveness of these techniques is assessed by analysing their impact on lipid content. The research optimises the operating factors of each technique to determine the most efficient conditions for lipid extraction.
2. **Analysis of Fatty Acid Composition:** The extracted lipids from the microalgae *Chlorella Vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis Oculata* are analysed to evaluate their fatty acid composition. This analysis provides insights into the suitability of these lipids as biodiesel feedstock. The percentage of various fatty acids present in the lipids is determined and compared with the properties of biodiesel derived from other sources from literature.
3. **Development of Regression Models:** The research employs data analysis techniques, specifically design of experiments (DOE) and response surface methodology (RSM), to develop regression models for the lipid extraction process. The effects of different

input/output parameters and their interactions are studied using these models. This approach aids in understanding the significant factors influencing the lipid extraction process and optimising the overall efficiency.

4. Comparison of Pre-treatment Techniques: The results obtained from the evaluation of the three pre-treatment techniques are compared and discussed. The research investigates how each technique affects microalgae reactions and the resulting enhanced lipid extraction. By comparing the outcomes, the study provides insights into the most effective pre-treatment technique for large-scale production.

The outcomes of the study provide valuable information for the production of biodiesel from microalgae. The analysis of fatty acid composition helps in understanding the potential of microalgal lipids as a raw material for biodiesel production.

1.7 Thesis outline

Chapter 1 gives a basic information about the algal biodiesel and how the conversion of biomass to biodiesel and other biofuels have obtained a positive attention in fossil fuel arena. This chapter also discuss about the aim of the research, research scope and the objectives. Here, the information of the thesis structure is given which shows about the processes and the result outcome and how it will be tried to use for biodiesel feedstock.

Chapter 2 discusses the general introduction to biodiesel produced from microalgae and their approaches to the environment. This introduction chapter also reviews the current background review regarding the microalgae growth parameters, various traditional latest pre-treatment techniques and extraction methodologies to generate lipids from the microalgae. Results from the previous research of lipid enhancement were reported in this chapter which also includes an analysis of fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) properties for various algal biofuels. This chapter concludes by identifying a research gap in the existing literature pertaining to the utilisation of microalgae for lipid extraction and subsequent transesterification into biodiesel.

Chapter 3 explores the materials, methods & experimental methodology planned to work in this research. This gap is found in the previous research and studies observed from the literature review regarding the generation of lipids from microalgae. This draws together the culturing conditions for algal growth and the algal pre-treatment techniques used in this research. The

methods of extracting lipids using methanol, conc sulphuric acid and hexane solvents to generate lipid productivity from microalgae *Chlorella Vulgaris* & *Nannochloropsis Oculata* and FAME composition is discussed in this chapter. This chapter describes the influence of the design of experiments using response surface methodologies (RSM) to predict the efficiency and optimisation of the produced model.

Chapter 4 details the results generated from the microalgae *Chlorella Vulgaris*. The chapter focuses on implementing a Response Surface Methodology (RSM) approach to establish an effective pre-treatment technique to produce algal biodiesel. The chapter proceeds to present and discuss the experimental findings, along with a statistical analysis, highlighting their significance in relation to existing studies. The obtained results are meticulously analysed and interpreted to shed light on the effectiveness of the developed pre-treatment technique. The significance of these findings is discussed in the context of the current body of research, emphasising how they contribute to the field of microalgal pre-treatment.

In Chapter 5, the experimental results obtained from microalgae *Nannochloropsis Oculata* are detailed. The chapter focuses on the development of a mathematical model using the design of experiments to analyse both the actual and predicted values. The chapter proceeds to present and discuss the experimental findings, providing a thorough statistical analysis that highlights their significance in relation to Literature. The results are carefully examined, allowing for a comprehensive interpretation of their implications for the effectiveness of the pre-treatment technique developed.

Chapter 6 focuses on the discussion and comparison of the gas chromatography (GC) results obtained from the extracted lipids. The chapter includes a detailed analysis of the biodiesel concentration derived from these lipids. Additionally, the fundamental concepts underlying the extraction analysis are explained, providing a comprehensive understanding of the lipid extraction process employed for the specific microalgal species investigated in this study.

Chapter 7 presents the final conclusion, highlighting the summary of the research findings and recommendations for future studies.

Chapter 2 Literature review

2.1 Introduction to biodiesel

The need for an alternative to fossil fuel is increasing daily, and research is being carried out every day to find a new solution or update the available solutions. Environmental change such as global warming caused due to increase in carbon-di-oxide levels becomes promising to find an alternative renewable fuel. Biodiesel is at the forefront of switching over to green energy with very few changes in engine infrastructure and requiring less implementation to the fuel supply chain. Governments all around the globe are already passing legislation for the usage of biofuels to fight global warming. EU policy requires at least 10% of transport fossil fuel to become a renewable source. The initial United States government legislation says that from May 2013, there is a requirement of 25% ethanol for gasoline blends (*ExxonMobil Affiliate to Produce Renewable Diesel to Help Reduce Transportation Emissions - Energy Factor*, no date). USA targeted to increase their gasoline blends to 34 billion litres of renewable fuel to 164 billion litres by 2022 (*Overview for Renewable Fuel Standard | US EPA*, no date). The international energy agency (IEA) estimates that by 2050, about 20% of liquified fuels will emerge from biofuels around the globe (*Energy Technology Perspectives 2020 – Analysis - IEA*, no date). Worldwide biodiesel production was estimated to be around 1.8 billion litres in 2003 (Medipally *et al.*, 2015) and 40 billion litres (*• Major biodiesel producing countries 2019 / Statista*, no date) in 2019. A forecast of biofuel production in in 2019 to 2025 is represented in Figure 2. 1.

A sharp increase in biodiesel production was observed for the past 15 years, which may go up in the future as well. This estimate stresses the fuel producers to find enormous amounts of materials and resources to find a way to produce more fuel in a short period. Algae are excellent biodiesel producers and are best in cultivation, and they are high in economic potential with a fair bio compound. A typical large scale algal cultivation is shown in Figure 2. 2. Algae are also proven to show decreased carbon-di-oxide levels after combustion (Gouveia and Oliveira, 2009a).

Figure 2. 1: Forecast of Global biofuel production in 2019 to 2025 (*Global biofuel production in 2019 and forecast to 2025 – Charts – Data & Statistics - IEA, no date*)

Figure 2. 2: Algal power plant in Germany(*Algal biofuels, no date*).

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Figure 2. 3: Major biodiesel producing countries 2019 (• *Major biodiesel producing countries 2019* | Statista, no date)

Recently, microalgae have gained more attention than most other sources of extractable biofuel. Bio-fuels are fuels produced from agricultural or forestry materials and the biodegradable part of industrial waste (Dufey and International Institute for Environment and Development., 2006). Biofuel extraction has been calculated to be 35 billion litres (Olson and Rosacker, 2013) and the USA, Brazil and European Union are the top producers (Balat, 2007). Bio-diesel is produced out of vegetable oils (Shay, 1993), jatropha curcas (Becker and Makkar, 2008), bio butanol (Dürre, 2007) and algae (Roessler *et al.*, 1994). The Figure 2. 3 shows the major biodiesel producing countries in 2019.

The petrol consumption is said to be depleted in the next 50 years while checking with the current consumption rate. With this, biodiesel has a favourable position to overcome this problem and environmental security factors resulting in less shallow sulphur content and reduced carbon-di-oxide (Antolín *et al.*, 2002; Vicente, Martínez and Aracil, 2004a). Using biodiesel as a renewable energy source, the carbon monoxide and sulphur content can be reduced to 10% and 30%. The exit after the combustion can be changed to an eco-friendly gas

with an increased oxygen level. They do not have any toxic compounds or other chemical elements harmful to the atmosphere. Some investigations concluded that the application of using biodiesel includes a decrease in air toxicity of about 90% on comparing with diesel (Cadenas and Cabezudo, 1998) and they are good in terms of biodegradability and flash point (Ma and Hanna, 1999).

In order to overcome the worldwide energy crisis, the requirement for lipid compounds and other biological materials has been studied to generate biodiesel, which has attracted almost everyone’s interest. Oleaginous microorganisms were also looked forward for high lipid output with a short growth period. Bacterial oils and waste oils are also analysed to study their lipid enhancement, but microalgal oils tops among them with many advantages. The shows the approaches of microalgal to Biodiesel production. The Table 2. 1 shows the comparison of various oil sources along with their advantages and disadvantages. Figure 2. 4 shows the fundamental approaches of microalgae conversion to biodiesel.

Table 2. 1: Different types of oil sources and their comparison

Organism	Pros	Cons
Oil from microalgae	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High fatty acids contents. • High dry weight. • Short growth period • Grows in different conditions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comparing diesel, they have low fuel value. • In some species cultivation cost is high.
Bacterial oils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speed growth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not all bacteria extract lipids
Oleaginous	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More resources are available • Some species gives high lipid content. • Short growth period • Grows in different conditions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex in cultivation and extraction. • High in cultivation cost. • More research are required to explain their extraction process.
Waste oils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cheap oil when comparing with other vegetable oils. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very hard for biodiesel conversion.

Figure 2. 4: Approaches of microalgae to biodiesel

2.2 Microalgae

Microalgae is a green plant-structured algae with known species of 100,000 diatoms. Microalgae has a fast-growing rate of 40 to 50% greater than terrestrial crops and is superior in carbon-di-oxide capacity (Shahid *et al.*, 2020). On culturing this to wastewater land, they have a high capacity to wipe off natural pollutants and reduce the CO₂ content. The latest applications of microalgae are used in wastewater treatment systems where the growth of microalgae has gotten attention (Vo Hoang Nhat *et al.*, 2018). Microalgae contain a large amount of organic matter such as starch, lipids, proteins, cellulose, etc.; extracting this helps to convert to sustainable bio compounds or bioenergy. Every algae differ in its oil content, lipid content, biomass and biodiesel production rate. Even some algal species hold a high protein rate (7 – 51%), a low amount of carbohydrates (4-22%), and low lipid content (4-24%) (Becker, 2007). Hence, not algae provide an effective route for bio-energy but finding a better method in cultivation and extraction has helped to generate an oil content comparable to that of conventional oil sources (Santos-Ballardo *et al.*, 2016). The organic matter is trapped inside the microalgae cell wall/membrane. This barrier makes the extraction process challenging for high-energy input and laboratory processes (Bozarth, Maier and Zauner, 2009). Some microalgae species, like *Botryococcus braunii*, have an effective isoprenoid weight of 70% and provide a lower O₂ level (Araujo *et al.*, 2011). These compounds can provide a vast range of applications in refineries, but this algae is tough to culture, and their growing process is also too slow. Microalgae such as *Chlorella sp* and *Dunaliella sp* have been seen to have a

reasonable growth rate with a cell count doubling in 24 hours period (Medina Félix *et al.*, 2022; Thuy Lan Chi *et al.*, 2022). Other microalgae like *Chlorella gracilis* and *Chlorella Vulgaris*, due to their high carbon content and high saline conditions, have been reported for their extraordinary growth and their ability to produce a large amount of lipid production (Medina Félix *et al.*, 2022; Shan Ahamed *et al.*, 2022; Sherafati *et al.*, 2022). *Nannochloropsis sp* and *Dunaliella sp* grown in marine conditions have been noted for their high stability and hard-to-kill. If they grow in outdoor conditions, they can provide mass culturing for biodiesel (Medina Félix *et al.*, 2022; Shan Ahamed *et al.*, 2022). Figure 2. 5 shows the various microscopic images of microalgal species.

Figure 2. 5: Microalgae species – Microscopic image ((2) (PDF) Isolation and Morphological Identification of Some Indigenous Microalgae from Ethiopia for Phycoprosecting, no date)

Microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* is freshwater unicellular green algae, spherical and without flagella, and grows for a diameter of 2 – 10 µm. This has been researched for years, grown in optimised conditions with CO₂ supply and shown a maximum lipid content of 15-25% (Li *et al.*, 2021). *Chlorella emersonii* has given a higher biodiesel production rate than *Chlorella vulgaris* by modifying growth conditions with low nitrogen levels and pH 6.5 (Demirbaş, Demirbaş and Demirbaş, 2008; Beer *et al.*, 2009).

2.3 Parameters influencing growth

Each microalgal species has parameters of a specific growth rate (μ) curve with lag, exponential, stationary, and death phases. The growth rate of the microalgae is measured using μ^{-1} , the increase of the biomass for a period. The initial stage of the algae starts with a lag time, and after that, the growth rate begins, followed by exponential growth, indicating the increase of cells. Once the exponential growth occurs, it becomes a linear phase showing the light quantity is absorbed, measuring the cell concentration of the microalgae (Metsoviti *et al.*, 2019).

2.3.1 Nutrients

The growth of the algae is influenced by light, CO₂, water supply and some micro/macro nutrients. Some specific nutrients include Nitrogen, Potassium and Phosphorus. The nutrient salts can be either in liquid, solid or semi-solid medium and can support the growth of the algal species. The nitrogen concentration highly influences the microalgae showing a higher growth rate and accumulating a good percentage of lipid output. Each type of growth media is used for different microalgae, like freshwater and marine algae (*Algae Growing Medias - Algae Research Supply*, no date). Ammonia is preferred for some species instead of nitrate salts, which also showed fast growth in microalgal cells. Trace metals, specifically copper, boron, zinc, manganese, iron and molybdenum, are also working on algal growth (Kumar *et al.*, 2010).

To achieve optimal performance of microalgae cultures, it is essential to provide the necessary nutrients in the culture medium. Various nutrient recipes have been developed and widely employed in microalgae culture media, including f/2, Algal, BBM, BG11, CHU-13, and Bold's Basal solution (NAKADA TAKASHI, 2012). These media formulations have been carefully designed to provide the specific nutrients required for robust growth and biomass composition of microalgae. By selecting the appropriate culture medium, researchers can create an environment that supports the maximal performance of microalgae cultures. It is widely acknowledged that maximising the productivity of microalgae cultures can be achieved by operating under nutrient excess conditions. However, it is crucial to determine the optimal level of nutrient excess based on economic and sustainability considerations. Excessive nutrients in the culture system can lead to nutrient wastage if the cultivation medium is not recirculated, which can have negative environmental impacts. Therefore, careful management of nutrient levels is necessary to strike a balance between maximising productivity and minimising

nutrient loss from the system, ensuring both economic efficiency and environmental sustainability (Acién *et al.*, 2017). Using Bold's Basal solution and f/2 media, microalgae strains of *Chlorella* show a high growth rate. CHU-13 medium indicates that it can increase the growth of *Botryococcus braunii*. Limitations in the media occur for certain strains showing slow growth rates.

2.3.2 Light and Light spectrum

Microalgae utilise light as an energy source for photosynthesis, an essential parameter for algal growth. Light availability plays a crucial role in the growth and productivity of photosynthetic microalgal species. It serves as the primary energy source for these organisms and is essential for their optimal functioning. However, it is important to strike a balance in providing sufficient light without subjecting the microorganisms to excessive levels. This is because excessive light, especially when combined with suboptimal temperature or high oxygen levels, can potentially harm the photosynthetic process (Ma *et al.*, 2022). The growth of microalgae relies on their photosynthesis rate, which is directly influenced by the level of irradiance they receive within the culture. Irradiance refers to the total amount of radiation reaching a specific point from all directions and across various wavelengths. It is a crucial factor that determines the availability of energy for photosynthetic processes in microalgae. By optimising the irradiance conditions, it is possible to enhance the growth and productivity of microalgae through efficient utilisation of light energy (Fernández Sevilla *et al.*, 1998).

The light zones in the algal growth are divided into photoinhibition, photolimited and photosaturated zones. Light attenuation occurs inside the algal culture, where the light intensity slowly goes deep inside the media as the light is absorbed by cells, and photons go into the culture due to absorption (Benson and Rusch, 2006). Beer-Lambert Law determines the effect of intensity as the exponential phase decreases (Bernard, 2011; Yuan *et al.*, 2014; Blanken *et al.*, 2016).

$$I = I_0 e^{-kz} \quad \text{Eqn (2.1)}$$

Where, I is the intensity of the light, I_0 is the intensity of light going into the media, z is depth and k is the attenuation rate.

Another element that plays a primary factor in microalgae light exposure is culture hydrodynamics, where the cells move towards the media and the light source. This is very important to find how little light is absorbed due to photosynthesis which helps to find the growth rate. The photosynthesis process has a relationship with electron transfer rate, CO₂ consumption and O₂ development (Metsoviti *et al.*, 2019).

Even though light is one of the major significant factors for growth rate, light intensity is necessary, and the light spectrum also plays a vital role. Some studies suggest that microalgae show an increase in growth rate in light wavelength. The range of the light is said to be photosynthetically active radiation. A research study conducted focused on microalgal culturing using laboratory conditions instead of photobioreactors (PBRs). The study utilised a light intensity of 75 lumens and maintained consistent culturing conditions throughout the entire culturing period for the algal species *Scenedesmus quadricauda* (Onumaegbu *et al.*, 2018a). Wavelength ranging from 500-800nm acts as an energy source for the growth reactions of the microalgae (Sukenic, Falkowski and Bennett, 1987). Blanken et al. (Blanken *et al.*, 2016) proposed an equation to determine the light intensity variations caused by the wavelengths.

$$I(z) = \sum_{500}^{800} \times I_{\lambda}(0) e^{-\alpha_x c_x z} \Delta \lambda \quad \text{Eqn (2.2)}$$

Where $I_{\lambda}(0)$ is the intensity of the light at the assigned wavelength, α_x is the absorption rate of the light, C_x is the concentration of the growing biomass, z is the depth.

2.3.3 Temperature

Next to the nutrients and light, temperature plays a vital role in the microalgal growth rate. Research has been conducted to study the growth rate's effect and how the temperature influences it. Temperature and light are the most common factors influencing the growth in culture conditions with nutrients. Microalgae exhibit optimal growth within a temperature range of 20°C to 35°C, although certain mesophilic species can tolerate temperatures up to 40°C. Deviating from the optimal temperature range can negatively impact the yield of microalgae strains. It is important to avoid overheating the cultures as excessive temperatures can be detrimental and lead to cell death. Striking the right balance in maintaining the

appropriate temperature is crucial for ensuring optimal growth and avoiding thermal stress. (Bernard and Rémond, 2012). Figure 2. 6 depicts the impact of temperature on the growth rates of microalgae, revealing that the optimal growth temperatures vary depending on the specific species.

Figure 2. 6: Temperature influence on microalgae growth rates (Ras, Steyer and Bernard, 2013)

By using photobioreactors, temperature control can be managed. The limitation of the temperature shows that a high temperature can even kill the cells inside the culture. Hence, when culturing in outdoor conditions, the temperature must be considered (Béchet *et al.*, 2010). Some models had been proposed in previous studies to predict the bacterial growth rate using a high temperature and concluded that these increased temperatures could reduce the growth (Ratkowsky *et al.*, 1983).

2.3.4 pH and carbon

Every microalgal species has a different optimum pH for its growth (Moheimani and Borowitzka, 2011). The pH is a parameter affected by the amount of carbon content in the culture media, and the usual way to lower the pH is by pumping CO₂ into the culture. Some culture media are grown by supplying CO₂ as a nutrient for their entire culture period as the algal species require them, and on considering the pH effect, the culture was shown to be diverse (Moheimani and Borowitzka, 2011). Culturing on a large scale with limited carbon, along with the addition of CO₂, enhances biomass productivity and growth, but on another side, they can

also cause acidification to the media (Borowitzka, 1998). Studies with *Emiliana huxleyi* on CO₂ effects resulted in increased organic carbon content while cultured in low nitrogen and potassium (Leonardos and Geider, 2005). *Nannochloropsis sp* density is seen to rise on raising the carbon supply with CO₂ injection, and this maintained a balanced pH between 6.75 – 7.50, where the unsupplied culture showed a rise in pH of 8.25 (Abu-Rezq *et al.*, 1999). pH fluctuations occur day and night due to photosynthesis and respiration caused by the environment. During the day, photosynthesis happens with the rise in CO₂ and pH rise and respiration reverse the process (Arudchelvam and Nirmalakhandan, 2012).

2.3.5 Sterility

It is broadly accepted that some impurities in microalgal cultures must be compromised once operations are intended for small goals in biofuel production and carbon dioxide sequestration. High-value products necessarily involve a more excellent standard of sterilisation during microalgal cultivation. Some organisms' contamination influences the final product quality and affects the efficiency of cell growth in some cases. Nonetheless, precautions need to be taken in the quick stage to avoid over-contamination. Because of the scarcity of organic carbon sources in the entire process, contamination of heterotrophic microorganisms is normally not a serious worry for autotrophic algal culturing facilities. Although monitoring the control of invasive and exotic algal species and predators is critical for the culturing process and the final product quality. PBR culturing is the major problem raised with cleaning the interior walls of the reactor. Culture is typically struck on the wall surfaces, forming a rigid biofilm to remove and increasing the possibility of contamination (Katiyar *et al.*, 2018) (Eldiehy *et al.*, 2022). To increase sterility during algae cultivation, the internal surface of the culture medium should be smooth and internal dimensions should be large enough to allow convenient cleaning (Katiyar *et al.*, 2017).

The introduction of air bubbles into microalgal cultures can pose a risk to cell integrity. Cell damage can occur during various stages, such as bubble ejection from the sparger, bubble breakup or coalescence within the liquid, and bubble bursting at the surface of the culture. It is widely recognised that smaller bubbles have a greater potential for causing damage compared to larger bubbles. Additionally, the height-to-diameter ratio of the system also plays a role, with lower ratios being associated with reduced bubble-induced damage. To mitigate this effect, it is advisable to minimize the air flow rate during aeration. Recommended values

typically fall below $0.1 \text{ v/v}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ to minimise the risk of bubble-related damage to the microalgae cells (Barbosa, Hadiyanto and Wijffels, 2004)

2.4 Transesterification

Transesterification has become the most frequently employed technique for biodiesel production at research labs and industries. The transesterification process involves transforming non-edible or edible oil accompanied by or without a catalyst. To make biodiesel, three moles of alcohol interact with 1 mole of oil (Fatima *et al.*, 2021). Ethanol and methanol are the most common alcohol products used in the transesterification process. Ethanol is derived from agricultural goods, and they are reusable and eco-friendly. As a result, it is preferred in the transesterification process. Methanol is broadly used during transesterification because of its low price and accessibility (Demirbas, 2005) and its high polarity, quick reaction rate and short length (Wilkanowicz *et al.*, 2020). To optimise the conventional methodology, Johnson *et al.* (Johnson and Wen, 2009) described a method for producing biodiesel from dried algal biomass using methanol and chloroform as solvents for extraction. The biodiesel rate was observed to be 15% significantly more significant when compared to the conventional transesterification method.

Biodiesel can be generated by microalgal cell disruption using pre-treatment techniques that help extract lipids. It is also clear that microalgae can produce large amounts of lipids. The Figure 2. 4 represents the approaches of microalgae to biodiesel. Biodiesel is a transesterified product which extracts triglycerides and fatty acids from animal fats, algal oils and crop oils. The chemical structure of the transesterification process is represented in Figure 2. 7.

Figure 2. 7: Transesterification process – Chemical structure (Karak, 2012)

The biodiesel produced from dried microalgal biomass requires the use of a significant quantity of energy for dewatering. Furthermore, if the wet microalgae are converted into biodiesel using the chloroform-transesterification method, the biodiesel yield is less than that generated from the dry biomass. Numerous strategies have concentrated on researching techniques for producing biodiesel from wet microalgal species to reduce energy. In a study, Lee et al. (J. Y. Lee *et al.*, 2010) indicated that after disrupting cell walls with a microwave-assisted technique using methanol and chloroform, the lipid recovery increased to 80% from the wet microalgae. Other organic solvents like carbon tetrachloride, benzene, hexane, chloroform and toluene were used for direct transesterification for producing biodiesel from wet microalgae and using chloroform extraction produced a higher biodiesel rate of 90%. In contrast, the yield got reduced to 35% by using hexane. Moreover, suggested procedures for producing high yields of biodiesels from wet microalgae engaged the utilisation of hazardous chloroform, which is unsuitable because of safety issues (Cheng, Huang, Li, *et al.*, 2014a). Avoiding the usage of catalyst and chloroform, these method involves the transformation of wet algae to biodiesel by using supercritical alcohol (Patil *et al.*, 2011; P. D. Patil *et al.*, 2013; Reddy *et al.*, 2014).

In the transesterification reaction, the triglyceride acts with Alcohol to develop glycerol and esters. In this chemical process, the triglyceride was blended with Alcohol using a catalyst, either Potassium hydroxide (KOH) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH). Throughout the

Figure 2. 9: Transesterification method of microalgae to biofuel production (Alaswad *et al.*, 2015)

For economically viable biodiesel produced from microalgal biomass, the whole procedure should reflect the following characteristics: reduced energy consumption during the conversion, less transesterification cost and lipid extraction process. Therefore, most previous research concluded that biodiesel production derived from lipid conversion could also be successfully used in biogas production (Anaerobic digestion). Whereas if the total production expense of biogas can be limited after commercialisation, the biodiesel sale cost may be actually reduced, raising the chances of algal biodiesel resources competing with fossil fuels more effectively as suggested by (*ExxonMobil Affiliate to Produce Renewable Diesel to Help Reduce Transportation Emissions - Energy Factor*, no date; Kargi and Moo-Young, 1985; Antolín *et al.*, 2002; van Manh *et al.*, 2011; Hernández-Melchor *et al.*, 2017; Lin and Chen, 2017; Gim and Kim, 2018a; Liu *et al.*, 2018; Fatima *et al.*, 2021; Wu *et al.*, 2022).

2.5 Cell morphology

To our knowledge, inter-species diversity in lipid extraction and cell disruption kinetics is still in research. Likewise, cell characteristics such as cell wall concentration, size and thickness, and lipid content may affect the comparative cost of lipid extraction and cell disruption using pre-treatment. The cell wall is the primary obstacle to the diffusion and transit of all compounds in and out of the cell, and the cell wall is likely to be the primary limiting hurdle to the dispersion of lipids from them (Halim, Danquah and Webley, 2012a). Consequently, as the algal species cell wall is relatively resistant to organic solvents, cell disruption becomes much

more essential for enhancing the extraction efficiency of microalgal lipids and other products. The cell wall composition of chlorophyte algae varies significantly, with different combinations of polysaccharide-enclosed substances like glucosamine and cellulose. The study of a case of microalgal cell walls in green algae is fascinating. Most Chlorophyta species have polysaccharide cell walls, whereas some have algaenan cell walls (Kodner, Summons and Knoll, 2009). To optimise species selection and downstream operational conditions in the biorefineries also, it is critical to evaluate the effects of microalgal species on downstream processes. However, apart from cell composition and size, their lipid content plays a vital role in disrupting the cell. Cell size may be significant as the cell develops bigger. The entire surface region surrounded by the lipid content (packed within the cell wall) also increases, and this cell wall growth helps to promote an increase in the amount of lipid enclosed within a particular surface area. The permeability of various cell wall compounds to the varying organic solvents is feasible, and thus, the cell disruption impacts the kinetics of lipid extraction. It is also possible that the different microalgal species and their cell wall have different bio compounds that require varying energy for cell disruption. This can be made possible by pre-treating the microalgae.

2.6 Pre-treatment

In various research studies from around the globe, techniques for pre-treating microalgae are still in development while researchers try to acquire more efficient lipid products. The cell disruption technique involves breaking down the cells within the cell membranes to remove the intercellular products. Cell wall cracking in microalgae poses a substantial obstacle in bioprocessing due to the complex and rigid composition of the cell wall. The cell wall serves as a protective barrier, consisting of intricate arrangements of complex carbohydrates, including cellulose, hemicellulose, and pectin, as well as proteins and other biopolymers. This complex structure restricts the accessibility of intracellular components, impeding efficient extraction and utilisation (Wang *et al.*, 2022). The rigid nature of the cell wall hampers the release of intracellular compounds during bioprocessing. The extraction of valuable constituents, such as lipids, proteins, and pigments, requires effective disruption and breakdown of the cell wall. The efficiency of bioprocessing can be greatly enhanced through cell wall cracking, which aims to disrupt the structural integrity of the cell wall and improve access to intracellular components. By breaking down the complex carbohydrates and other polymers, the release of target compounds can be facilitated. This enables subsequent

extraction, digestion, and conversion processes to be more effective, leading to increased yields and improved product quality (Wood, 2022). Some microalgal species are naturally good for efficient lipid extraction, but that does not apply to all types of algae. It has also been shown that pre-treatment processes consume a lot of energy during cell disruption (Chen *et al.*, 2018). In order to produce significant cell disruption, the right pre-treatment method must be chosen to enhance the disruption efficiency (Dixon and Wilken, 2018). Recent studies have shown that many new cell disruption techniques and methods are involved in the development of bioethanol and biofuels. The major obstacle to the use of biofuels has been the operational costs of large-scale production because the production of biofuels requires more input products (Yoo *et al.*, 2012). However, biofuels are emerging as non-toxic alternative fuel resources that are less harmful to the environment. The use of biodiesel is increasing gradually, and as the demand rises, more pre-treatment methods and techniques are required (Engler, 1985a). A variety of pre-treatment techniques are currently used for cell disruption. These methods are mainly classified into mechanical, physical, thermal, chemical, biological, pulsed electric field, and combined techniques. Mechanical processes are the most widely used methods to reduce the rate of shear force required for cell wall rupture. In recent years, microwave, catalytic, bead beating, autoclaving, enzymatic, ultrasonic, autoclave, steam explosion, high-pressure homogenisation, high-speed homogenisation, and sonication methods have been studied for use in biodiesel applications and have shown good economic efficiency outcomes in large-scale production. It should be noted that the same microalgae can produce divergent lipid productivity results when using different pre-treatment techniques. As such, it is better to conduct a systematic evaluation on how the pre-treatment method influences the cell wall and cell size of a specific microalgae before choosing a certain technique (Medeiros, Kirleis and Vetter, 1978). When comparing the production processes of pre-treated biomass with non-pre-treated biomass, the energy balance favours the former (Mercer and Armenta, 2011). The Table 2. 2 shows the list of microalgal species pre-treated with cell disruption techniques.

Table 2. 2: Lipid extracted after pre-treatment in microalgae.

Microalgae	Pre-treatment technique	Lipid productivity (mg/L/Day)	References
<i>Phaeodactylum tricomutum</i>	Solvent	44.8	(Deshmukh, Kumar and Bala, 2019)
<i>Chaetoceros muelleri</i>	Microwave	21.8	(Sajjadi <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Solvent	17.4	(Sajjadi <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
<i>Botryococcus braunii</i>	Solvent	5.5	(Ferreira <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
<i>Dunaliella tertiolecta</i>	Homogenisation	60.6 – 69.8	(Sajjadi <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
<i>Nannochloropsis oculata</i>	Solvent	84.0 – 142.0	(Deshmukh, Kumar and Bala, 2019)
<i>Scenedesmus sp.</i>	Solvent	40.8 – 53.9	(Deshmukh, Kumar and Bala, 2019)
<i>Chlorella sp.</i>	Autoclaving	42.1	(Ferreira <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Enzymatic	11.2 – 40.0	(Deshmukh, Kumar and Bala, 2019)
<i>Chlorella protothecoides</i>	homogenisation	1214	(Deshmukh, Kumar and Bala, 2019)
<i>Chlorella emersonii</i>	Ultrasonic	10.3 – 50.0	(Deshmukh, Kumar and Bala, 2019)
<i>Pavlova salina</i>	Microwave	49.4	(Deshmukh, Kumar and Bala, 2019)

2.6.1 Mechanical Pre-treatment

Mechanical pre-treatment techniques involve the destruction of the cell wall using shear forces. Mechanical pre-treatment techniques can be classified into the categories of high-pressure homogenisation, high-speed homogenisation, and bead milling (Schütte *et al.*, 1983; Engler, 1985b; Shirgaonkar, Lothe and Pandit, 1998). These methods are proven to extract lipids in a way that enhances large-scale biofuel production (Kargi and Moo-Young, 1985) (Tedesco, Mac Lochlainn and Olabi, 2014). The main objective of these methods is to reduce cell wall particle size and crystallinity at the time of cell disintegration (Greenwell *et al.*, 2010). Mechanical pre-treatment methods have the advantage of preventing the cells from being contaminated and protect cell function from being damaged during cell rupture (Montgomery, 2014). These methods become more effective when used in a combination, and they increase the cell surface area and produce more disruption efficiency (Spiden *et al.*, 2013).

2.6.1.1 High-pressure homogeniser

High-pressure homogenisers (HPHs) are specially made for emulsification techniques. This method is broadly used for the microalgae cell disruption process because of its continuous operation and scalability to generate wet biomass (Ekpeni *et al.*, 2015). The HPH method has been shown to recover more microalgae lipids during cell rupture (Hoare and Dunnill, 1989).

Different types of valve seat formats are available to optimise cell disruption efficiency (Moore, Hoare and Dunnill, 1990). The cells flow through the valve and strike the impact ring, exit the valve, and are discharged. Here, cell disruption is achieved through shear forces due to the impact caused, and hydrodynamic cavitation shows a pressure drop (Halim *et al.*, 2012a). A graphical representation of HSH working principle is shown in Figure 2. 10. HPHs show a higher possibility of obtaining wet microalgae concentrates with 25 W/W% solids for lipid recovery efficiently without consuming more energy (Lee, Lewis and Ashman, 2012a). In industries, pre-treatment methods using high-pressure homogenisers are used for cell disruption in seaweeds and yeast cells to improve lipid production (J.-Y. Lee *et al.*, 2010a). An overview of research studies using this method is shown and discussed in Table 2. 3. The Figure 2. 11 shows the comparison of lipid extraction using different solvent extraction after homogenisation pre-treatment. The list of studies in the Table 2. 3 shows that increasing the pressure and number of cycles will have a good impact on the lipid efficiency. Some studies suggest that lowering the dry cell weight and culture stress levels seems important but that modifying the nozzle diameter does not seem very effective (Halim *et al.*, 2012a). Even though the use of HPHs is the most preferred method, they do have some disadvantages as well. When using a low DCW (0.01–0.85% w/w), the energy demand increases, and the hard cells become challenging to break. This indicates that HPH methods are not mild methods and are not acceptable for breaking fragile elements (Verni *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 2. 10: Schematic diagram of HPH value seat

Figure 2. 11: Comparison of lipid extraction with (●) and without (○) homogenisation extraction of chloroform: methanol in the form of 2:1, v/v (Allali *et al.*, 2012).

Table 2. 3: Overview of the previous research studies – High pressure homogeniser

Microalgae	Operating conditions	Output studied	Review	Reference
<i>Nannochloris oculata</i>	68.9 MPa and 310 MPa using a nozzle diameter of 130 mm and 185 mm respectively, 6 passes. – 100ml	Efficiency increased.	Biodiesel production, Total lipids.	(Lee, Lewis and Ashman, 2012b)
	1% DCW, 125 MPa, 5 passes.	Efficiency of 200 (mg/g cell)c	Biodiesel production, Total lipids.	(Shene <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
<i>Chlorococcum sp.</i>	0.85% DCW, 8Mpa, 4 passes – 200ml	90% cell disruption achieved.	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Halim <i>et al.</i> , 2012a)
<i>Tetraselmis suecica</i>	86 MPa. 0.85% DCW, 5 passes – 200ml	34.157 cell/mm ³ cell concentration	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Halim <i>et al.</i> , 2012a)
<i>Auxenochlorella protothecoides</i>	150Mpa, 5 passes.	yields up to 35% (dry weight)	Perfect cell count. Protein analysis	(Papachristou <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
	Energy input of 1.5 MJ/kg Dry Weight – 40ml			
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	150Mpa, 5 passes.	~25% (dry weight) protein release	Perfect cell count. Protein analysis	(Papachristou <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
	Energy input of 1.5 MJ/kg Dry Weight – 40ml			
<i>Nannochloropsis sp.</i>	150Mpa, 1% DCW, Nitrogen added, 6 passes – 250ml	90% protein achieved.	protein analysis	(Grimi <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>Chlorella saccharophila</i>	200 to 1000 bar, t-butanol, ammonium sulphate.	Efficiency of 400 (mg/g cell)c	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Mulchandani, Kar and Singhal, 2015)

2.6.1.2 Bead mills

Bead mills are widely used for lipid extraction during microalgae cell disruption. They provide good disruption efficiency in a single pass, and their industrial implementation values include temperature maintenance, easy operating procedures, large biomass set up, and easily available equipment. (Bierau, Zhang and Lyddiatt, 1999). The Figure 2. 12 below shows the basic components of bead mills. They are classified into two types: agitated vessels and shaking vessels. Shaking vessels can be used to disrupt cells by vibrating the whole vessel. Agitated vessels use a spinning agitator that is filled with cell culture and beads. The cell disruption rate depends on size of the beads, the rigidity of the cell, and the biomass material of the microalgal cell (Halim *et al.*, 2013). It is theorised that after shear force is applied, the cells will be disrupted in the bead collision zones, and the energy will be transferred from the beads to the cells (Melendres *et al.*, 1992)(Bunge *et al.*, 1992). The Figure 2. 13 shows the developing characterisation of microalgae under nitrogen starvation in bead milling process. An overview of the literature is shown in Table 2. 4 and discussed below.

Based on the case studies from the literature, various factors such as feed rate suspension, continuous operation, bead diameter, bead density, milling chamber design, biomass concentration, agitator design, agitator speed, bead filling, and the processing time of each batch affects the cell disruption rate during bead mill pre-treatment processes (Huang, Bandyopadhyay and Bose, 2005) It can be also said that increasing the size of the beads will show more effective results than using small (0.5 mm) beads. The selected case studies also show that it is best to use low-density beads for low-viscosity media and high-density beads for high-viscosity media (Doucha and Lívanský, 2008)(Schütte *et al.*, 1983). In spite of their advantages, their cons include their high energy demands and high operational costs, which makes this method less preferred for industries.

Figure 2. 12: Schematic view of wet bead milling process (Nekkanti, Vabalaboina and Pillai, 2012)

Figure 2. 13: Developing characterisation of microalgae under nitrogen starvation in bead milling process (Taleb *et al.*, 2016)

Table 2. 4: Overview of the previous research studies – Bead milling

Microalgae	Operating conditions	Output studied	Review	Reference
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	25 gDW L ⁻¹ biomass concentration, 2039 rpm, protease, and cellulase (2% v/w, 1:1), 45° C, 24 h - 75ml	75% Lipid recovery (solid phase)	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Alavijeh <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Nannochloropsis sp</i>	3 kw 0.5 beads, 4500 rpm/10mins – 25ml	Highest biomass concentration and COD reduction of 1.268 g/L and 71%, respectively	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Emparan <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	speed of the agitator set with 10 m ⁻¹ and a power of 24.5 kW for 90 mins	95% increase in cell disruption	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Schwenzfeier, Wierenga and Gruppen, 2011)
	3.3kW, 0.40–0.50 mm beads, 10.7% Dry cell weight. – 1.4L	99% cell disintegration	Perfect cell count. Total lipids	(Doucha and Lívanský, 2008)
	(25–145 gDW kg ⁻¹) and agitator speeds (6–12 m s ⁻¹)	97% cell disintegration	Perfect cell count. Protein analysis	(Postma <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
<i>Nannochloropsis oculata</i>	175 MPa, Chloroform, methanol	Efficiency of 2.8 (mg/g cell)c	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Taleb <i>et al.</i> , 2016)

2.6.1.3 High-Speed homogeniser

High-speed homogenisers (HSH) are devices that use a stirring mechanism that rotates at very high rpm and that consist of rotors and stators that are preferably assembled out of stainless steel. Cell disruption occurs when the cutting spindle rotates at a high speed, causing hydrodynamic cavitation and high shear forces inside microalgal cells by breaking their cell walls and extracting the intercellular elements from them. According to cell wall characteristics, operating conditions such as the homogenising speed, number of passes, and running period can be optimised to increase efficiency (Singh *et al.*, 2022a). The HSH

technique is a very simple but very aggressive cell disruption technique that achieves effective results. The main advantage of this process is its short operating time and its potential to generate lipids and other compounds. Some of the research was conducted to increase the extraction yield using different species and biochemicals (Balasubramanian, Yen Doan and Obbard, 2013). The main disadvantages of this technique are the high operational costs, the protein denaturation caused due to the shear force, and the increase thermal effect, and these make this technique less favourable for biorefinery industries (Engler, 1985b). An overview of studies from the literature using this method is shown in Table 2. 5.

Table 2. 5: Overview of the previous research studies – High-Speed homogeniser

Microalgae	Operating conditions	Output studied	Review	Reference
<i>Synechococcus sp.</i>	10000 rpm for 1 min (5 cycles)	8.82% lipid recovery	Total lipids.	(Wang, Yin and Zeng, 2022a)
<i>Porphyridium cruentum</i>	5500 rpm for 10 min	ω 3-PUFA food products	Perfect cell count,	(Bernaerts <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
<i>Laminaria digitata</i>	150 – 500 bar for 15 min	20% lipid content	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Malafrente <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
<i>Chlorella sp.</i>	12000rpm for 15 mins	Lipid efficiency of 13.05%	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Singh <i>et al.</i> , 2022b)
<i>Nannochloropsis sp.</i>	Speed of 10000 rpm – 1 min – 15ml	Dry extraction yield of 75%	Total lipids.	(Wang and Wang, 2012)

2.6.2 Physical pre-treatment

Physical pre-treatments involve the application of mechanical forces such as shear force, microwaves, and ultrasound. Physical pre-treatment methods have advantages such as cost effectiveness, ease of commercialisation, and time saving. They consist of two major classifications: microwave and ultrasound methods.

2.6.2.1 Ultrasound Pre-treatment

During ultrasonic pre-treatment, acoustic or sound energies of high-frequency waves are generated. By transmitting these shock waves into the cell wall, they cause cell disruption because of their high shear force. The pressure variation in these waves can produce cavitation within the cell (Chisti and Moo-Young, 1986)(Shi *et al.*, 2021). The impact of ultrasound waves is mostly influenced by the cell wall structure and composition of the microalgae (Figure 2. 14). The Figure 2. 15 shows Ultrasonic system schematic representation along with their necessary parts. Because of high temperature and pressure levels, the cavitation generates chemical reactions that are able to destroy organic matter and produce shear force, leading to the creation of H^+ and OH^- reactive radicals (Alzate *et al.*, 2012a). The ultrasound method is used in various applications, such as in olive mill wastewater, chicken and cattle manure, and sludge (González-Fernández *et al.*, 2012a) (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). Microalgae biomass efficiency has been successfully increased to between 16% and 100% with high acoustic energy input. One study observed that there was no improvement in *spirulina maxima* when a semi continuous reactor was used. This was mainly because of the characteristics of microalgae, which have a soft cell wall (Samson and Leduy, 1983). High temperatures should be avoided when using the ultrasound technique, as they result in the loss of volatile organics and reduce biomass production. This was suggested during a study with *Nannochloropsis salina*, which showed lower biomass yield when compared to raw biomass (Schwede *et al.*, 2011). A review of case studies is shown in Table 2. 6.

Figure 2. 14: Graphical show of *Scenedesmus obliquus* for ultrasonic pre-treatment (Goswami and Kalita, 2011)

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Table 2. 6: Overview of the previous research studies - Ultrasonic

Microalgae	Operating conditions	Output studied	Review	Reference
<i>Botryococcus sp.</i>	0.5% DCW, 5mins, 10kHz. – 100ml	8.8% lipid recovery	Total lipids.	(J.-Y. Lee <i>et al.</i> , 2010b)
<i>Salvinia molesta.</i>	5 mins and frequency of 2 kHz – 100ml	19.7% increased lipid content	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Mubarak, Shaija and Suchithra, 2016)
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	20 kHz using 750 W for different time of 0, 5, 10, and 20 mins at 25°C	23% lipid content	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Halim <i>et al.</i> , 2012a; Khan, Park and Maeng, 2022a)
<i>Chlorella sp.</i>	20 kHz, 0.8 kW-hr/L cells	Efficiency of 12.6 (mg/g cell)c	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Natarajan <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>Schizochytrium sp.</i>	150 W, time for 30 min, with temperature 50 °C	Oil yields up to 93.76 (dry weight)	Total lipids.	(Hao <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
<i>Scenedesmus sp.</i>	20w and frequency 18Hz for 5s.	21.3% to 28.3% lipid yield	Perfect cell count. Protein analysis	(Ren <i>et al.</i> , 2019a; Papachristou <i>et al.</i> , 2020)

Figure 2. 15: Ultrasonic system schematic representation. a - Transducer, b – Thermometer, c - Ultrasonic reactor, d - Cryostat, e - Ultrasonic generator (Chuah *et al.*, 2017).

When pre-treating with ultrasonication, the working temperature significantly increases from around 50 to 90 °C, which also kills proteins and other intercellular elements (Borthwick *et al.*, 2005a). The disadvantage of this method is its low disruption efficiency. Lipid quality can be increased with temperature control, but this decreases the efficiency slightly (Hao *et al.*, 2021).

2.6.2.2 Microwave techniques

Microwave techniques use optimal electromagnetic waves with frequencies ranging from 0.3 to 300 GHz that are used to heat localised areas. Here, the microwaves increase the kinetic energy of water molecules until they reach their boiling state (Rodriguez *et al.*, 2015). Microwave treatments produce thermal radiation, and this effect is said to increase the temperature due to polarised macro molecules. The Figure 2. 16 shows the microwave assisted pretreatment in biomass and solvent technique for biodiesel production. These modules are aligned around the pole of the electromagnetic field, which is where hydrogen ions break down (P. Patil *et al.*, 2013). The pressure and the heat energy produced by microwaves cause damage to the cell wall and cell membranes (Choi *et al.*, 2006). A review of case studies using microwave techniques is shown in Table 2. 7.

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Table 2. 7: Overview of the previous research studies - Microwave

Microalgae	Operating conditions	Output studied	Review	Reference
<i>Nannochloropsis oceanica</i>	Power of 1025 W and frequency of 245 MHz for 15 mins	38.46% Lipid production	Total lipids.	(Cheng, Huang, Yu, <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>Yarrowia lipolytica</i>	900W power and a frequency of 245 MHz For 15 minutes	lipid production of 8.18%	Total lipids.	(Mubarak, Shaija and Suchithra, 2016)
<i>Chlorella sp.</i>	For 15mins, 450W power. Biomass & methanol ratio of 1:12 (w/v), Catalyst – KOH	32.18% lipid content	Biodiesel, Total lipids.	(Kalsum <i>et al.</i> , 2018a; Qadariyah <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
	Power of 450W, time of 60mins. Catalyst – 0.2 M H ₂ SO ₄ – 5 mins	75.68% (FAME for biodiesel production)	Biodiesel, Total lipids.	(Qadariyah <i>et al.</i> , 2018a)
	2450 MHz and temperature of 100 °C, 5 mins	Increased lipid efficiency.	Total lipids.	(Zheng <i>et al.</i> , 2011a)
<i>Botryococcus braunii</i>	Power 1250 W, Frequency 2450 MHz, at 150°C - 20 min	Enhanced lipid efficiency.	Biodiesel production, Total lipids.	(Gim and Kim, 2018a; Hao <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
<i>Nannochloropsis sp.</i>	65 °C - 25 min	42.22% dry biomass yield for biodiesel	Biodiesel production, Total lipids.	(Wahidin <i>et al.</i> , 2018a)
	1.2 kW power and frequency of 2.45 GHz. 5 – 15 mins.	Increased cell disruption efficiency.	Total lipids.	(Iqbal and Theegala, 2013)
<i>Nannochloropsis oculata</i>	140°C, 15 mins	Lipid content increase: 6.25-fold	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Billler, Friedman and Ross, 2013)

Figure 2. 16: Picture of microwave-assisted treatment for microalgae (Kumar *et al.*, 2020).

2.6.3 Thermal pre-treatment

Thermal pre-treatment methods are techniques in which heat is added to the surface of algal biomass. This makes the microalgae disrupt the chemical bonds inside their cells, improving the solubilisation (Aboufoth, El Gohary and El Monayeri, 2015). They provide high biomass yields and have low energy requirements when compared to other physical pre-treatment methods. Thermal pre-treatments are basically carried out by adding alkali or acidic chemicals to improve the cell disruption efficiency. Despite these high thermal properties, they may produce recalcitrant components that result in low biomass production and cannot be degraded anaerobically (Mahdy *et al.*, 2014). These methods are categorised into two types: steam explosion and autoclaving.

2.6.3.1 Steam explosion

Steam explosion is an economical and effective method that is used in the processing of lignocellulosic components to improve the biomass efficiency. This method uses high temperature from about 160° to 260°C (1.03 – 3.40 MPa) (Velásquez, Ferrando and Salvadó, 2003). By using a catalyst such as NaOH or H₂SO₄, it is possible to obtain enhanced lipid efficiency (Schell *et al.*, 1998). Particle size, chemical composition, and shapes can be modified

via explosive depressurisation and autohydrolysis (Romaní *et al.*, 2013)(Chen *et al.*, 2011). In the search for the best method for cell disruption to enhance efficiency and to extract sugars and carbohydrates, the steam explosion technique is said to be perfect. The application of steam explosion with the acid catalyst method can efficiently extract more lipids (Lorente, Farriol and Salvadó, 2015). A schematic representation of steam explosion reactor is shown in Figure 2. 17. A review of the case studies using steam explosion is shown in Table 2. 8.

Figure 2. 17: Schematic diagram of steam explosion and fractionation reactor (Matsakas *et al.*, 2018).

2.6.3.2 Autoclaving

This method is a heat transfer process that uses an absolute pressure of 0.3 MPa and a temperature of 121 °C for lipid extraction (Olofsson *et al.*, 2014). There are some studies that were conducted using a continuous reactor under a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 15 to 20 days and at a temperature of 95 °C that show a positive energy balance. As such, it is clear there will be good biomass yield achieved by thermal pre-treatment methodologies when they are used in large-scale applications. A review of previous research studies is shown in Table 2. 9 below.

Balancing the energy of biomass production between energy consumed during production and energy harvested in the form of fuel is essential for biomass production to be cost effective. However, some reports suggest that using thermal pre-treatments with microalgae results in a

negative balance (Mahdy *et al.*, 2014). When thermal methods are compared to other pre-treatment techniques such as physical and ultrasound pre-treatment methods, the energy that is consumed is comparatively low (Marsolek *et al.*, 2014).

Table 2. 8: Overview of the previous research studies – Steam explosion

Microalgae	Operating conditions	Output studied	Review	Reference
<u>Steam explosion</u>				
<i>Nannochloropsis gaditana</i> sp.	150 °C for 5 mins	Lipid recovery 0.3–3.6%	Total lipids.	(Nurra <i>et al.</i> , 2014a)
<i>Chlorella sorokiniana</i>	120 °C for 5 mins	17.9% and 18.2% lipid extraction	Total lipids.	(Lorente, Farriol and Salvadó, 2015)
<i>Scenedesmus dimorphus</i>	100°C – 130°C	Enchanted solubilization	Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Sarat Chandra <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>Botryococcus braunii</i>	90°C, 10mins	Hydrocarbon (0.4% at 75 °C). 97.8 wt% recovery	Biodiesel production Perfect cell count, Total lipids.	(Kita <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
<i>Scenedesmus</i> sp.	90°C	Efficient cell disruption	Total lipids.	(Marsolek <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>Nannochloropsis</i>	30°C and 60°C	biomass yield of 41%	Total lipids.	(Marsolek <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>Chlorella pyrenoidosa</i>	130 °C for 60 mins – 10ml	2.1-fold increased lipid recovery	Total lipids.	(Song <i>et al.</i> , 2021)

Table 2. 9: Overview of the previous research studies –Auto-claving

Microalgae	Operating conditions	Output studied	Review	Reference
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	100 °C for 10 min – 200ml	15.4% Lipid yield	Total lipids.	(Florentino de Souza Silva <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
	100 °C, 1.5 MPa - 5 min	lipid content of 29.34%	Total lipids.	(J.-Y. Lee <i>et al.</i> , 2010a).
	121°C with 0.1 MPa for 5 min	lipid content of 24%	Total lipids.	(Prabakaran and A. D. Ravindran, 2011)
<i>Botryococcus sp.</i>	125 °C with 1.5 MPa for 5 min	5.4–11.9% Lipid recovery	Total lipids.	(J. Y. Lee <i>et al.</i> , 2010)

Balancing the energy of biomass production between energy consumed during production and energy harvested in the form of fuel is essential for biomass production to be cost effective. However, some reports suggest that using thermal pre-treatments with microalgae results in a negative balance (Mahdy *et al.*, 2014). When thermal methods are compared to other pre-treatment techniques such as physical and ultrasound pre-treatment methods, the energy that is consumed is comparatively low (Marsolek *et al.*, 2014).

2.6.4 Chemical treatment

Chemical treatments are ways of introducing chemical substances such as alkaline or organic solvents, detergents, chaotropes, antibiotics, hypochlorites, and chelating agents to enhance cell disruption. Usually, alkaline pre-treatment methods using alkaline compounds such as potassium, sodium hydroxide, and calcium at pH levels varying from 9 to 12 are applied for algal biomass. Acid pre-treatments are carried out by exposing H₂SO₄ and HCl at lower pH levels. Antibodies have the ability to extract lipids from cell membrane components by inhibiting them from the inside, whereas chelating agents cross-couple the cell membrane

molecules to cause disruption. Detergents mix with membrane molecules, with the solvents in them dissolving and piercing the cell membrane and cell wall (Halim *et al.*, 2012a; Miranda, Passarinho and Gouveia, 2012). Oxidising agents such as hydrogen peroxide and ozone are used to disrupt cell walls. The energy required to enhance biomass is also too low compared to other methods such as physical or thermal ones (Kendir and Ugurlu, 2018). Even though chemical pre-treatment methods are generally used for pre-treating cells, studies using them for microalgae biomass production are not as common as those using physical or thermal methods. The major problem with using chemical pre-treatments methods is that they are corrosive and toxic and may also produce inhibitory components. They may also lead to contamination (Gonzalez-Fernandez *et al.*, 2018).

Scenedesmus and *Chlorella* biomass showed pH improvements from 9 to 11 when chemical pre-treatment methods were used. By increasing the pH to 13, the microalgal cells were damaged because of the high alkalinity. It is also stated that low positive total energy values were attained in all cases (Cho *et al.*, 2013). Other studies concluded that treating *Chlorella* sp. and *Nannochloropsis* sp. with different alkaline solutions has a negative effect, as these microalgae have robust cell wall conditions (Bohutskyi, Betenbaugh and Bouwer, 2014). Using oxidising agents on microalgae looks challenging when compared to acid or alkali pre-treatment methods to generate biomass. Microalgae biomass is limited when it is pre-treated by ozonation. Applying ozone pre-treatments to the biomass improved energy efficiency from 6% to 66% at different stages (Cardeña *et al.*, 2017). Apart from these chemical methods, TiO₂ and hydroxyl radicals should also be studied to see if they increase biomass energy. These methods comprise different categories: solvent pre-treatments, catalytic pre-treatments, alkali and acid treatments, and enzymatic treatment.

2.6.4.1 Solvent pre-treatment

Biochemicals such as c-phycoyanin, astaxanthin, etc., are used as solvents to extract lipids. Studies report that some amine solvents can be used for cell disruption by modifying their polarity by adding them carbon dioxide. It can be said that algal biomass is highly influenced by amine solvents (Jessop and Subramaniam, 2007). Additionally, not all amine solvents react with CO₂, and interaction depends on the polar compounds in the form of algal carbamates. To study this, more studies are needed to determine the properties of the reaction. In order to control the high energy consumption needed at the time of cell disruption and drying,

switchable hydrophilicity solvents (SHSs) can be used. SHSs have the capacity to extract lipids by making contact with the lipids and organic solvents, thus increasing the extraction efficiency (Guo *et al.*, 2022). A review of the relevant research literature is shown in Table 2. 10.

2.6.4.2 Catalytic pre-treatments

These methods comprise heterogeneous and homogeneous catalytic pre-treatment methods for biodiesel production (Atadashi *et al.*, 2013). Studies have noted that the use of a homogeneous catalyst in the process of biodiesel production results in advantages such as product purification, the reusability and recovery of the catalyst, lower water consumption, and less energy (Vicente, Martínez and Aracil, 2004b). Research using 1 wt% of homogenous catalysts such as CH₃ONa, CH₃OK, NaOH, and KOH for biodiesel production with the addition of sunflower oil at a temperature of 60 °C for 3 h resulted in a biodiesel yield of 91.22% (Li *et al.*, 2011). A review of previous research studies is shown in Table 2. 11.

2.6.4.3 Enzymatic treatment

This is a biochemical method that requires a mechanical technique, has a lower energy requirement, and can cause cells to rupture to achieve effective lipid production for biodiesel (Mercer and Armenta, 2011). Cell efficiency can be improved by this technique, as the extraction process works with cellulose, alkaline protease, sanilase, and papain (Taher *et al.*, 2014). Supercritical CO₂ (SC-CO₂) is the most broadly used process for the enzymatic pre-treatment for the cell rupture; it also has the ability to convert lipase formation to produce extraction catalytic stability (Gießauf and Gamse, 2000). The process is non-flammable, inexpensive, and inert in nature, so it is very suitable for biodiesel production (Kondo *et al.*, 2002) (Tewari *et al.*, 2004). Additionally, enzymatic pre-treatment demonstrates an advantage when using rapeseed oil during the pre-treatment process, as it can separate microalgal strains and glycerol (Besa, 2018). A review of previous research studies is shown in Table 2. 12.

Table 2. 10: Overview of the previous research studies – Solvent treatment

Microalgae	Operating conditions	Output studied	Review	Reference
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Amine solvents (dimethylbutylamine, dipropylamine, ethylbutylamine, phenethylamine, and Dimethylcyclohexylamine) + culture mixed in ratio of 1:1 with CO ₂ treatment – 50ml	Lipid extraction yield of 9.16%	Total lipids	(Choi and Lee, 2022)
<i>Chlorella sp</i>	Dimethylbenzylamine solvent, Culture (1:1 ratio for 1 hr extraction time)	Lipid extraction of 25.97,32 and 40.8%.	Total lipids	(Anto, Premalatha and Mathimani, 2022)
<i>Scenedesmus</i>	hexane: isopropanol (3:2) and solvent: Culture (75:1) for 2 hr extraction time.	FAMEs of 13% and total lipids, with polar FAME about 1.5% of total lipids	Biodiesel Production. Total lipids.	(Lage <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
<i>Nannochloropsis oceanica</i>	TEPDA solvent: culture (1:4 ratio with 2 hr extraction time)	98.2% of lipid extraction efficiency.	Biodiesel Production. Total lipids.	(Guo <i>et al.</i> , 2022)

Table 2. 11: Overview of the previous research studies – Catalytic treatment

Microalgae	Operating conditions	Output studied	Review	Reference
<i>Nannochloropsis sp.</i>	Mixing 10% of Mg and Zr for 4 hours at a temperature of 65°C	biodiesel Potassium hydroxide yield of 28.0%.	Biodiesel Production. Total lipids.	(Wimmer and Zarevúcka, 2010)
<i>Monoraphidium sp.</i>	2ml hexane and 5ml of 20% saturated NaCl solution.	82.86% of saponifiable components and 17.14% of unsaponifiable components.	Total lipids.	(Delmiro <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	dried in oven at 48 h at 100 °C	Lipid yield of 53.25%	Total lipids.	(Raheem <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
	220 °C, 2 hr methanol per gram of biomass - 8 ml	Biodiesel yield of 74.6%	Biodiesel Production. Total lipids.	(Felix <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
<i>Scenedesmus acutus</i>	dried in vacuum of 60 °C for 20 hr.	~99 wt% hydrocarbons for biodiesel. 12.6% of extracted lipids.	Biodiesel Production. Total lipids.	(Santillan-Jimenez <i>et al.</i> , 2016)

Table 2. 12: Overview of the previous research studies – Enzymatic treatment

Microalgae	Operating conditions	Output studied	Review	Reference
<i>Rhodotorula glutinis</i>	Adding glycerol, AA and ChCl with 60°C for 120 mins, solid–liquid ratio is 1:20	Lipid yield improved by 32.1% and 54%	Total lipids	(Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	12 hrs hydrolysis by protease 2% (v/w) enzymes at 45°C for 45 mins 12 hrs hydrolysis by cellulase (2% v/w) enzymes at 45°C for 45 mins	44% lipid yield.	Total lipids	(Alavijeh <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
	Enzymatic hydrolysis was performed at pH 4.8 and 50 °C for 72 hrs.	1.10–1.69-fold and 85.3% hydrolysis yield.	Total lipids.	(Lee <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
	Mixing sanilase and trypsin enzymes for hydrolysis.	30% of lipid yield	Total lipids.	(Liang, Zhang and Cong, 2012)
<i>Scenedesmus sp.</i>	Culture + Supercritical SC-CO ₂ . enzyme was loaded with 15% to 50% and methanol was loaded at a liquid molar ratio of (3 - 15:1) with a temperature about 35 °C – 55 °C.	biodiesel yield was obtained	Biodiesel Production. Total lipids.	(Taher <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>Nannochloropsis sp.</i>	Enzymatic treatment with 50 °C for 30 mins and a pH of 4.	90.0% lipid yield.	Total lipids.	(Wu <i>et al.</i> , 2017)

2.6.5 Biological pre-treatment

Biological pre-treatments involve three factors: fungi, bacterial, and enzyme activity. These methods are considered to have low investment requirements, mild operating conditions, and less energy consumption and represent the best alternative to the aggressive mechanical techniques (Harrison, 1991). Lipases, glucanases, peptidases and glycosidases are also the most used enzyme classification methods to disrupt the cell wall. During the process, the enzymes mix inside a molecule inside the cell wall/membrane and break the bonds, resulting in cell disruption (McKenzie and White, 1991) To enhance the algal biomass, an enzyme or mixture can be increased. The mixture mostly contains cellulose, starch-degrading enzymes, and hemicellulose (Lucy F. R. Montgomery and Günther Bochmann, 2014). Biological methods may be the best alternative to chemical and physical methods, as they avoid causing inhibitory problems; they are effective low-temperature alternative techniques to thermal pre-treatment methods (Zheng *et al.*, 2011b). The major disadvantage of biological methods is that they need 10–14 days, much longer than all of the other pre-treatment methods; they also need a big space to be carried out on an industrial scale. These methods can be used by themselves or can be combined with other pre-treatment techniques if the concentration of the recalcitrant compound is very high (Kumar *et al.*, 2009). Some studies have shown that biological pre-treatment methods are mainly used for commercial enzymes and result in high methane output (Fu *et al.*, 2010). Biological pre-treatment methods also include algicidal pre-treatments, which consist of viruses, cyanobacteria, bacteria, and microalgae themselves. They have the capability to attack the extracellular compounds on the microalgae to extract the lipids (Demuez, González-Fernández and Ballesteros, 2015). The use of *Chlorella vulgaris* ESP-31 with bacterium *Flammeovirga yaeyamensis* for oil extraction over a 3-day-long pre-treatment process showed enzymes breakage in xylanase, amylase, and cellulase with a high lipid content of 21.5% (Chen, Bai and Chang, 2013). Furthermore, a similar investigation of *Nannochloropsis* sp. biomass with different combinations of lysozyme, protease, cellulose, and pectinase enzymes showed a higher lipid content than when a single enzyme was used (Wu *et al.*, 2017).

2.6.6 Supercritical fluid extraction

This method is said to be one of the best and most effective techniques for lipid extraction processes and is eco-friendly (Abrahamsson *et al.*, 2018; Patil *et al.*, 2018b). This method requires the pressure and temperature to be increased more than the critical point to induce cell breakage. Substances such as CO₂, ammonia, methanol, and others can be used as supercritical extractants, and SC-CO₂ is the most commonly used substance due to its low cost, low temperature, and low pressure (Nagappan *et al.*, 2019). Lipids can be also directly transesterified into biodiesel using this method (Lee, Posarac and Ellis, 2012). A study with the microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis oculata* in combination with ethanol as a co-solvent resulted in cell disruption and extracted lipid percentages of 97% and 83% (Obeid *et al.*, 2018). A similar study conducted by Viguera *et al.* (Viguera *et al.*, 2016) using *Chlorella protothecoides* microalgal species at 70 °C and 300 bars resulted in a higher lipid yield rate. SC-CO₂ along with *n*-hexane was used for lipid extraction in the microalgae *Schizochytrium* sp., and the results suggested that the lipid efficiency extracted from SC-CO₂ was more than the efficiency obtained from *n*-hexane (Zinnai *et al.*, 2016). Another study compared Bligh–Dyer with SC-CO₂ using *Scenedesmus obtusiusculus* and *Scenedesmus obliquus* at 12 Mpa and 20 °C and found that the lipid extraction rate was higher than 90% in the SC-CO₂ process, and the author suggested that this method is good for industrial purposes (Lorenzen *et al.*, 2017). Using ethanol as a co-solvent in *Pavlova lutheri*. with various operating and extraction conditions, De Melo *et al.* achieved 3.5-fold and 7.9-fold higher extraction than fish oil (de Melo *et al.*, 2020). The main problem lies in this method with their high price equipment and their limitation in large scale application.

2.6.7 Pulsed electric treatment

Pulsed electric and high-intensity field pulsed methods are techniques that use electric fields to disrupt the cell and produce lipid extraction. This produces electro-mechanical vibrations and an electric field that creates tension in the cell wall/membrane (Sheng, Vannela and Rittmann, 2011). The high-strength power of ~30 kV passes through the cell wall/membrane, and by increasing the power of the electric field by ~2000 Hz, a large number of dissimilar electric charges pass over the dipolar molecules and break large elements, decreasing the complex molecular forms and piercing into the cell (Michael B Salerno *et al.*, 2009). When the electric field exceeds a specific voltage, the inner pressure generated within the membrane creates an unequal amount of energy in an attempt to form unrepairable pores in the cell (Schoenbach *et*

al., 2000). This pulse electric not only kills all of the cells in the membranes, but also attacks the molecular components within the cell. This technique also affects the nutritional products and the proteins due to the very high temperature. This method has the advantage of being combined with other methods to achieve efficient cell disruption, but the solution that is added should be ion free. When treating marine algae with this pulse effect, the microalgae need to be prewashed and deionised to improve the ability of the pulse field to pass into them. This pre-treatment method produces mixed outputs. A study showed that less than 5% biogas was produced from the biomass (Michael B. Salerno *et al.*, 2009). Due to these problems, this method is not favoured by biorefineries.

2.6.8 Combined Pre-treatment methods

Combining various pre-treatment techniques can be used to reduce costs and enhance efficiency. Thermochemical pre-treatment methods are a blend of thermal and chemical methods, and when applied to *spirulina* biomass, they showed low biogas production, as these methods use toxic and chloride-based chemicals with a low pH (Samson and Leduy, 1983). Research using combined processes used the microwave and bead mills pre-treatment processes along with cell shattering via high-frequency shock (Cravotto *et al.*, 2008)(Viro *et al.*, 2008). The sonication method breaks the cell wall and reduces the size because of the cavitation effect (Lee, Yoon and Oh, 1998). Cell disruption occurred during bead beating in the microalgal cells due to the high-speed spinning beads (Alzate *et al.*, 2012b) (González-Fernández *et al.*, 2012b). The amount of energy can be reduced for lipid extraction by combining ultrasonic and chemical cell disruption methods (Prabakaran and A.D. Ravindran, 2011). There are fewer studies on the use of combined methods compared to those highlighting the use of single pre-treatment methods, so future studies can focus on using combining methods for cell disruption. A list of previous studies is shown in Table 2. 13.

Table 2. 13: Overview of the previous research studies – Combined pre-treatment methods.

Species	Treatment type	Operating conditions	Production yield	References
<i>Chlorella sp.</i>	Homogenisation + Thermal	84 MPa (123 °C and pH of 1.5, Chloroform, methanol)	Efficiency of 4.5 (mg/g cell) ^c	(Spiden <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Microwave + Solvent	700 W, 50 s - Chloroform:methanol:water (2:2:1.9)	Lipid recovery of 31.70	(Lee <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
<i>Nannochloropsis oceanica</i>	Microwave + dilute acid	140°C, 25 mins - H ₂ SO ₄ (1% v/v)	Hydrogen yield of 183.9 mL/g TVS	(Xia <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
<i>Scenedesmus sp.</i>	Thermal + alkaline	100°C, 8 h – NaOH	Lipid extraction- 45.54 mL H ₂ /g (VS) of hydrogen	(Yang <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
	Ultrasonication + solvent	30 kHz, 1 kW for 5 to 60 min - Hexane, chloroform/methanol (1:1 v/v)	Efficiency of 0.144 to 0.72 (mg/g cell) ^c	(Adam <i>et al.</i> , 2012)

2.6.9 Other latest pre-treatment techniques

There is a need for novel techniques to decrease the recalcitrant properties of microalgae and influence biomass to disrupt high-value lipids, and new techniques are being implemented. Most researchers consider their work to be eco-friendly and appropriate for large-scale production. However, while their findings may be of good quality, they focus on industrial applications.

Updates to biological techniques with modifications were implemented in a recent study on lignocellulosic biomass, which showed that changing cellulose elements leads to increased enzyme hydrolysis, lower energy use, lower operational costs, and less hemicellulose loss (Gaurav *et al.*, 2017; Zabed *et al.*, 2019).

The photocatalysis method uses light absorption to increase the temperature, creating a chemical reaction. *Chlorella vulgaris* treatment saw a mineralisation efficiency of 57% efficiency when using a light intensity of 4000 lux and a temperature of 25 ± 1 °C (Lu *et al.*, 2022). *Chlorella pyrenoidosa* and *Scenedesmus obliquus* treatment were investigated and resulted in decreased cell toxicity (Lu *et al.*, 2022).

A study on cell disruption techniques resulted in advances in explosive decompression. This method uses propane, butane, or carbon dioxide for lipid extraction. *Haematococcus pluvialis* was suspended at a dry cell weight of 18.11%, and using explosive decompression, extraction increased from 72.3% to 92.6%. Because of the higher dry cell weight and the lower specific energy consumption, a high extraction yield was obtained (Eppink *et al.*, 2019).

Another study used pulsed arch technology in grape seeds to disrupt cells. This technology used high-electric energy discharge during a time phase and produced cavities within the cells due to the high temperature and pressure (Boussetta, Lesaint and Vorobiev, 2013). This is one among a high aggressive method, but it is not still studied in microalgae. Perhaps this method could be modified in the future so that it could be used to disrupt cells with low electric energy, shear forces, and temperature to obtain good lipid productivity.

The autolysis extraction technique, a less explored method, represents a good approach for disrupting lipids. Cell disruption can be triggered by different atmosphere cues such as anoxia when there is an increase in temperature. *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* (*Production and characterization of algae extract from Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*, no date) *Nannochloropsis gaditana* (Halim *et al.*, 2019) were treated at temperatures of 50 °C and 38 °C, respectively, during a 24 h incubation period and showed cell breakage. This technique is considered for application because of its mild treatment conditions and low processing costs, even though this method seems to be slow.

Ionic liquid methods have been indicated to facilitate lipid extraction from wet microalgae. The influence of the ionic liquid 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium methyl sulphate [EMIM][MeSO₄] was tested on *Nannochloropsis* sp. and resulted in a biodiesel yield of 40.9% (Wahidin *et al.*, 2018b). Another study was conducted with 1 g of dry *Chlorella vulgaris* that had 4 mL of ionic liquid (1,3-dimethylimidazolium methyl phosphate) + 4 mL of methanol added to it, and

it was treated for about 18 h at 65 °C. The results indicated the occurrence of cell disruption (Orr *et al.*, 2016). This method is also considered to be a mild process with slow results.

Research was conducted with *Nannochloropsis oculata* and *Scenedesmus dimorphus* using convectional ultrasonication at 100 W and a 20 kHz frequency and focused ultrasonication at 40 W and 3.2 MHz. The results indicated that higher efficiency and a better cell disruption efficiency can be obtained using focused ultrasonication than with convectional ultrasonication (Wang *et al.*, 2014).

Pressurised liquid extraction is a technique that is also known as an accelerated solvent extraction technique. This method extracts the intercellular compounds in a shorter extraction time by utilizing a combination of pressure and temperature (Ruiz-Domínguez *et al.*, 2021a). In addition, there have been several studies that have used supercritical water, propane, dimethyl ether, and n- butane as solvents (Ruiz-Domínguez *et al.*, 2021b; Wang *et al.*, 2021).

2.7. Discussion on different pre-treatment techniques

Microalgae are single-cell organisms. Their photosynthesis produces around 70% of the O₂ in the atmosphere. Not all microalgae are single-cell organisms, and some species of microalgae can grow as single cells or in colonies (according to colour) and take the shape of spheres or filaments (*Microalgae: how tiny, single-celled organisms can revolutionise the world - Advisian*, no date). During cell disruption, the inner forces cause temperature changes as well as cavitation, pressure, and molecular energy variations. The quality of the final product may be impacted by these events separately or collectively, depending on whether the contaminants are produced or the algal elements are degraded (Khan, Shin and Kim, 2018). From the above methods, it is clear that mechanical and physical methods are considered to be more effective in enhancing lipid efficiency in large-scale applications. The cell disruption caused during high-speed homogenisation and bead milling works according to the principle of shear force, which is similar to the energy transfer caused by the current and waves effects observed in the microwave, ultrasound, and pulsed electric field techniques. Enhancing the efficiency of microalgae mainly relies on cell wall characteristics as well as on strain and operational parameters, including temperature, enzyme doses, and power input. Often, pre-treatment is the best way to improve biomass production with various ranges of efficiencies. Studies suggest that biomass yield can improve from 20% to 60% after the application of pre-treatment

methods. The Figure 2. 18 shows the various microalgae that have been studied using different pre-treatment methods. Using a thermal pre-treatment method, *Botryococcus* sp. showed an improved lipid yield and increased biomass production (J.-Y. Lee *et al.*, 2010a). The homogeniser and microwave methods were found to be more efficient compared to other methods. *Botryococcus* sp. showed lipid production of 28.6% and 28.1% when the microwave and homogeniser methods were used, respectively, and the bead beating method showed a higher lipid percentage when used with *Botryococcus braunii* compared to other pre-treatment techniques such as the French press, sonication, and homogeniser methods (Lee, Yoon and Oh, 1998). It should also be noted that the efficiency of the bead beating technique is not easily measured. *Chlorella vulgaris* showed high efficiency when the microwave method was applied and 7.9% lower efficiency compared to other mechanical methods. The microwave pre-treatment of *Scenedesmus* sp. resulted in high lipid efficiency when compared to other methods. However, the osmotic pre-treatment method is quite simple and produced similar output to the mechanical methods for *Scenedesmus* sp. and *Chlorella vulgaris*. A small problem with this method is that it requires a long pre-treatment time of 48 h (J.-Y. Lee *et al.*, 2010a). A pre-treatment method similar to the microwave method that uses animal fats and vegetable oils has been studied and suggests that the microwave method is a simple, efficient, and easy pre-treatment technique. Furthermore, this research indicated the lipid extraction can be also easily measured and concluded that the microwave technique is the most applicable method for the large-scale production of microalgal biomass (Mahesar *et al.*, 2008) (Virost *et al.*, 2008). In various studies, modifying the pre-treatment methods and conditions has been seen as a strategy to enhance lipid production. The current studies in microalgal biofuel are mentioned because they highlight the ability of different methods to recover lipids (Han *et al.*, 2015). The biomass production and the lipid recovery rate change from species to species and also vary across treatment methodologies. *Dunaliella salina* and *Chaeoceros muelleri* were evaluated using osmotic shock by Lina *et al.* (González-González *et al.*, 2019), where the effect of biomass and the water ratio was analysed with different levels of fluorescence ranges and timings.

Figure 2. 18: Schematic representation of lipid productivity of micro-algae (J.-Y. Lee *et al.*, 2010a)

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Many results were generated with different iterations, and it was concluded that the various results differ according to economic and efficiency factors. In a work by Gruber *et al.* (Gruber-Brunhumer *et al.*, 2016), studies were conducted with methods such as microwave, ultrasonication, enzymatic, and wet milling using the microalgal biomass of *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Acutodesmus obliquus*, and *Chlorella emersonii* to study single and combined pre-treatment technique effects, and varying lipid-recovery rates and cost analysis were achieved. Another study by Francesco *et al.* (Ometto *et al.*, 2014), looked over the impacts of cell rupture using thermal, thermal hydrolysis, enzymatic, and ultrasound techniques using *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella vulgaris*. In the initial set of experiments, the yields were shown to increase with the ultrasonic and enzymatic techniques compared to the untreated biomass, and then, when combining the thermal and thermal hydrolysis strategies, the yield percentages were lower. Additionally, apart from modifying and combining pre-treatment techniques, most of the studies focussed on cultivation process such as the selection of species (Okoro *et al.*, 2019), growth media (Mehrabadi, Craggs and Farid, 2016), CO₂ (Singh and Singh, 2014), light (Zhu, Li and Hiltunen, 2016), temperature (Dickinson *et al.*, 2017) and nutrients (Cordeiro *et al.*, 2017). Hence, the first suggestion for the microalgal pre-treatment is to determine the effects of the processing conditions, modifications, and pre-treatment techniques in combination to

obtain an increase in the yield percentage functions. In a previous report using microalgae *Botryococcus braunii* pre-treated with thermal method for 140 °C for 10 min, a recovered lipid yields of 97.8 wt% was obtained (Kita *et al.*, 2010). In research using chemical methods and *Nannochloropsis oceanica* with diluted H₂SO₄ (1% v/v), the researcher obtained a hydrogen yield of 183.9 mL/g TVS (Yang *et al.*, 2010). Thermal pre-treatments are recommended compared to other methods such as ultrasound and biological pre-treatment methods (Alzate *et al.*, 2012a). For *Chlorella vulgaris*, enzymatic pre-treatment methods were more effective in enhancing biomass production. It also represents an energy-balanced pre-treatment method other than hydrothermal, thermal, and ultra-sound treatments. When thermal, ultrasound, hydrothermal, and microwave pre-treatments were compared using microalgae obtained from an open pond, a high lipid yield, organic matter solubilisation, and biomass concentration were found. It was also noted that thermal pre-treatment methods showed a positive energy balance because of energy gain (Fabiana Passos, Javier Carretero, 2015). Physical pre-treatment methods using ultrasound or microwaves are used to increase the biomass. The final quality of the product is related to the biochemical composition and morphology of the microalgae during cell disruption. The cell disruption effect was determined by Komaki *et al.* (Komaki *et al.*, 1998) by studying three various strains of *chlorella vulgaris*. The results indicated that digestibility occurred in one among them. Additionally, the selection of the extraction process has an impact on the final product. The summary of advantages and disadvantages of various pre-treatment techniques are shown in Table 2. 14.

For the process of biodiesel production, cell disruption and lipid extraction from microalgae have been studied and researched for years. The cell disruption pre-treatment techniques used for microalgae have both pros and cons depending on the energy consumption, type of microalgae, cost effectiveness, applicability, and efficiency. As discussed above, further advanced studies may be required to face the challenges of these methods and to bring them to reality.

Table 2. 14: The summary of advantages and limitations of various pre-treatment techniques

Cell rupture method	Parameters affecting lipid production	Advantages	Disadvantages	Reference
Mechanical	Design of blade, number of passes pressure and speed of rotation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Surface area increases. ▪ No inhibitory & toxic compounds. ▪ Easy to operate and commercialisable. ▪ biomasses ease to handle. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Requires high energy. ▪ High capital and maintenance cost. ▪ Influence inert materials. 	(Cho <i>et al.</i> , 2012) (Halim <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
Ultrasonic	Power, time and cycle number.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Extraction time and solvent consumption is reduced. ▪ Bulk medium of cell contents is reduced. ▪ No inhibitory & toxic compounds. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Requires high energy consumption. ▪ Scaling up is difficult. ▪ High capital and maintenance cost. 	(Chandler <i>et al.</i> , 2001) (Taylor <i>et al.</i> , 2001) (Fykse, Olsen and Skogan, 2003) (Borthwick <i>et al.</i> , 2005b)
Microwave	Temperature, stirring, power and time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Less energy demand and solvent usage. ▪ Speed and uniform heating. ▪ Eco-friendly. ▪ High extraction yield. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Efficiency differs when solvents are volatile or nonpolar. ▪ Scaling up is difficult. 	(Pan, Niu and Liu, 2002) (Virot <i>et al.</i> , 2008)
Auto-clave	Temperature, thermal, Stress and pressure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High lipid content. ▪ Life span of the product of maintained. ▪ Less energy demands. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Requires high energy consumption for industrial process. ▪ Time consuming process and difficult in scaling up. 	(Halim <i>et al.</i> , 2013) (Ryckebosch, Muylaert and Foubert, 2012) (Luo, Xiao and Luo, 2010)
Steam Explosion	Temperature, thermal Stress, microalgae specie and pressure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No inhibitory & toxic compounds. ▪ Hazardous wastes can be reduced while lipid recovery. ▪ Low cost and Commercialisable. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Efficiency is compared with microalgae specie. ▪ Requires high energy consumption for industrial process. ▪ Time consuming process and difficult in scaling up. ▪ Energy cost for high temperature. 	(H <i>et al.</i> , 2013) (Cheng and Timilsina, 2011) (Nurra <i>et al.</i> , 2014b) (Brown <i>et al.</i> , 1992)
Catalytic & Enzymatic	Stirring, Chemical concentration of KOH and NaOH. Enzymatic type, Stirring.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lower energy consumption. ▪ Hemi-cellulose solubilisation. ▪ Higher lipid yields and speed process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Expensive chemical cost. ▪ Toxicity and inhibitory. ▪ Contamination during extraction. ▪ Expensive Enzymatic cost. ▪ Agitation condition. 	(Harun and Danquah, 2011) (Miranda, Passarinho and Gouveia, 2012) (González-Fernández and Ballesteros, 2012) (Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2016)

2.8 Selection and processing of pre-treatment technique

The selection of a pre-treatment method and other processing steps is very crucial. These steps must be followed throughout the research process, from microalgae culturing to final processing. There are numerous choices for processing, and some steps may favour the discovery of new techniques.

1. Many iterations must be carried out for process development using published literature. New methods should be evaluated and analysed for lipid yield by considering the environmental impacts and cost factors of the method.
2. Improvement must be carried out according to successful studies using the available modern techniques, and the processing should be continued.
3. Energy and cost are very significant. Along with this, product evaluation is also important and can show an increase in process profitability.
4. Following the safety and legislation protocols is also essential. When using chemical methods, it is very important to consider safety and legislation factors.

2.9 Energy consumption of pre-treatment techniques

Even if pre-treatment techniques increase recovery, they demand a certain amount of energy for processing. The evaluation of cost effectiveness and energy consumption of different pre-treatment techniques should be economically relevant. The energy requirements should be viewed according to several factors, such as type of species, growth conditions, pre-treatment method, concentration, etc. For the mechanical and physical methods, the energy demands are ultimately high compared to other methods. Generally, for these methods, the energy consumption and cost effectiveness are the most influential conditions. However, for non-mechanical methods, the energy consumption depends on stirring, time, and temperature. Compared to biological enzymatic hydrolysis treatments, this technique requires very less energy but is only dependent on stirring (Córdova, Passos and Chamy, 2019). By working on the industrial conditions, this method can be optimised in terms of its operating parameters to have a shorter working duration, which might increase its cost as well (Verni *et al.*, 2023) the various mechanical methods such as the high-pressure homogenisation (HPH), high-speed homogenisation, microwave, ultrasonic, and bead milling techniques, studies conclude that HPH seems to be a more energy consuming technique (Halim *et al.*, 2012b) (Lee, Lewis and Ashman, 2012a) (J. Y. Lee *et al.*, 2010) followed by ultrasonication and microwave (McMillan

et al., 2013). Therefore, further studies have to be carried out to predict an actual energy demand that will help the specific pre-treatment technique chosen for industrial applications.

2.10 Overview of Design of experiments

The Design of experiments (DOE) is designed to find, in any experimental design, the individual and interactive effects of input process parameters that could affect the output response simultaneously. Furthermore, when the number of input processing conditions increases, the overall research technique could predict the cost considerations, which are attributed to the time and resources required to carry out the required number of experiments (Román-Ramírez and Marco, 2022). This experimental part can be avoided by employing the Design of Experiment (DOE) method, which provides a compelling set of variable combinations (Design matrix) that maximises their interaction and influence on the resulting measured response. The Design of an experiment is a systematic approach to investigating a system that plays an essential role in organising, executing, analysing, and interpreting experimental data. While a system model can be statistically estimated accurately by minimising the number of experiment runs required. Similarly, in a situation where numerous variables influence a specific response, the best approach is to design a reliable experiment, sound, provides a proper conclusion, and can be drawn economically and efficiently. The minimum information about the experiments could be necessary for the DOE to work like,

- Limits of the experiments
- Specific processing factors
- Mathematical studies to show the response values in any point within the limits of the experiments.

The important steps in processing a successful DOE can be shown in 5 steps,

- State the problem
- Planning the experiments
- Working the experiments
- Statistical methods are used to run and analyse the data
- Conclude the results

The design of the experiment method consists of two models, 2-level factorial and Taguchi techniques. These methods can show responses with minimal experimental data and various output responses and factors. The Taguchi method uses the applications of quadratic

parameters along with some input factors to analyse the data (Montgomery, 2012). Along with this, response surface methodology (RSM) is used to represent the effects of the input variable on the output response and the Eqn. 2.3 shows the functions for identifying the response data.

$$y = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i X_i + \sum \beta_{ii} X_{ii}^2 + \sum \beta_{ij} X_i X_j \quad \text{Eqn. 2.3}$$

where Y is the response. β_0 , β_i , β_{ii} , and β_{ij} are regression coefficients for an intercept, linear, quadratic, and interaction. X_i and X_j are factors. The quality of the model used is supported by various response values, including p-value, R^2 , adequate precision, and lack of fit. The aim of this is to generate and optimise numerous responses and the output response lipid extraction (%) is indicated by y.

2.11 Response Surface Methodology (RSM)

RSM is a statistical and mathematical method used to model problems and identify the output response with various factors. This can be utilised in any industrial processing and analytical method. RSM is a set of criteria for determining the most feasible region to conduct experiments so that the prediction is as precise as possible. Once a problem is identified and defined, the response tries to provide alternative experimental approaches to analyse the data. The significant advantage of this method is that the task of adopting the research and testing to the problem is completed before the experiments are carried out. In this study the following steps are carried out to create a mathematical design to enhance the lipid efficiency (%):

- The model enables to determine the optimal conditions for the implemented experimental operating factors that provides the maximised lipid efficiency (%) output.
- Capability to determine a mathematical model that matches the design data collected.
- RSM is able to design a set of experiments that will reveal adequate and reliable response measurements.

From the Eqn. (2.3), β_0 , β_i , β_{ij} can be estimated using regression analysis and they are the second order polynomial which is used in RSM, where β_0 is Intercept regression coefficient, $\sum \beta_i X_i$ is the major factor effects, $\sum \beta_{ii} X_{ii}^2$ is the quadratic effects and $\sum \beta_{ij} X_i X_j$ is the interaction of the 2 – factors.

In this research, the independent variable from the experiments is microwave power, microwave time, homogenising speed, homogenising time, ultrasonic frequency, ultrasonic

time and extraction time. The main objective of implementing RSM is because the input factors' topography is easily understood, and the best response arising regions are identified. The idea is to expand quickly and efficiently along a path to reach a maximum and minimum response in order to optimise the response effectively.

2.11.1 Box-Behnken Design (BBD)

The Box-Behnken Design (BBD) is designed and coded levels which are -1, 0 and 1. This indicated the minimum, centre and maximal factors which was described by Box and Behnken(Box and Behnken, 1960). The schematic diagram of BBD is shown in Figure 2. 19.

Figure 2. 19: Three – factor BBD representation

BBD is specified by the following features like,

- They are sensitive to the failing data and runs. It is affected by failing data points and failed runs. Repeated runs are required for a more optimal solution.
- Each input data is assigned with one of 3 uniformly spaced values, that are generally coded as -1, 0 or +1.
- BBD gives more precise coefficients in the proximity of the lattice mid-point, but it is less accurate in characterising the design point at the cube's corners.
- The set of different points is therefore sufficient to adapt a quadratic model, indicating that it was created for quadratic model valuation.

2.11.2 Central Composite Design (CCD)

Central Composite Design (CCD) is a widely used experimental design technique that allows researchers to explore and understand the relationships between variables. It involves the selection of specific levels of factors and the arrangement of experimental runs based on a central point, axial points, and factorial points. CCD is particularly useful for studying non-

linear responses and optimising process parameters. By systematically varying the levels of factors and analysing the corresponding responses, CCD helps researchers identify optimal conditions and understand the influence of factors on the outcome of interest. The design provides flexibility in exploring the design space and can accommodate a wide range of experimental settings. Overall, CCD is a valuable tool for experimental design and optimisation in various fields of research and industry (Prajapati, Kodgire and Singh Kachhwaha, 2022a).

2.11.3 Advantages of using Box-Behnken Design (BBD) over Central Composite Design (CCD)

The merits of using BBD over CCD can be summarised as follows:

- BBD techniques ensure that there is a variation in all three levels of factors, making it a cost-effective choice for conducting experiments.
- BBD configurations are designed in a ball shape form, which allows for easy rotation between blocks during factorial designs.
- BBD separates the experimental runs, enabling various units to be applied independently. This helps to estimate the relationship between dependent and independent variables without interference from other units.
- BBD is specifically tailored to address experimental boundaries and avoids repeated and extreme conditions, ensuring a more balanced and controlled experimental setup.
- BBD is particularly useful when a few experimental runs are needed, making it an efficient choice for studies with limited resources or time constraints. However, it may not be the best option for studies requiring multiple runs.

2.10 Conclusions considering overall project aim and the objective

This literature review has provided a comprehensive overview of biodiesel production using microalgae as a sustainable feedstock. The research scope of this study focuses on the analysis and optimisation of lipid extraction from two microalgal species, *Chlorella Vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis Oculata*, with the aim of enhancing biodiesel production. Several key findings and research gaps have been identified, which will guide the direction of the current research project. It is seen that microalgae offer great potential as a renewable and environmentally friendly source of biodiesel. Both *Chlorella Vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis*

Oculata exhibit favourable characteristics for lipid production, including rapid growth, high lipid content, and adaptability to challenging conditions. By exploring the lipid extraction efficiency from these species, this study aims to contribute to the development of a sustainable biodiesel feedstock.

The research project will focus on evaluating the effectiveness of three different pre-treatment methods: microwave, high-speed homogeniser, and ultrasonic techniques. These mechanical methods have shown promise in enhancing lipid extraction from microalgae, but further optimisation is required to determine the most effective operating factors and for large-scale applications. The use of design of experiments (DOE) and response surface methodology (RSM) will enable the development of regression models to analyse the interaction between input and output parameters and optimise the lipid extraction process.

Throughout the literature review, it became apparent that there is a research gap in the specific area of lipid extraction from microalgae and its conversion into biodiesel by wet method, where most of the research papers focused on using dry algae for biofuel production. Also, while numerous studies have focused on the growth and characteristics of microalgae, limited research has addressed the optimisation of lipid extraction processes. This research project aims to fill this gap by investigating the effectiveness of different pre-treatment techniques and optimising the lipid extraction process for biodiesel production. The findings of this research will contribute to the growing body of knowledge in the field and provide valuable insights for the development of a sustainable energy source.

Chapter 3: Materials, methods & Experimental methodology

3.1 Microalgal strain

The microalgae species *Chlorella vulgaris* is a genus of mono-cell green species which belongs to the phylum Chlorophyta. It looks spherical and grows in diameter of 2 to 10 μm . The chloroplast of this algae has green photosynthetic pigments chlorophyll-a and -b, and due to these pigments, it multiplies rapidly during photosynthesis with less amount of minerals, water, carbon-di-oxide and sunlight. *N. Oculata* is an algae gene belonging to the phylum Ochrophyta family and Eustigmatophyceae class. These unicellular microalgae look spherical and grow to a diameter of 2-5 microns. *N. Oculata* mainly occur in marine resources worldwide, and their biomaterials are rich in concentrations of protein, photosynthetic pigments, omega-3 fatty acids and lipids. This strain is said to be a bulldog among the algal strains as they are difficult to kill (Martínez-Roldán and Cañizares-Villanueva, 2020). Microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* strain is supplied from Algae research supply, 1405 Buena Vista Way, Carlsbad, CA. 92008, USA. *Nannochloropsis Oculata* strain is supplied from Reefphyto, United Kingdom. The experiments flow of this research study is shown in Figure 3. 1

Figure 3. 1: Research flow diagram

3.2 Medium conditions

F/2 medium is widely considered an excellent growing medium for freshwater algae. Here, a slightly modified version of the F/2 medium was prepared for growing the algae. The chemical composition of the medium includes Sodium nitrate, Monosodium phosphate, Sodium carbonate, trace metals solution and vitamin solution. This medium is widely used for growing marine algae, and the original formulation is termed F medium (Guillard, 1975; Ryther and Guillard, 2011). Later the primary nutrients in this medium were decreased to half and named as F/2 medium. The complete details of the medium recipe are shown in Table 3. 1. The medium prepared for this study follows the chemical specifications and guidelines provided by Algae Research Supply (f/2 Media - Algae Research Supply). In order to prepare the solution, start with 950 ml of the deionised water and the compounds in the table are added by dissolving 2.2g freshwater algae culturing salts (the salt contains sodium carbonate, sodium bicarbonate, and trace metal containing sodium chloride). The trace and vitamin solutions as shown in Table 3. 2 & Table 3. 3 .The two-trace metal and vitamin solutions are generally produced as high-concentration stock solutions to allow weighing of reasonable amounts.

Table 3. 1: Modified F/2 Stock Solution Chemical components.

Components	Stock Solution	Quantity	Molar Concentration in Final Medium
NaNO ₃	75 g/L dH ₂ O	1 ml	8.82 x10 ⁻⁴ M
NaH ₂ PO ₄ H ₂ O	5 g/L dH ₂ O	1 ml	3.62 x 10 ⁻⁵ M
Na ₂ CO ₃	30 g/L dH ₂ O	1 ml	1.06 x 10 ⁻⁴ M
Trace Metal Solution	See table 3.2	1 ml	-
Vitamin Solution	See table 3.3	0.5 ml	-

To prepare 100 ml of the F/2 final trace metals solution, the composition shown in Table 3. 2 was mixed with 100 ml of deionised water in a 250 ml conical flask. Then the final volume of the medium was made with 100 ml of deionised water to produce 100 ml of the final F/2 trace metal solution.

Table 3. 2: Modified F/2 Trace metal solution chemical components.

Components	Stock Solution	Quantity	Molar Concentration in Final Medium
FeCl ₃ 6(H ₂ O)	-	3.15 g	1.17 x10 ⁻⁵ M
Na ₂ (EDTA)2(H ₂ O)	-	4.36 g	1.17 x10 ⁻⁵ M
CuSO ₄ 5(H ₂ O)	9.8 g/L dH ₂ O	1 ml	3.93x10 ⁻⁸ M
Na ₂ MoO ₄ .2(H ₂ O)	6.3 g/L dH ₂ O	1 ml	2.60 x10 ⁻⁸ M
ZnSO ₄ .7(H ₂ O)	22.0 g/L dH ₂ O	1 ml	7.65 x10 ⁻⁸ M
CoCl ₂ 6(H ₂ O)	10.0 g/L dH ₂ O	1 ml	4.20 x10 ⁻⁸ M
MnCl ₂ 4(H ₂ O)	180.0 g/L dH ₂ O	1 ml	9.10 x10 ⁻⁷ M

To prepare 100 ml of the F/2 vitamin solution, the chemical composition shown in Table 3. 3 was added in 90 ml of deionised water in a 250 ml conical flask and stirred. The final volume of the medium was made with 100 ml of deionised water to produce 100 ml of the final F/2 vitamin solution.

Table 3. 3: Modified F/2 Vitamin solution chemical components

Components	Stock Solution	Quantity	Molar Concentration in Final Medium
Thiamine HCl (Vitamin B1)	-	200 mg	2.96 x10 ⁻⁷ M
Biotin (Vitamin H)	0.1 g/L dH ₂ O	10 ml	2.05 x10 ⁻⁹ M
Cyanocobalamin (Vitamin B12)	1 g/L dH ₂ O	1 ml	3.69 x10 ⁻¹⁰ M

At last, to prepare the 1 L of the final F/2 medium, the listed composition is added as per the chemical list in the Table 3. 1, Table 3. 2 & Table 3. 3 and autoclaved.

3.3 Microalgae culturing

Microalgae were grown in a 3×5 litres flask. The modified F/2 medium compounds are added to deionised water and cultivated in the school of computing, engineering & physical sciences at the University of the west of Scotland and cultivated for 21 days. The cultivation duration of 21 days was determined based on the observation of the microalgal growth patterns and the achievement of the stationary phase. Our monitoring revealed that the microalgae reached the stationary phase around the 20th day of cultivation. At this stage when observed from a compound microscope, a higher number of algal cells began to die, and the growth phase ceased, indicating the completion of the growth cycle. Hence, we decided to conclude the cultivation process and proceed with the experimentation phase. The initial culturing conditions were started at room temperature (18 °C) and pH 9.4 with continuous illumination and aeration. The flasks are connected with an air pump to provide effective growth, and they are grown with a light source of 75 lumens fluorescent bulbs for 24 h for the entire culture period. Regarding the use of 75 lumens fluorescent bulbs, we opted to utilise the available laboratory facilities and resources while considering energy conservation (by avoiding photobioreactor). The laboratory room had an illumination of approximately 75 lumens, which, while not optimal, still facilitated reasonable growth of the microalgae. These conditions align with those used by (Onumaegbu *et al.*, 2018a) in their algal research. In order to avoid the settlement at the bottom, the flasks were shaken and swirled thrice a day. The Figure 3. 2 shows the microalgae culturing done in this research study. To minimise contamination, the culturing equipment is autoclaved at 121 °C and this helped to eliminate potential contamination from bacterial growth, ensuring the purity of the culture medium throughout the growth period.

3.4 Determination of optical density and growth analysis

The growth rate of the culturing microalgae was monitored daily. About 10ml of the sample was analysed in Thermo scientific evolution 220 photo spectrometer. Measurements with optical densities of OD₆₈₀ (same medium as blank) and the absorbance are noted daily for the entire cultivation period to work on cell density calculations. Once reaching the stationary phase, it was observed that OD₆₈₀ showed a peak in cell density count, as shown in Figure 3. 3. Also, the OD₆₈₀ avoids light scattering by the chlorophyll and carotenoids pigments (Liang, Zhang and Cong, 2012). So, the cell calibration curve analysis is planned to be set with OD₆₈₀.

Figure 3. 2: Microalgae culturing

Figure 3. 3: Optical density against culturing period

Initially, the initial growth of the microalgal strains was performed to study the growth rates, biomass productivity and cell concentration. Assessment of dry weight calculations was done by centrifugation and represented in Table 3. 4. The weighing machine used in this research is done in Sartorius AC 211S, and centrifugation was performed in Heraeus instruments Megafuge 1.0.

3.5 Growth analysis

The microalgae growth curves, biomass doubling time, variations in the specific growth rate in different culture phases (0–21 days) and biomass productivity (after 21 days of culturing) were estimated relying on the curves of the correlations between OD₆₈₀ and dry weight. This can be calculated by using the Eqn. (3.1) below (Onumaegbu *et al.*, 2018a).

$$\text{Specific growth rate } (\mu) = \ln\left(\frac{N_2 - N_1}{T_2 - T_1}\right) \quad \text{Eqn. 3.1}$$

Where,

N1 and N2 are the number of cells at the initial and end of log phase.

T1 and T2 are the initial and final day of the log phase.

The growth curve (Figure 3. 4) indicates that the higher concentration is obtained after 14 days of the culturing. The *C.Vulgaris* initially showed a slow growth rate on comparing with *N.Oculata* for the first two weeks, then started moving to the stationary phase and continued till the end of the culturing period. The initial and final specific growth rate of the *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis Oculata* is found to be 0.092 (d⁻¹) to 3.856 (d⁻¹) and 0.645 (d⁻¹) to 3.957 (d⁻¹) respectively.

Figure 3. 4: Microalgal growth chart

3.6 Dry weight determination and harvesting process

To make a standard curve for the biomass dry weight, the grown culture was taken, diluted with four different concentrations to an OD₆₈₀ and taken in 4×50ml Falcon tubes. For every sample in a tube, OD₆₈₀ was calculated using a photo spectrometer against the blank (deionised water). Falcon tubes were centrifuged at 3300 rpm for 30 minutes and the supernatant part was collected and poured into a separate flask and filtered using cellulose nitrate membrane filters of 0.45 µm Whatman filter paper. The pellet was left to dry in an oven for 24 hours at 30°C. After drying, the algae biomass weight was determined from the original weight of the filter paper minus the weight with biomass to get the dry weight per g/ml. The concentration against the dry weight curve was plotted on Microsoft Excel using the OD₆₈₀. The relationship between the dry weight and the OD₆₈₀ was calculated with four different concentrations of microalgal cells and the results are shown in Table 3. 4. The Figure 3. 5 represents the microalgae filtration process for dry weight assessments.

Table 3. 4: Microalgae concentration in various diluted samples.

Sample	Volume	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>			<i>Nannochloropsis Oculata</i>		
		OD ₆₈₀	Dry weight of algae (g)	Concentration (g/ml)	OD ₆₈₀	Dry weight of algae (g)	Concentration (g/ml)
1	15	0.496	0.0075	5.00×10^{-4}	0.567	0.0086	5.73×10^{-4}
2	25	0.765	0.0142	5.68×10^{-4}	0.896	0.0245	9.80×10^{-4}
3	45	1.376	0.0299	6.64×10^{-4}	1.423	0.0354	7.87×10^{-4}
4	50	1.465	0.0354	7.08×10^{-4}	1.674	0.0449	8.98×10^{-4}

Figure 3. 5: (a). Microalgae filtration process. (b) Filtered biomass

3.7 Microwave

The pre-treatment was conducted using a Bosch HMT84M451B Solo Microwave – 51 x 30cm Stainless Steel with 2.45 GHz operational frequency. The duty cycle and the power were manually changed to operate on the designed set of experiments. 100ml of the culture is taken in a beaker and processed for microwave pre-treatment. The culture samples were treated with different microwave power of 90 W, 600 W and 900 W with varying time phases such as 90, 135 and 180 secs. A set of experiments were performed using pre-determine conditions with different power and time. In order to establish the appropriate ranges for our study, we performed a preliminary investigation and conducted a thorough review of existing research that examined microwave pre-treatment technique parameters for microalgae cell disruption. This comprehensive analysis enabled us to identify feasible and relevant ranges, which would provide valuable insights into the correlation between the microwave pre-treatment process and lipid extraction. The processing parameters for the microwave pre-treatment method is represented in Table 3. 5.

3.8 High speed homogeniser

This pre-treatment was carried out in an Mxbaoheng HQ-2475 High-Speed Homogeniser, which comprises a spindle internal cutting tool (12 mm diameter) to homogenise into small molecules at different speed levels and a manual speed controller knob. The Figure 3. 6 shows the HSH operating process. This model HSH has a motor power of 220W and a power input of 110V. This HSH model manual shows operating continuously for no more than 5 mins and pauses for 2 mins. After connecting the power supply, about 100ml sample is taken in a round bottom flask and kept on the operational base. The spindle head was submerged into the sample 2-3 mm away from the bottom of the flask, and the power supply was turned on. The speed knob was adjusted for the required rpm, and a stopwatch was used to run as per the time cycle. A set of experiments were performed with different speeds of 6000, 14000, and 22000rpm with running time of 5,10 and 15 mins and extraction time 2,3 and 4hr extraction time. The processing parameters for the HSH pre-treatment method is represented in Table 3. 5.

Figure 3. 6: High-Speed Homogeniser operating process

3.9 Ultrasonic

The ultrasonic technique is a potential pre-treatment for attenuating microalgal cells and releasing natural algal contents. This technique involves compression sequences in the pre-treating algal volume, which generates acoustic cavitation to break their cells to extract lipids (Kurokawa *et al.*, 2016; Peng *et al.*, 2020). Thus, this technique can successfully cause damage to the structural and functional characteristics of the microalgae. The Ultrasonic working model is represented in Figure 3. 7. The pre-treatment in this ultrasonic method was done using Fisherbrand 11201 series ultrasonic machine. They provide various configurable parameters for laboratory applications, such as cleaning, mixing, and degassing. This model has dual frequencies of 37 and 80 kHz, working at a power of 480 W. This model has the advantage of working in low volume with high frequency with dimensions of 7.0 x 11.8 x 8.7 in. For pre-treating, 100 ml of the culture sample is treated in the ultrasonic machine at operating conditions as designed by the designed expert software. A set of experiments were performed with different frequencies of 37 and 80 kHz with running time of 10,15, and 20 mins and extraction time 2,3 and 4hr extraction time. To determine the ranges, we conducted a preliminary investigation and reviewed existing studies that explored similar ultrasonic pre-treatment parameters for microalgae. This allowed us to identify feasible and relevant ranges that could yield meaningful insights into the relationship between the ultrasonication process and lipid extraction. The processing parameters for the Ultrasonic pre-treatment method is represented in Table 3. 5.

Figure 3. 7: Ultrasonication Operating process

Table 3. 5: Operating parameters of microalgal pre-treatment

Pre-treatment Variables	Levels			Pre-treatment Variables	Levels			Pre-treatment Variables	Levels		
	-1	0	1		-1	0	1		-1	0	1
Microwave power (W)	90	600	900	Speed (rpm)	6000	14000	22000	Frequency (kHz)	37	-	80
Microwave time (Mins)	1.5	2.25	3	Running time (Mins)	10	15	20	Ultrasonic time (Mins)	10	15	20
Extraction time (Hrs)	2	3	4	Extraction time (Hrs)	2	3	4	Extraction time (Hrs)	2	3	4

3.10 Extraction procedure and lipid quantification

100 ml of the pre-treated samples were taken in a round bottom flask which was added with 100 ml of methanol and 2 ml concentrated Sulphuric acid. Anti-bumping granules were added to the mixture, which was then subjected to reflux using a heating mantle for varying extraction times (2, 3, and 4 hours). The extraction procedure is shown in Figure 3. 8. As the temperature of the methanol solution reached its boiling point of approximately 100°C, it caused the wet microalgal sample to boil along with it. This facilitated the formation of a bridge between the algal cells and the chemical solution, allowing the microalgal sample to react with the methanol and methylate the lipids, resulting in the formation of fatty acid methyl esters (FAME).

Next, sodium bicarbonate was introduced to the mixture to neutralize the pH and ensure its neutral state. The pH level of the solution was tested using pH paper. The neutralized mixture was then transferred into a separating funnel by adding 150 ml of hexane. After approximately 5-10 minutes, layer separation occurred, with the top hexane layer containing the lipids, while the bottom layers with methanol retained the residuals. The bottom methanol layer was washed three times with 150 cm³ of hexane, and the lipids were collected by evaporating the solvent using a steam bath.

The weight of the extracted lipids was determined by calculating the difference between the weight of the extracted lipids and the initial biomass weight. This process allowed for the quantification of the lipid extract. The equation was expressed in terms of Eqn. (3.2).

$$\text{Lipid productivity (\%)} = \frac{\text{Wieght of extracted lipids (g)}}{\text{Initial biomass weight (g)}} \times 100 \quad \text{Eqn. (3.2)}$$

The extracted lipids are identified using Gas Chromatography (GC). Gas chromatography (GC) has been known as one of the best analysis techniques. This technique has seen highly sensitive, improved reproducibility and precision. This GC's advantage is getting the relatively specific analysis of fatty acids (Braithwaite and Smith, 1999) (Maziar Yahyav, 2012). A flame Ionisation detector (FID) is a practical GC route analysis of microalgal samples and this response to all organic elements (Sasić, 2008). The extracted lipid was analysed by GC using the software Agilent GC78ZOA. The FID uses a sample injector, detectors, GC injectors and a capillary column of 0.2 – 0.7mm. GC injectors and detectors of 100 m, head pressure of 3 to 40psi, injected at a flow rate of 0.5–15 mL/min, 0.1–8 µm, film thickness, the capacity of 100 mg/pack. The packed column has a diameter of 2-4mm, 10 – 40psi, length of 0.5 – 5m and film thickness of 0.1–8 µm. The Table 3. 6 shows the GC conditions used in this study. As hexane was used as a solvent for extraction, the GC blank was carried out using hexane.

About 1µl of the extracted lipid oil was injected into GC. Hydrogen, helium and nitrogen are used as carrier gas. Here the injected sample is separated due to the increased heat inside the oven. The separated components are analysed using a standard Supelco 37 component FAME mix to confirm the presence of each individual FAME peak, and the concentration of the individual peaks is calculated. To ensure the concentration standard, another GC sample analysis is carried out using 80:20 biodiesel and diesel from soya to prepare a comparison frame. The GC results of the 80:20 biodiesel and diesel from soya is represented in appendix C.2. The GC layout system used for identifying lipid components in this study shown in Figure 3. 9.

The AGILENT software produces peaks and their retention time, and the results are represented in Figure 3. 10. Mostly, the GC analysis run around an hour and the identified concentrations were determined by their peak area. The concentrations are calculated in µg/ml (ppb) and as a % of the total peak area. The concentrations (C) were calculated by the eqn.

(3.5) and the identified compounds, and their concentration were compared with the extracted microalgal oil.

$$C = \frac{pA(\text{sample})}{pA(\text{std})} \times \text{certified value}(\mu\text{g/ml}) \quad \text{Eqn. (3.5)}$$

Figure 3. 8: Lipid extraction Procedure - (a) Reflux (b) Solvent phase separation (c) Steam bath (d) Microalgal oil

Figure 3. 9: GC Layout

Figure 3. 10: A convectional GC analysis spectrum (Hamoudi-Belarbi *et al.*, 2018).

Table 3. 6: GC analysis conditions

Analysis conditions & parameters	Time (mins)	Temperature (°C)	Specifications
Flame detector	N/A	300	N/A
Column flow	1 ml	N/A	BPX-70. 50m × 0.25mm diameter × 0.25µm film thickness
Operating mode	N/A	N/A	Split less
Total running time	62	N/A	N/A
Injector	N/A	150	N/A
Oven	5	100	250@4/min

3.11 Response surface methodology (RSM)

To measure the lipid yield, statistical techniques were used to optimise and monitor the experimental and predicted conditions. Response surface methodology (RSM) is used to estimate the experimental variability; this method generally utilises the quantitative data from experiments to find the linear regression model, which generates output factors that are influenced by other similar factors (Myers H Raymond, 2016). The main benefits of this RSM are obtaining multiple factor levels for the experimental analysis with minimal levels of experimental data. This can efficiently and precisely optimise the equation for response factors by reducing the experimental cost (Montgomery, 2013).

3.12 Statistical analysis

The software Design-Expert 12.0.3 was used for the regression and graphical analysis of the data. A total of 17 experiments were determined by the design of experiments. Their results were evaluated from the lipid extraction parameters using 100 ml of the grown microalgae sample. The output response factor was set as lipid extraction (%) obtained after the extraction. Regression analysis was done with the experimental data used in this study with the values -1, 0 and +1. As found from the RSM, the quadratic model is fitted as all the experimental factors are studied independently (Carton and Olabi, 2010). The effect of independent factor influenced the dependent variable, and this was analysed by the quadratic equation [Eqn. (2.3)].

The analysis incorporates the Box-Behnken Design (BBD) to calculate the coefficients of the second-order polynomial regression model for pre-treatment techniques using three input factors. The software utilises variables A, B, and C to represent the input factors and analyse their responses.

In this study, each pre-treatment technique has three specific input parameters assigned. In the case of microwave pre-treatment, the software assigns the input factors as A - Microwave power, B - Microwave time, and C - Extraction time. Similarly, for HSH (Homogenising Speed Homogeniser) pre-treatment, A - Homogenising speed, B - Running time, and C - Extraction time.

The Optimal (custom) option within the RSM was chosen specifically for the Ultrasonic pre-treatment. This custom setup design includes three input factors: A for ultrasonic time, B for

extraction time, and C for frequency. As the ultrasonic machine used in this study has only two frequencies, it necessitated modifications in the Response Surface Methodology (RSM). Hence, the custom setup design with two numeric factors (A and B) and one categorical factor (C) was employed. The Table 3. 7illustrates pre-treatment techniques and their input conditions.

Table 3. 7: Pre-treatment methods and their RSM Reaction conditions used for lipid extraction

Symbols	Variables	Microwave			High Speed homogeniser			Ultrasonic				
		Levels	Variables	Levels	Variables	Levels	Variables	Levels				
		-1	0	1		-1	0	1				
A	Microwave power (W)	90	600	900	Speed (rpm)	6000	14000	22000	Ultrasonic time (mins)	10	15	20
B	Microwave time (mins)	90	135	180	Running time (mins)	10	15	20	Extraction time (Hrs)	2	3	4
C	Extraction time (Hrs)	2	3	4	Extraction time (Hrs)	2	3	4	Frequency (kHz)	37	N/A	80

3.12.1 RSM methodologies

This method is a mathematical procedure for optimising the output response (Lipid efficiency %), which is tested in all experimental treatments. In the experimental process, the limits of the input and output variables are assessed from the literature review and implemented for this investigation. When designing the mathematical model for the percentage of lipids recovered, the following approaches must be followed.

- **Identifying the boundaries of each factor:** A set of experiments were carried out to determine the limit of each input data using a microwave, high-speed homogenisation and ultrasonic. All of these experimental trials were carried out to the limits and specifications of the manufacturer. For the microwave, the Bosch HMT84M451B model was used with the experimental conditions between 90 to 900 W with microwave time between 90 and 180 secs. Moreover, for the high-speed homogeniser, Mxbaoheng HQ-2475 limits are set between the homogenising speed of 6000 to 22000 rpm with a running time between 5 mins to 15 mins. Similarly, for ultrasonic Fisherbrand FB11201, the boundary limits are frequency of 37 and 80 kHz with an exposure time

between 10 to 20 mins. The extraction reaction time for all the experimental analyses was assigned between 2 to 4 hrs.

- **Experimental analysis:** The cell disruption experiments were performed using the microwave, high-speed homogenisation and ultrasonic. The output responses were executed in line with the design matrix and in a randomised order to minimise any systematic error during the experimentation. The software design expert 12.0.1 was used to develop the coded data and generate the design matrix. The lipid recovered represents the rational responses, and all experimental errors will be stated in a mathematical expression. The lipid recovered represents the output responses, and all experimental errors will be stated in a mathematical expression.
- **Designing a mathematical model:** The model and the experimentation used here has 3 major factors showing the output response, which is indicated as $y = f(A, B, C)$. The A, B and C represents the input factors and y is the response (lipid efficiency). The quadratic eqn. (3.3) is rearranged to obtain the Eqn. (3.4)

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1A + \beta_2B + \beta_3C + \beta_{11}A^2 + \beta_{22}B^2 + \beta_{33}C^2 + \beta_{12}AB + \beta_{13}AC + \beta_{23}BC + \beta_{33}C^2 + \beta_{12}AB + \beta_{13}AC + \beta_{23}BC$$

Eqn. (3.4)

- **Reducing & finalising the model:** The eqn. (3.4) provides the final mathematical design with the significant and the non-significant terms, where the non-significant terms can be identified with p-value $> \alpha$. The reduction can be made manually by repeating the experiments or automatically using the software's selection procedures. The final model is achieved when all the necessary terms become significant.
- **Post analysis:** As the final model is developed, the factors and factor-interaction results will be illustrated using the software's perturbation and contour plots. The perturbation plot is beneficial for assessing the impact of all parameters at a specific location in the design process. In the case of more than two factors, this plot can be utilized to identify the elements that significantly influence the responses. The answer is illustrated by varying only one element while maintaining the other factors remain constant. A factor with a high slant or curve indicates that the reaction is responsive towards that factor.

A reasonably flat line indicates that the factor is insensitive to changes (Abbasi, Ekrami-Kakhki and Tahari, 2017). All those plots will also be displayed as 3D graphs that depict the response for the factors involved in input variables. Once the design model is finalised, it will be simple to optimise microalgal pre-treatment techniques with microwave, HSH and ultrasonic. The software implemented the regression analysis using statistical analysis to calculate the coefficients in the eqn. (3.4).

Examining the adequacy of the suitable model: Each term of the statistical significance mathematical model was evaluated using F-sequential, lack of fit and others like adequate precision, predicted R^2 , adequate R^2 and R^2 . In order to develop the adequacy of the model, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. ANOVA can be used to measure the model's and each term's measurements, p-value or Prob greater than F (Prob > F). The model is said to be adequate if the significance level, $\alpha = 0.05$, and the model's every term is seen to be within that range, then the model is said to be 95% reliable. To consider the lack of fit test, it can be seen as insignificant if the Prob >F value goes beyond the significance level. The sum of squares is indicated in term of SSi and the mean squares of the residuals and a correlation of term variance and residual variance are shown in MSR and Fcal – value.

3.12.2 Optimisation methodologies

The core optimisation objective using the software Design expert 12.0.1 is to look for various input factors and combine them simultaneously to study the operating input factors and output responses. This technique is also known as multiple response optimisation. Furthermore, numerical, and graphical optimisation strategies are widely employed to choose each factor with suggested targets and responses. In the general framework, numerical optimisation is applied to maximise or minimize responses depending on one or more various factors, in this study employs the Desirability Function Approach. The DFA utilizes a desirability function, denoted as $D_{(x)}$, which consists of multiple desirability values (d_i). Each desirability value ranges from the lowest to the highest, with a numerical range of 0 to 1. The goal is to achieve the highest combined desirability, computed by taking the geometric mean of all the desirability functions, and the graphical optimisation is utilised to identify multiple responses, and the design expert software briefly defines the areas on a contour plot, the critical response can be combined or layered. This empowers a conceptual look for the most suitable point and

delivers not only an optimum point (But in industrial operations, it is hard to state the specific point) but also the optimum region.

When dealing with multiple responses, incorporating a desirability function becomes crucial for effectively analysing and optimising the outcomes. The desirability function assigns individual desirability scores to each response and then combines them into an overall desirability score. This process involves assigning weights to each response based on their relative importance, and the software Design Expert 12.0.1 uses a scale of +, ++, +++, +++++, and ++++++ to define the desired levels of each response to have a look on graphical optimisation. By using these designations, the study can specify the desired values for certain factors and allow the output responses to vary accordingly within the defined desirability range. This approach facilitates the evaluation of the overall desirability of a specific factor combination and helps in making informed decisions during the optimisation process (Daramola *et al.*, 2019).

3.12.3 Numerical and graphical optimisation

Design of experiments optimisation seeks a mixture of factorial designs that meet specified requirements known as "optimisation criteria" at each of the responses and input variables (multiple response optimisation). Here, numerical, and graphical optimisation methodologies are applied to determine the desired targets for each input factor and output response (Sun *et al.*, 2022). The software shows different regions in the graphical optimisation feature where requirements fulfil the proposed criteria simultaneously. Superimposing or extending critical response contours on a contour plot accomplishes the optimisation, and the best understanding can then be found visually and selected. Grey shading denotes regions that fail to meet the optimisation criteria. As shown in Figure 3. 11, the area that is not shaded grey meets the objectives of each response.

Figure 3. 11: Graphical optimisation – Example (Godbole, Sabale and Mathur, 2020)

3.13 Conclusion

This chapter presents a comprehensive overview of the equipment, materials, and methods utilised in the research, encompassing the cultivation process, pre-treatment experiments, and FAME profile analysis. The fundamental equations underpinning this study are thoroughly explained and discussed. The methodologies employed for the cultivation of the microalgae species, including optical density calculations, pre-treatment processes, and their analysis parameters, are thoroughly outlined in this chapter. The chapter also delves into the calculations and analysis methods used to determine lipid efficiency. This includes a comprehensive examination of the various factors and parameters that contribute to lipid extraction.

Chapter 4. Results and mathematical modelling of microalgal strain *Chlorella vulgaris* on different pre-treatment techniques

4.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the experimental analysis of this study. This also states experimental studies, statistical analysis, and discussions of *Chlorella vulgaris*. With 100 ml of the sample, a set of 17 experiments were performed for all the pre-treating methods as proposed in this study (Microwave, high-speed homogeniser and ultrasonic) to enhance the lipid recovery. Microwave parameters are power (90, 600 and 900 w), microwave time (90,135 and 180 sec) and extraction time (2,3 and 4 hrs). Likewise, for high-speed homogeniser, the operating conditions are speed (6000, 14000, 22000rpm), running time (5,10 and 15mins) and extraction time (2,3 and 4hrs). The ultrasonic machine was operated with frequency (37 and 80kHz), running time (10, 15 and 20 mins) and extraction time (2,3 and 4hrs). These techniques showed an enhanced lipid percentage, and their results are represented in Appendix B.1. The mathematical model is performed for the design of experiments using Design expert software, and the results from the experiments were developed successfully from the output responses of the actual and predicted values. The RSM model was used to optimise the model by maximising the lipid recovery percentage for all the sets of experimental studies.

4.2 RSM modelling

The analysis employs Response Surface Methodology (RSM) to calculate the coefficients of the second-order polynomial regression model with three input factors for each of the pre-treatment techniques (RSM for lipid extraction are presented in Appendix B.3 to B.5). Based on the design of experiments, an equation for lipid extraction (%) can be derived using the quadratic model. For *C.Vulgaris* and its three pre-treatment methods, Equation (4.1, 4.2, and 4.3) represents the respective equations. In Eqn (4.1), A, B, and C signify the microwave power, microwave time, and extraction time. Similarly, in Eqn (4.2), A, B, and C denote the homogenising speed, running time, and extraction time. Finally, for ultrasonic pre-treatment, Eqn (4.3) features A, B, and C representing the ultrasonic time, extraction time, and frequency. The final mathematical model representing the response in terms of the significant factors for each pre-treatment methods, as determined by the software, is presented below:

$$\text{MW: Lipid extraction (\%)} = 12.74 + 2.79A + 1.62B - 0.5033C + 1.08AB - 0.6595AC + 0.6550BC - 0.1088B^2 - 0.7333C^2 \quad \text{Eqn. (4.1)}$$

$$\text{HSH: Lipid extraction (\%)} = 13.80 + 5.24A - 2.83B^2 - 3.08C^2 \quad \text{Eqn. (4.2)}$$

$$\text{Ultrasonic: Lipid extraction (\%)} = 8.06 + 1.82A + 0.8422B + 2.54C - 1.50A^2 \quad \text{Eqn. (4.3)}$$

The quadratic model results are shown in Table 4. 1 (microwave), Table 4. 3 (HSH) and Table 4. 5 (Ultrasonic). Based on these tables, it was determined that the second-order quadratic model suits this analysis because the p-value is not more than 0.05. Also, the values of R² are no more than 0.2 and not greater than 0.9. The ANOVA was done to examine the similar factors that influence lipid extraction, and the results are shown in Table 4. 2 (microwave), Table 4. 4 (HSH) and Table 4. 6 (Ultrasonic). From these tables, it can be seen that the model F-value for the three methods is 37.38, 9.31 and 21.76, respectively, which implies that the models are significant. There is only a 0.01% chance that this large F-value could have occurred due to noise for microwave and ultrasonic models. However, for the HSH model, there is a chance that 0.38% of the F-value could have emerged due to noise. P-values <0.05 indicate that the model terms are significant. The lipid extraction (%) is the significant factor shown as a p-value with a value less than 0.05, indicating that the model is significant. In order to calculate the accuracy of the model, lack of fit is applied, and the p-value of the lack of fit has to be >0.05. In this design, the p-value of the lack of fit & F value for the microwave model is 0.4826 & 0.9895, HSH model p-value of the lack of fit & F values are 0.2459 and 2.08. Also, the ultrasonic model p-value of the lack of fit is 0.1307, and F-value is 4.28. These p-values of the lack of fit and F-values imply that the lack of fit is insignificant relative to the pure error. There is a 48.26% (microwave), 24.59% (HSH) and 13.07% (Ultrasonic) chance that a lack of fit F-value this large could occur due to noise. The presence of a non-significant lack of fit in the analysis is an encouraging outcome that signifies the validity and logical nature of the model. (Kashyap, Gogate and Joshi, 2019). This result indicates that the model is fitting well to the experimental data, supporting its reliability and usefulness for predicting the response variable under different conditions.

Table 4. 1: Microwave - RSM Response for Lipid extraction (*Chlorella vulgaris*)

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Predicted R ²	
Linear	< 0.0001	0.0631	0.6927	
2FI	0.0584	0.1231	0.6664	
Quadratic	0.0237	0.4826	0.8027	Suggested
Cubic	0.4826			Aliased

Table 4. 2: ANOVA for Microwave quadratic model – *Chlorella vulgaris*

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	57.02	9	6.34	37.38	< 0.0001	significant
A- Microwave Power	28.30	1	28.30	166.93	< 0.0001	
B-Microwave Time	18.83	1	18.83	111.10	< 0.0001	
C-Extraction Time	1.83	1	1.83	10.77	0.0135	
AB	3.04	1	3.04	17.95	0.0039	
AC	1.14	1	1.14	6.75	0.0355	
BC	1.72	1	1.72	10.12	0.0155	
A ²	0.8557	1	0.8557	5.05	0.0595	
B ²	0.0488	1	0.0488	0.2876	0.6084	
C ²	2.22	1	2.22	13.07	0.0086	
Residual	1.19	7	0.1695			
Lack of Fit	0.5054	3	0.1685	0.9895	0.4826	not significant
Pure Error	0.6811	4	0.1703			
Cor Total	58.21	16				

Fit statistics - Standard deviation - 0.4117, Mean - 12.69, Coefficient of variance (CV) % - 3.24, R² - 0.9796, Predicted R² - 0.8027, Adequate precision - 18.5369.

Table 4. 3: HSH - RSM Response for Lipid extraction (*Chlorella vulgaris*)

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.0084	0.0542	0.3121	
2FI	0.4218	0.0468	0.1364	
Quadratic	0.0144	0.2459	0.2017	Suggested
Cubic	0.2459			Aliased

Table 4. 4: ANOVA for HSH quadratic model – *Chlorella vulgaris*

Source	Sum Squares	of Df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	366.09	9	40.68	9.31	0.0038	significant
A-Speed	219.56	1	219.56	50.26	0.0002	
B-Running time	6.53	1	6.53	1.50	0.2609	
C-Extraction Time	4.71	1	4.71	1.08	0.3335	
AB	14.18	1	14.18	3.25	0.1146	
AC	22.18	1	22.18	5.08	0.0589	
BC	2.69	1	2.69	0.6157	0.4584	
A ²	12.95	1	12.95	2.96	0.1288	
B ²	33.81	1	33.81	7.74	0.0272	
C ²	39.98	1	39.98	9.15	0.0192	
Residual	30.58	7	4.37			
Lack of Fit	18.62	3	6.21	2.08	0.2459	not significant
Pure Error	11.95	4	2.99			
Cor Total	396.67	16		9.31		

Fit statistics - Standard deviation - 2.09, Mean - 10.19, Coefficient of variance (CV) % - 20.51, R² - 0.9229, Predicted R² - 0.2017, Adequate precision - 9.4747

Table 4. 5: Ultrasonic - RSM Response for Lipid extraction (*Chlorella vulgaris*)

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Predicted R ²	
Linear	<0.0001	0.0802	0.7828	
2FI	0.5349	0.0677	0.3865	
Quadratic	0.0458	0.1307	0.6820	Suggested
Cubic	0.1307			Aliased

Table 4. 6: ANOVA for Ultrasonic quadratic model – *Chlorella vulgaris*

Source	Sum Squares	of Df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	170.15	8	21.27	21.76	0.0001	significant
A- Ultrasonic time	25.99	1	25.99	26.59	0.0009	
B- Extraction time	6.68	1	6.68	6.84	0.0309	
C- Frequency	104.05	1	104.05	106.44	<0.0001	
AB	0.2928	1	0.2928	0.2996	0.5991	
AC	0.9940	1	0.9940	1.02	0.3428	
BC	0.3197	1	0.3197	0.3271	0.5831	
A ²	7.99	1	7.99	8.17	0.0212	
B ²	0.2540	1	0.2540	0.2598	0.6240	
Residual	7.82	8	0.9775			
Lack of Fit	6.86	5	1.37	4.28	0.1307	not significant
Pure Error	0.9621	3	0.3207			
Cor Total	177.97	16				

Fit statistics - Standard deviation - 0.9887, Mean - 7.29, Coefficient of variance (CV) % - 13.57, R² - 0.9561, Predicted R² - 0.6820, Adequate precision - 14.4772

The fit statistics analysis can be used to investigate the actual data from the factor parameters. The model's p-value is less than 0.05, and the lack of fit p-value is greater than 0.05, with R^2 greater than 0.9 indicate its adequacy (Ansori and Mahfud, 2022) (Kashyap, Gogate and Joshi, 2019). Adequate precision measures the signal-to-noise ratio. An adequate precision ratio greater than 4 is desirable, and the value of adequate precisions are 18.5369, 9.4747 and 14.4772, indicating an adequate signal (Kashyap, Gogate and Joshi, 2019). Also, the proposed model's R^2 values are 0.9796, 0.9229 and 0.9561, showing 97.96%, 92.29% and 95.61% chances of differences in experimental response values. A high percentage of R^2 shows an excellent correlation between the predicted/experimental responses, and the proposed model has good reliability in finding lipid extraction (%). The fit summary output reveals that, based on the statistical analysis, the linear model for the response variable is highly recommended for further investigation. This recommendation is supported by the maximum values obtained for the predicted R^2 . Additionally, the ANOVA results indicate an adequate precision ratio of above 4 for the response surface linear model. This signifies that the entire model is highly adequate and suggests adequate response capability. In conclusion, the adequacy of the model is confirmed by the acceptance of the reduced model in essential statistical tests. This indicates that the model can be effectively utilised for predicting the responses and performing optimisation processes.

4.3 Model verification

To confirm the accuracy of the model and the experimental data, the validation for the model is processed for adequacy check. A precise mathematical design can come up with a practical approach to the actual process.

Figure 4. 1 (a) displays the perturbation plot, providing an illustration of the impact of microwave power (A), microwave time (B), and extraction time (C) on the response variable. The plot demonstrates distinct trends for each factor within the specified optimising range. Notably, the inclination of line A indicates that microwave power significantly influences the lipid percentage compared to the other two factors. Similarly, the upward trend of line B suggests a combined effect of microwave power and time on the lipid extraction. Further analysis reveals that an increase in lipid extraction (%) is primarily attributed to variations in microwave power and heating time. Higher power levels correspond to a greater production of lipids, while longer microwave running times contribute to enhanced lipid recovery.

Conversely, the downward trajectory of line C indicates that extraction time has a lesser impact compared to the other factors. Furthermore, the importance of microwave power in cell disruption and lipid enhancement becomes evident. Previous research conducted by the (Prajapati, Kodgire and Singh Kachhwaha, 2022a) has demonstrated that microwave power plays a pivotal role in microwave-assisted microalgal pre-treatment. Additionally, by (Sivaramakrishnan *et al.*, 2020a), it has been found that prolonged microwave time positively correlates with improved cell disruption efficiency. Consequently, based on the perturbation plot, an increase in power consistently leads to a higher lipid production.

And the Figure 4. 1 (b) presents the perturbation plot, showing the interaction between the input processing conditions of speed (A), running time (B), and extraction time (C). This plot provides valuable insights into the significance of these factors. The observed lines indicate that the running speed of the homogeniser (A) plays a more substantial role compared to the other two factors. As depicted by the increasing line A, it can be concluded that the lipid extraction increases with an increase in the running speed. This suggests that higher running speeds of the homogeniser lead to a greater lipid yield compared to the other factors. Conversely, the dropping line B indicates that running time does not have a significant impact on lipid recovery. Similarly, line C, representing extraction time, shows a decreasing trend from the midpoint, suggesting that it also has a relatively lesser effect on the final lipid yield. These observations align with the findings of the (Wang, Yin and Zeng, 2022b), demonstrating that increasing the homogenising speed enhances cell disruption and subsequently improves lipid extraction. Therefore, the perturbation plot represents the importance of the running speed of the homogeniser in maximising lipid yield.

Figure 4. 1 (c & d) shows the perturbation plot which indicates the reaction between the input process conditions of Ultrasonic time (A) and Extraction time (B). From these plots, it can be studied that the increase in lipid extraction (%) is because of ultrasonication time and extraction time for two of the frequency levels (37 and 80 kHz). The lines A and B shows the effectiveness of ultrasonic time and extraction time, respectively. From this plots, it is clearly seen that the dominating factor in both of the microalgal cell discretion using ultrasonic technique is ultrasonic time. The incline of the extraction time is directly proportional to this relevant factor and the steeper slope of the ultrasonic exposure time indicating as a more effective parameter. The (Ren *et al.*, 2019b) study focused on ultrasonication and its impact on lipid yield it was

observed that increasing ultrasonication time leads to an enhanced lipid yield. This finding aligns with the perturbation plot in this study for microalgal ultrasonication pre-treatment.

Figure 4. 2 (a, b and c) shows the predicted versus actual plot, revealing a close alignment of data points along a diagonal line. This indicates that the predicted model is well-suited to the experimental data. The plot serves as a valuable tool for identifying any discrepancies between the model's predictions and the actual observations. It highlights any potential deviations from the expected relationship between the variables. Specifically, the plot often exhibits a cluster of data points in the lower-left region, while a 45-degree line is typically used as a reference to divide the data sets equally (Das and Mishra, 2017).

Furthermore, the Figure 4. 3 (a, b, and c) showcases a diagnostic tool that examines the relationship between the normal % probability and the internally studentized residuals. This assessment allows for the evaluation of model assumptions and the adequacy of the normal distribution of the experimental values. The proximity of the data points to the reference line indicates satisfactory adherence to the assumptions. In addition, Figure 4. 4 (a, b, and c) presents the relationship between the predicted values and the internally studentized residuals, providing further insight into the model's suitability. The constant variance observed across all response values and the random scattering of data points between +3, 0, and -3 signify a well-fitting model (Abbasi, Ekrami-Kakhki and Tahari, 2017).

These plots play a critical role in assessing the adequacy and performance of the model, providing valuable information on the alignment between predicted and actual data points. The findings derived from these plots support the conclusion that the model is satisfactory for the given experimental data.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 4. 1: *Chlorella vulgaris* - (a) Perturbation plot for lipid extraction (%) – Microwave. (b) Perturbation plot for lipid extraction (%) – HSH. (c) Perturbation plot for 37 kHz ultrasonic lipid extraction (%). (d) Perturbation plot for 80 kHz ultrasonic lipid extraction (%).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4. 2 : *Chlorella vulgaris* - (a) Predicted vs actual plot – Microwave. (b) Predicted vs actual plot – HSH. (c) Predicted vs actual plot – Ultrasonic.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4. 3: *Chlorella vulgaris* - (a) Internally studentized residuals vs normal 1% probability – Microwave. (b) Internally studentized residuals vs normal 1% probability – HSH. (c) Internally studentized residuals vs normal 1% probability – Ultrasonic.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4. 4: *Chlorella vulgaris* - (a) Predicted vs internally studentized residuals – Microwave. (b) Predicted vs internally studentized residuals – HSH. (c) Predicted vs internally studentized residuals – Ultrasonic.

4.4 *Chlorella Vulgaris* - 3-D Response Surface Result Discussion

4.4.1 3D RSM – Microwave

Figure 4. 5 and Figure 4. 6 shows the graphical RSM three dimensional (3D) plots of the response in lipid extraction (%) over power. The impact of the power and the heating time was calculated and represented in the Figure 4. 5, the plot indicates the power between 900 to 90w with heating times between 180 and 90 secs. At a fixed factor of 3 hours of extraction time, the lipid extraction (%) decreases from 19 to 11%. The final lipid extraction percentage is 42.10%. The decrease in lipid yield also might be because of the cell's inability to during the microwave treatment process. It is difficult to break the cell to extract lipids even at maximum power and low heating time. As represented in Figure 4. 6, at 900 w with heating times between 180 to 90 secs and increasing the extraction time in actual factor of 4 hours, the lipid extraction (%) decreases from 17 to 11% with a final lipid percentage of 35.29%. The variation of lipid extraction (%) was investigated, and it concluded that the higher lipid yield concentration percentage was obtained due to increased power and the volume of pre-treated microalgae concerning increased heating time. Both factors are considered to be more significant. Apart from extraction time, the power and heating time plays a prominent role in the microwave-assisted lipid extraction process.

In the Figure 4. 7, at a fixed number of 135 secs heating time, the power was considered from 900 to 90 W with 4 to 3 hours of extraction time. It was observed that the lipid extraction (%) drops from 14.2 to 10%. The final recovered lipid extraction (%) at this extraction time is 29.57%. In the Figure 4. 8, with a fixed microwave power of 90 w, with exposure time from 180 to 90 secs the lipid percentage decreases from 11 to 9% with a final product of 18.18%. This is because the higher microwave power may encourage the extraction process towards the microalgae for increasing lipid efficiency. The result states that raising the power along with heating time and reducing the extraction time might remain the same as the efficiency of the output lipid yield. It is better to find a maximum extraction time with furthermore experiments, where the cell is fully ruptured, releasing lipids. Also, cell disruption may not have a significant effect because of the cell's inability to during the microwave treatment.

Figure 4. 5: *Chlorella vulgaris* RSM plot in 3D for power and time for amount of lipid extracted (extraction time 3 hours)

Figure 4. 6: *Chlorella vulgaris* RSM plot in 3D for power and time for amount of lipid extracted (extraction time 4 hours)

Figure 4. 7: *Chlorella vulgaris* RSM plot in 3D for power and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (Heating time – 135 sec)

Figure 4. 8: *Chlorella vulgaris* RSM plot in 3D for time and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (Microwave power – 90 w)

In summary, the increase in microwave power can significantly increase lipid extraction (%). This technique demonstrates that at the power of 600W have seen to disrupt cells and enhance lipid (%). This correlates with the research done by references (Cheng, Huang, Li, *et al.*, 2014b, 2014c; Onumaegbu *et al.*, 2019a; Ashok *et al.*, 2021a; Qu *et al.*, 2021a; Prajapati, Kodgire and Singh Kachhwaha, 2022b). This study also proves that the input of heat energy is beneficial in converting the transition state to FAME, thus the formation of the compound is increased (Ashok *et al.*, 2021b). Although a decrease in lipid efficiency is observed with reduction in power and heating time, as some of the microalgal cells were left undisrupted. However, when the microwave power is increased from 495 – 900W, an increase in efficiency can be seen. may be, this not possible if the heating time is increased more than 180 secs. The efficiency might gradually fall as more amount of the liquid is vaporised. The extraction time after pre-treatment plays a significant part in lipid extraction (%). The more time given for the extraction reaction provides an enhanced outcome of lipid efficiency using microwave pre-treatment. Some literature was studied to investigate the effects of microwave assisted pre-treatment to

increase the lipid productivity in order to produce biofuel. Heat energy is needed to transform the reactant from the transition state to FAME, thus increasing the temperature is favourable for the formation of the product (Ashok *et al.*, 2021c). The results are also similar to the study conducted by (Cheng, Huang, Li, *et al.*, 2014d). Also, the extraction time set in this study (3.5 to 4 hrs with heating time 180 secs) seems to be satisfactory in order to get the complete extraction under this treatment. Hence, an enhanced lipid extraction is obtained owing to increased cell disruption with microwave method. (Onumaegbu *et al.*, 2019b), carried out microwave pre-treatment with the similar extraction times used in this study with *Scenedesmus quadricauda* and concluded that the more reaction time will destroy the cell completely and will result in reduced lipid efficiency. Enhanced lipid efficiency is achieved, extracted from *Botryococcus braunii* LB 572 with 2450 MHz in 20 mins at 150°C and power of 1250 W were found to have more fatty acids in C14 – C24 (Gim and Kim, 2018b). This analysis shows that more lipid efficiency is generated with higher microwave power. Thus, this results are well agreed with references (Lee, Lewis and Ashman, 2012c; Biller and Ross, 2014; Dai, Chen and Chen, 2014; Yan *et al.*, 2020a) where these researchers concluded that the increased power would have a very significant influence on microalgal cells. Future studies should try to focus on utilising the ionic liquid for biodiesel production. In this study, without using drying or centrifuge techniques and saving more energy and time, a short time of 180 secs and power of 600 W gave an output of 15.24% lipid efficiency in *C.vulgaris*. This study has a higher productivity rate using microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* in microwave treatment, and the results correlate with all the studies discussed.

4.4.2 3D Graphical – High pressure homogeniser

The interaction between the speed, running time and extraction time were evaluated by analysing the 3D surface plot. The Figure 4. 9 and Figure 4. 10, indicated that when the speed of the homogeniser increases along with running time, the lipid percentage seems to increase. However, the rate was gradually decrease with the decrease in running speed. From the Figure 4. 9, at a running time of 15 mins, and considering the homogenisation speed of 22000 rpm and 6000 rpm and a fixed extraction time of 2 hrs. The % of the lipid recovery falls from 11% to 2% with a final % recovered at this point is 81.81%. This result says that increasing the running speed and reducing the running time looks like this does not significantly influence lipid efficiency. Sometimes, the over-running time can influence the cell disintegration, and this may be attributed to the cell wall, which will not be disrupted entirely at the times of pre-

treating techniques to enhance the lipid (%). In the Figure 4. 10, at a running speed of 14000rpm and a running time 15 mins with a fixed extraction time, it can be observed at the speed of 22000rpm, and 6000 rpm with 15 mins running speed, the lipid extraction (%) decreases from 12% to 2.5% with a final lipid recovery percentage of 80%. This result confirms that low running speed and high speed enhance lipid efficiency, but longer extraction times and faster running speeds could reduce lipid efficiency.

Figure 4. 9: *Chlorella vulgaris* RSM plot in 3D for speed and running time for amount of lipid extracted (extraction time 2 hours)

Figure 4. 10 : *Chlorella vulgaris* RSM plot in 3D for speed and running time for amount of lipid extracted (extraction time 4 hours)

Figure 4. 11: *Chlorella vulgaris* RSM plot in 3D for speed and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (running time – 10 mins)

Figure 4. 12: *Chlorella vulgaris* RSM plot in 3D for running time and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (Speed – 22000rpm)

The graphical plot in the Figure 4. 11 and Figure 4. 12 shows the output responses of the lipid efficiency with homogenisation speed and extraction time. From the Figure 4. 11, at a fixed running time of 10 mins, and the homogenisation speed of 22000 rpm and 6000 rpm the lipid percentage decreases from 17.5% to 5% and with a final lipid recovery rate of 72%. This

decrease is due to the cell wall disruption may be highly influenced during the increased running time. In the Figure 4. 12, at a fixed speed factor of 22000 rpm, considering the running time from 15 to 5 mins with extraction time from 4 to 2 hrs, the lipid extraction (%) decreases from 11.24% to 2.5% with a final recovery of 77% lipid extraction. There may also be a chance that the speed time will also affect the temperature in the sample due to the high running speed, and this might also influence the cell disruption rate.

This study proves that the homogenisation speed of 22000 rpm for 10 mins has seen algal cells disrupted for enhancing lipid efficiency (%), and this correlates with the research conducted by references (Bernaerts *et al.*, 2017; Zhou *et al.*, 2017; Wang, Yin and Zeng, 2022a). The set of experiments done in this study proves that decreasing the speed reduces lipid efficiency as most of the algal cells are left untreated, which will directly affect the efficiency rate of the lipid produced—the extraction time of 3-3.5hr looks to be good enough for a complete extraction (Onumaegbu *et al.*, 2018b). This study clearly says that it is better to stay with an optimum speed, and the maximum speed and time can kill the cells giving out less efficiency during extraction. Hereby, the efficiency of the lipid percentage increased as the HSH treatment gives a high cell disruption rate. Few research from the literature have been studied to look on the effects of lipid extraction from HSH method. Mengwai *et al.* studied the effect of *Synechococcus sp.* PCC 7002 with a shear speed of 10000 rpm for 1 min (5 cycles) and recorded a lipid content of 8.82%. This present research indicates that higher lipid efficiency was achieved from HSH pre-treatment. This study also correlates well that the increased shear rates can increase the lipid outcome (Ginzberg, Korin and Arad, 2008)(Wang, Yin and Zeng, 2022a)(Zhou *et al.*, 2017). Another study conducted by (Bernaerts *et al.*, 2017), using microalgal biomass *Porphyridium cruentum* ran for 5500 rpm for 10 min resulted in enriching ω 3-PUFA food products without disturbing the product's structural characteristics. (Malafronte *et al.*, 2021), carried out research with *Laminaria digitata* by combination of thermal treatment (70 °C 1hr) followed by HSH 150 – 500 bar was able to disintegrate algal cells and extracting higher amount of monosaccharide and polysaccharide content. A different study conducted by (Singh *et al.*, 2022b), with homogenization speed of 12000rpm for 15 mins using microalgae *Chlorella sp.* had seen a lipid content of 13.05%. Similar results were obtained by references (Huppertz, 2011; Guo *et al.*, 2014; Imatoukene *et al.*, 2020; Yildiz *et al.*, 2021; Singh *et al.*, 2022b) agrees that the increase in speed of the homogeniser with a considered amount of running time has a capability to extract the organic compounds from

them. In this research study, a homogenisation speed of 22000 rpm for 10 mins increase the microalgae lipid extraction (%) to 19% in *C.Vulgaris* with higher lipid productivity rate.

4.4.3 3D Graphical – Ultrasonic

Figure 4. 13 and Figure 4. 14 shows the graphical RSM three dimensional (3D) plots of the response in lipid extraction (%) over Frequency. In the Figure 4. 13, at a fixed frequency of 37 kHz, the ultrasonication running time was considered between 20 mins and 10 mins at an extraction time between 4 and 2 hours. It can be seen that the lipid efficiency falls from 6.5% to 2.5%, with a final recovered lipid efficiency rate of 61%. And the Figure 4. 14, with a fixed frequency of 80 kHz and considering the running time between 20 and 10 mins at an extraction time between 4 and 2 hours, a final extraction rate of 45% is obtained from the efficiencies decreasing from 12% to 6.5%. These changes can be seen because of higher frequency, which motivates the cells in the microalgae to extract yield and get a higher lipid efficiency. Moreover, the lower efficiency indicates that the cells are not fully disrupted and fail to extract as much as lipid yield. In summary, the increase in ultrasonic frequency has an excellent ability to increase lipid extraction (%).

Figure 4. 13: *Chlorella vulgaris* RSM plot in 3D for ultrasonic time and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (Frequency – 37 kHz)

Figure 4. 14: *Chlorella vulgaris* RSM plot in 3D for ultrasonic time and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (Frequency – 80 kHz)

The ultrasound method generates cavitation inside the cell structure by damaging and altering the membrane permeability, thus releasing the lipids. The applied ultrasonic frequency plays a significant role in lipid extraction, but only a few experiments are conducted to view the effects of lipid recovery. In this study, using a frequency of 80 kHz, a maximum efficiency of 11.54%

for *C.Vulgaris* was obtained, which is very high when compared with 37 Hz frequency. The biomass concentration also seemed to be nearly the same, but a higher efficiency was obtained in *Nannochloropsis oculata*. These results can conclude that a higher frequency must break the cell to extract the lipids from the microalgae. The cell disruption was observed from the ultrasonic technique, but a little droplet was seen on the top layer after pre-treatment. These droplets are meant to be free of pre-treatment and dissolve with the external environment, such as a solvent (Zhang *et al.*, 2014). But because of using hexane, a high polarity solvent, the lipids in the droplets are covered and gathered in the hexane layer. In comparison with previous studies (Converti *et al.*, 2009; Keris-Sen *et al.*, 2014; Zhang *et al.*, 2014, 2016; dos Santos *et al.*, 2015), and (Merouani *et al.*, 2016) conducted a study with a rising frequency range of 20 kHz – 1100Khz for hydrogen production. They explained the effects of frequencies to generate energy production. (Zhang *et al.*, 2016) experimented with *Trichosporon oleaginous* at a frequency of 520 kHz for lipid extraction and obtained a biodiesel yield of 90%. Considering these factors, 80 kHz seems to extract high lipid efficiency in this study.

The exposure time of the ultrasonication exhibited a high correlation efficiency regardless of the frequency and reaction time. (Converti *et al.*, 2009) evaluated *N.Oculata* by ultrasonic technique at 6 hr extraction time using the Bligh and dyer process and got a 24% lipid yield. *Chlorella pyrenoidosa* biomass was studied by (D’oca *et al.*, 2011) with ultrasound pre-treatment for a running time of 20 mins and, using the same Bligh and dyer extraction procedure, obtained a lipid yield of 12.20%. (Joyce, Wu and Mason, 2010) concluded with their experimental studies that increasing temperature and ultrasonic running for 30 mins does not affect cell disruption. The green microalgae *Spirulina platensis* with ultrasonic power of 100 W and 30 kHz was analysed by (Tavakoli *et al.*, 2021) with varying extraction times between 5 and 30 minutes using ethanol as solvent observed an excellent yield of carotenoids in 20 mins of running time. In this study, 20 mins running time showed an increased lipid recovery which could be associated with a large number of microalgal cells is disrupted. It should be noted that the high extraction reaction may kill the cell during the reflux process, so it can be seen that it is better to stay within a time frame of 3 – 4 hours of extraction time to get the desired amount of lipids. These findings in this present study suggest that 4 hours of extraction time with 20 mins of running time will be a good factor in lipid extraction process parameter conditions.

4.5 Validation of the experimental results

Generally speaking, the lipid extraction using the mechanical techniques, the primary concept lies behind here is the breaking process of the cell wall. For validating this model, 2 sets of experiments in each of the methods (microwave, HSH & ultrasonic) were performed under the optimum parameters that are predicted and the results are represented in Table 4. 7.

Table 4. 7: Microalgal pre-treatment techniques and their experimental validation results - *Chlorella vulgaris*

<u><i>Chlorella vulgaris</i></u>				
Run	Microwave power (w)	Microwave time (Mins)	Extraction time (Hrs)	Lipid efficiency (%)
1	600	90	2	Predicted model: 12.10 Validation model: 14.01
2	90	135	2	Predicted model: 14.58 Validation model: 14.86
Run	Homogenising speed (rpm)	Running time (mins)	Extraction time (Hr)	Lipid efficiency (%)
1	22000	10	2	Predicted model: 17.33 Validation model: 18.23
2	6000	5	3	Predicted model: 5.31 Validation model: 3.26
Run	Ultrasonic frequency (rpm)	Ultrasonic time (mins)	Extraction time (Hr)	Lipid efficiency (%)
1	80	15	2	Predicted model: 9.69 Validation model: 11.22
2	80	15	3	Predicted model: 10.60 Validation model: 12.94

The fair correction between the experimental and the predicted values confirms the model adequacy. Moreover, all the pre-treatment techniques and their regression model for and their responses had high coefficient determination. Hence, the establishment of the optimum conditions will try to reduce the overall production cost process and will also provide a basis for further studies of the microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* in pre-treatment.

4.6 Optimisation of lipid extraction

The study presented in the quadratic model equation briefly describes the effects of the processing input parameters on the output responses of lipid efficiency (%), and the optimisation is done in Design expert 12.0v software. Every optimum condition and responding have a relative strength compared to the other factors and responses. Significance ranges from the least adequate number of 1 (+) to the most significant essential factor of a critical value of 5 (++++). The basic principle of optimisation is based on maximising the final product, which helps to predict the total processing and extraction cost. The graphical optimisation pictures clearly show two different regions of yellow and grey. The yellow region indicates that the analysed parameters are feasible, whereas the responses with no goal are indicated in grey. From Figure 4. 15, lipid extraction of 13.23% was recovered from microwave power 600w for 120 sec and extraction time of 2 hours. Figure 4. 16 shows that 16.29% was obtained from an HSH speed of 14000 rpm, 5 mins running time and extraction time of 2 hours. Figure 4. 17 shows that lipid extraction of 10.25% was acquired from 80 kHz frequency, 15 mins exposure time and 2 hours extraction time.

Figure 4. 15: *Chlorella vulgaris* Graphical optimisation with minimising power, running time and extraction time with maximising lipid extraction - Microwave

Figure 4. 16: *Chlorella vulgaris* Graphical optimisation with minimising speed, running time and extraction time with maximising lipid extraction – HSH

Figure 4. 17: *Chlorella vulgaris* Graphical optimisation with minimising frequency, exposure time and extraction time with maximising lipid extraction - Ultrasonic

4.7 Effects of pre-treatment techniques on *Chlorella vulgaris*

Extraction experiments were conducted on untreated algal species using hexane, methanol, and concentrated sulfuric acid to assess the influence of pre-treatment on lipid efficiency. A minimum reaction time of 2 hours was employed, and the results were compared to the lipid efficiency obtained after pre-treatment. The untreated microalgae, *Chlorella vulgaris*, exhibited a final lipid efficiency of 4.64%. The Figure 4. 18 shows the maximum lipid extraction from pre-treatment techniques and the untreated. The results of the pre-treatment techniques are presented in appendix B.1.

Figure 4. 18: Effect of lipid efficiency (%) for the untreated and pre-treated *Chlorella vulgaris*

To confirm that cell disruption was a result of the microwave power and time used during pre-treatment, a compound microscope was utilised to observe changes in the cell wall. Initially, with lower power, the *C.Vulgaris* cells appeared to be ruptured. However, with increased power, the cells formed clusters, leading to increased lipid yield. Nevertheless, excessive power caused outer cell wall bursts, resulting in increased cell disruption. In comparison to the untreated samples, microwave pre-treated *C. vulgaris* demonstrated a maximum lipid yield of 15.24%.

The HSH mechanical force applied during the processing technique ensures thorough mixing of microalgae and cell disruption. Higher speed was found to enhance cell disruption efficiency and lipid yield, with the algae forming clusters. Under the compound microscope, similar cluster formations were observed during lipid extraction from microalgae, resulting in an enhanced lipid extraction of 18.65% and a higher lipid yield of 75.13%.

The ultrasonic technique effectively disrupts algal cells and facilitates the release of lipids. The study demonstrated that increasing the frequency led to enhanced lipid yield, with ultrasonication performed at 37 and 80 kHz frequencies. Compared to the untreated samples, *Chlorella vulgaris* exhibited an increased lipid percentage of 11.54% after ultrasonic pre-treatment. This indicates a 59.79% improvement achieved through ultrasonic treatment.

Furthermore, the effects of various pre-treatment methods on lipid extraction were assessed, revealing that the extraction procedure had minimal impact across all methods. These findings align with the perturbation plots Figure 4. 1, which indicate that extraction time has a less effect.

On making a concluding remarks on the effects of the pre-treatment methods on *Chlorella vulgaris*, once the microwave pre-treatment technique is implemented in fresh algal biomass, high-intensity absorption occurs because of the higher water content. The comparative investigation of the microwave and HSH were exciting. The microwave system achieved a vastly higher cell disruption rate in a short time despite the HSH extraction rate requiring some extra running time. This suggests that the cell damage methodology differed between all these pre-treatment techniques with differing final lipid yield percentages. This could be attributable to the tiring behaviour of the microwave's cyclic heating, indicating that the disturbance of the cell wall involves more than just a heat factor. In some aspects, the efficiency was enhanced through the mechanical disruption method via homogeniser. This is probably due to the high efficiency and impactful research capacity corresponding approach in addition to the other mechanical pre-treatment installations. The ultrasonic result of this research indicates that although relatively lower lipid rates compared with other pre-treatment techniques, ultrasonic is still effective in both microalgae cases.

4.8 Conclusion

The wet microalgal biomass of *Chlorella vulgaris* analysed in this research exhibited enhanced lipid extraction efficiencies of 15% using microwave-assisted treatment, 18% using high-speed homogenization, and 12% with ultrasonic treatment coupled with a Concentrated sulphuric acid and methanol extraction process. These results demonstrate the sustainability and efficacy of the wet method for utilising algae biomass. The optimisation of microwave-assisted treatment involved determining the optimal factors of 900W power, 180 seconds of heating time, and 3.5 hours of extraction time. Similarly, for high-speed homogenisation, the optimal parameters were identified as 22000 rpm speed, 5 minutes of running time, and a 3-hour extraction process. For ultrasonic treatment, the optimal parameters were found to be 80 kHz frequency, 15 minutes of exposure time, and a 3-hour extraction duration. The implementation of response surface methodology (RSM) optimisation in this research demonstrated that varying the factors significantly increased the efficiency of the output response. The quadratic parameters exhibited a notable impact on the output response, indicating the suitability of the design for Box-Behnken simulations. This process of microalgal lipid extraction using the optimised methods holds great potential for the production of biodiesel feedstock. By offering a sustainable alternative to fossil fuels, this approach contributes to the development of environmentally friendly energy sources. The findings of this research highlight the importance of efficient and effective techniques for the production of biodiesel from microalgae, ultimately supporting the advancement of renewable energy technologies.

Chapter 5. Results and mathematical modelling of microalgal strain *Nannochloropsis Oculata* on pre-treatment techniques

5.1 Introduction

This chapter focuses on the experimental research conducted for this study, specifically regarding the investigation of *Nannochloropsis Oculata*. It encompasses the experimental design, statistical analysis, and in-depth discussions of the findings. A series of 17 experiments were conducted as assigned by Design – Expert software, with each experiment using a sample volume of 100 ml. The primary objective of these experiments was to explore the effectiveness of various pre-treatment methods in enhancing lipid recovery. Microwave parameters are power (90, 600 and 900 w), microwave time (90, 135 and 180 sec) and extraction time (2, 3 and 4 hrs). Likewise, for high-speed homogeniser, the operating conditions are speed (6000, 14000, 22000 rpm), running time (5, 10 and 15 mins) and extraction time (2, 3 and 4 hrs). The ultrasonic machine was operated at different frequencies (37 kHz and 80 kHz), running times (10 mins, 15 mins, and 20 mins), and extraction times (2 hrs, 3 hrs, and 4 hrs). Through these experiments, the aim was to extract lipids and optimize the processing factors for improved lipid recovery from *Nannochloropsis Oculata*.

5.2 RSM Modelling

The optimisation of the extracted lipids using the 3 different pre-treatment techniques are done with RSM. The experimental results obtained from the lipid extraction of *Nannochloropsis Oculata* using different pre-treatment techniques and the reaction conditions applied in the RSM for lipid extraction are presented in Appendix B.6 to B.8. The analysis incorporates Response Surface Methodology (RSM) to calculate the coefficients of a second-order polynomial regression model with three input factors for each pre-treatment method. The quadratic model allows for the derivation of an equation to predict lipid extraction (%) based on these factors. For *N.Oculata* and its three pre-treatment methods, Eqn (5.1, 5.2, and 5.3) represent the mathematical models. In Eqn (5.1), the factors A, B, and C correspond to microwave power, microwave time, and extraction time, respectively. Similarly, Eqn (5.2) represents the relationship between homogenizing speed (A), running time (B), and extraction time (C) for another pre-treatment method. Lastly, Eqn (5.3) presents the mathematical model

for the ultrasonic pre-treatment, with factors A, B, and C representing ultrasonic time, extraction time, and frequency, respectively.

$$\text{MW: Lipid extraction (\%)} = 23.97 + 6.08A + 5.27B - 6.25A^2 - 5.41B^2 \quad \text{Eqn. (5.1)}$$

$$\text{HSH: Lipid extraction (\%)} = 19.71 + 11.76A - 4.06AC - 4.85B^2 - 2.17C^2 \quad \text{Eqn. (5.2)}$$

$$\text{Ultrasonic: Lipid extraction (\%)} = +11.47 + 2.14A + 1.68B + 3.55C + 0.9220AB + 1.04AC - 0.0761B^2 \quad \text{Eqn. (5.3)}$$

Table 5. 1 (Microwave), Table 5. 3 (HSH) and Table 5. 5(Ultrasonic) shows quadratic model results from the different pre-treatment techniques. From these tables, it can be said that the second order quadratic model fits this analysis because of the p-value < 0.05. Also, the values of $R^2 < 0.2$ and $R^2 < 0.9$. The regression analysis of the ANOVA was carried out to analyse the input factors that impacts the lipid percentage, and the outcomes are indicated in Table 5. 2 (Microwave), Table 5. 4 (HSH) and Table 5. 6 (Ultrasonic). The quadratic model results show the F – value of 7.21, 17.27 and 55.28, which shows the models are significant. There is a 0.82% chance for microwave, 0.05% chance for HSH and only 0.01% chance for ultrasonic that the F-value this large could have occurred due to noise. P-values <0.05 indicate that the model terms are significant. The significant factor in the lipid extraction (%) is shown as a p-value with a value less than 0.05, indicating that the model is significant. In order to calculate the accuracy of the model, lack of fit is applied, and the p-value of the lack of fit has to be >0.05. In the microwave model, the p-value of the lack of fit is 0.8834, and F-value is 0.2120, and in the HSH design, the p-value of the lack of fit is 0.4927, and F-value is 0.9608. In ultrasonic design p-value of the lack of fit is 0.5068, and F-value is 1.08. This implies the lack of fit is not significant relative to the pure error. There is a 88.34% (microwave), 49.27 (HSH) and 50.68% (ultrasonic) chance that a lack of fit F-value this large could occur due to noise. The presence of a non-significant lack of fit in the analysis serves as a strong validation of the model's robustness and coherence (Kashyap, Gogate and Joshi, 2019). This result confirms that the model fits well with the experimental data, validating its reliability and applicability for predicting the response variable across various conditions.

Table 5. 1: Microwave - RSM Response for Lipid extraction (*Nannochloropsis oculata*)

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.0114	0.2840	0.3292	
2FI	0.5144	0.2415	0.2644	
Quadratic	0.0227	0.8834	0.6283	Suggested
Cubic	0.8834			Aliased

Table 5. 2: ANOVA for Microwave quadratic model – *Nannochloropsis oculata*

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	1164.49	9	129.39	7.21	0.0082	significant
A- Microwave Power	295.49	1	295.49	16.46	0.0048	
B-Microwave Time	215.09	1	215.09	11.98	0.0105	
C-Extraction Time	45.27	1	45.27	2.52	0.1562	
AB	88.20	1	88.20	4.91	0.0622	
AC	4.33	1	4.33	0.2415	0.6381	
BC	18.84	1	18.84	1.05	0.3397	
A ²	138.00	1	138.00	7.69	0.0276	
B ²	123.05	1	123.05	6.86	0.0345	
C ²	37.42	1	37.42	2.08	0.1920	
Residual	125.63	7	17.95			
Lack of Fit	17.24	3	5.75	0.2120	0.8834	not significant
Pure Error	108.40	4	27.10			
Cor Total	1290.12	16				

Fit statistics - Standard deviation - 4.24, Mean – 17.69, Coefficient of variance (CV) % - 23.94, R² - 0.9026, Predicted R² - 0.6283, Adequate precision - 6.9841.

Table 5. 3: HSH - RSM Response for Lipid extraction (*Nannochloropsis oculata*)

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Predicted R ²	
Linear	< 0.0001	0.1478	0.6281	
2FI	0.3062	0.1507	0.4505	
Quadratic	0.0334	0.4927	0.6721	Suggested
Cubic	0.4927			Aliased

Table 5. 4: ANOVA for Microwave quadratic model – *Nannochloropsis oculata*

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	1399.28	9	155.48	17.27	0.0005	significant
A- Microwave Power	1125.75	1	1125.75	125.05	< 0.0001	
B-Microwave Time	11.28	1	11.28	1.25	0.2999	
C-Extraction Time	37.58	1	37.58	4.17	0.0803	
AB	17.80	1	17.60	1.95	0.2048	
AC	65.85	1	65.85	7.31	0.0304	
BC	0.5700	1	0.5700	0.633	0.8086	
A ²	23.72	1	23.72	2.63	0.1486	
B ²	99.11	1	99.11	11.01	0.0128	
C ²	19.86	1	19.86	2.21	0.1811	
Residual	63.02	7	9.00			
Lack of Fit	26.39	3	8.80	0.9608	0.4927	not significant
Pure Error	36.63	4	9.16			
Cor Total	1462.30	16				

Fit statistics - Standard deviation - 3.00, Mean - 17.52, Coefficient of variance (CV) % - 17.13, R² - 0.9569, Predicted R² - 0.6721 Adequate precision - 14.5748

Table 5. 5: Ultrasonic - RSM Response for Lipid extraction (*Nannochloropsis oculata*)

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Predicted R ²	
Linear	<0.0001	0.1133	0.8043	
2FI	0.3857	0.1079	0.6120	
Quadratic	0.0025	0.5068	0.9177	Suggested
Cubic	0.5068			Aliased

Table 5. 6: ANOVA for Ultrasonic quadratic model - *Nannochloropsis oculata*

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	314.02	8	39.25	55.28	<0.0001	significant
A- Ultrasonic time	35.70	1	35.70	50.28	0.0001	
B- Extraction time	28.38	1	28.38	39.97	0.0002	
C- Frequency	199.94	1	199.34	281.59	<0.0001	
AB	4.25	1	4.25	5.99	0.0401	
AC	8.41	1	8.41	11.85	0.0088	
BC	1.91	1	1.91	2.69	0.1395	
A ²	19.73	1	19.73	27.78	0.0008	
B ²	0.0216	1	0.0216	0.0305	0.8658	
Residual	5.68	8	0.7100			
Lack of Fit	3.65	5	0.7307	1.08	0.5068	not significant
Pure Error	2.03	3	0.6755			
Cor Total	319.70	16				

Fit statistics - Standard deviation - 0.8426, Mean - 11.14, Coefficient of variance (CV) % - 7.56, R² - 0.9822, Predicted R² - 0.9177, Adequate precision - 21.9447

The fit statistics provide valuable insights into the factors and actual data used in the analysis. The model's p-value is less than 0.05, and the lack of fit p-value is greater than 0.05, with R^2 greater than 0.9 indicate its adequacy (Ansori and Mahfud, 2022) (Kashyap, Gogate and Joshi, 2019). Adequate precision, which measures the signal-to-noise ratio, is desirable when it exceeds 4. In this case, the adequate precision values of 6.9841, 14.5748, and 21.9447 indicate a positive signal and reliable results (Kashyap, Gogate and Joshi, 2019). Furthermore, the proposed models exhibit R^2 values of 0.9026, 0.9569, and 0.9822, which correspond to a 90.26%, 95.69%, and 98.22% chance of differences in experimental response values. These high R^2 values indicate a strong correlation between the predicted and experimental responses, affirming the reliability of the proposed model in determining lipid extraction (%). Consequently, the model is considered suitable, and the response process parameters can be effectively enhanced. The fit summary responses suggest that the linear model for the response variable is highly recommended for further investigation, supported by the maximum values of predicted R^2 . The adequate precision ratio above 4 confirms the model's adequacy and response capability. Overall, the model's acceptance in essential statistical tests signifies its utility for predicting responses and performing optimisation processes.

5.3 Validation of the model

To verify the reliability of the model and the experimental data, a validation process is conducted to assess its adequacy. A rigorous mathematical design ensures that the model aligns closely with the actual process, offering a reliable approach for practical applications.

Figure 5. 1 (a) displays the perturbation plot, which represents the interaction between the input process conditions of microwave power (A), microwave time (B), and extraction time (C). The plot provides important insights into the relationship between these factors and lipid extraction (%). It clearly illustrates that an increase in lipid extraction is primarily driven by variations in power and heating time. The perturbation plot reveals that higher microwave power levels, combined with longer exposure times, lead to an enhanced percentage of lipid extraction. This indicates that the power level and heating time have a significant impact on lipid production. The relationship between microwave power and lipid extraction is particularly shown, highlighting the crucial role of power in achieving optimal lipid yields. Furthermore, the analysis reveals a less significant relationship between lipid extraction (%) and extraction time. This can be observed from the line representing extraction time (C) drops from the midpoint.

The decreasing trend indicates that extraction time has a relatively smaller impact on lipid extraction compared to the other factors. The (Qu *et al.*, 2021b) conclusions align with the findings from the perturbation plot, further supporting the significance of microwave power and running time in influencing cell disruption and lipid extraction. The perturbation plot analysis deepens our understanding of the influence of process conditions on lipid extraction in microwave-assisted microalgal pre-treatment. These insights offer valuable guidance for optimising the extraction process and maximising lipid production for microwave-assisted microalgal pre-treatment processes.

Similarly, the Figure 5. 1 (b) showcases the perturbation plot, illustrating the interaction between the input processing conditions of speed (A), running time (B), and extraction time (C). The perturbation plot reveals that the running speed of the homogeniser (A) plays a more prominent role compared to the other two factors. The increase observed in line A indicates that the running speed of the homogeniser enhances lipid extraction. Higher running speeds result in increased lipid yield compared to the other factors under consideration. Conversely, line B, representing running time, demonstrates a limited influence on lipid recovery. The dropping line suggests that variations in running time do not significantly affect the final lipid yield. Similarly, line C, which represents extraction time, exhibits a decreasing trend from the midpoint, implying that its impact on lipid yield is relatively modest. These observations align with the findings reported by the (Wang, Yin and Zeng, 2022b), emphasising the crucial role of the running speed of the homogeniser in maximising lipid yield. Consequently, the perturbation plot highlights the significance of carefully optimising the running speed of the homogeniser to enhance lipid yield during the pre-treatment process.

Figure 5. 1 (c & d) displays the perturbation plot, illustrating the relationship between the input process conditions of Ultrasonic time (A) and Extraction time (B). These plots provide valuable insights into the influence of ultrasonication time and extraction time on lipid extraction (%), specifically for two frequency levels (37 and 80 kHz). From the perturbation plots, it is evident that the increase in lipid extraction (%) is primarily attributed to variations in ultrasonication time and extraction time with higher frequency levels. The plots clearly demonstrate that the dominant factor in microalgal cell disruption using the ultrasonic technique is ultrasonication time. The inclination of the extraction time is directly proportional to this influential factor, with a steeper slope indicating a more effective parameter. The findings of the (Ren *et al.*,

2019b) study, which focused on ultrasonication and its impact on lipid yield concluded that the higher frequencies have an enhanced impact on cell disruption. The study revealed that increasing ultrasonication time leads to enhanced lipid yield, a result consistent with the insights derived from the perturbation plot in this study on microalgal ultrasonication pre-treatment.

Figure 5. 2 (a, b & c) depicts the predicted versus actual plot, demonstrating that the data points form a near-diagonal line. This alignment indicates that the predicted model aligns well with the experimental data, suggesting the adequacy of the model in representing the observed responses. The close proximity of the squares to each other further supports the suitability of the model for the dataset (Das and Mishra, 2017).

The Figure 5. 3 (a, b & c), a diagnostic tool is employed to examine the relationship between the normal % probability and the internally studentized residuals. The plot showcases the assumption of normality and verifies the distribution of the experimental values. The proximity of the points to the line suggests that the model assumptions are satisfied and that the normal distribution assumption is adequately met. Figure 5. 4 (a, b and c) represents the relationship between the predicted values and the internally studentized residuals. This plot is utilised to assess the model's suitability. In an adequate model, the residuals should exhibit a constant variance across all response values, and the squares should be randomly scattered within the range of +3, 0, and -3. The observed pattern of the residuals indicates the adequacy of the model, fulfilling the criteria for a reliable representation of the data (Abbasi, Ekrami-Kakhki and Tahari, 2017).

These diagnostic plots validate the model's suitability and its ability to effectively represent the experimental responses.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 5. 1: *Nannochloropsis oculata* - (a) Perturbation plot for lipid extraction (%) – Microwave. (b) Perturbation plot for lipid extraction (%) – HSH. (c) Perturbation plot for 37 kHz ultrasonic lipid extraction (%). (d) Perturbation plot for 80 kHz ultrasonic lipid extraction (%).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5. 2 : *Nannochloropsis oculata* - a) Predicted vs actual plot – Microwave. (b) Predicted vs actual plot – HSH. (c) Predicted vs actual plot – Ultrasonic

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5. 3 : *Nannochloropsis oculata* - (a) Internally studentized residuals vs normal 1% probability – Microwave. (b) Internally studentized residuals vs normal 1% probability – HSH. (c) Internally studentized residuals vs normal 1% probability – Ultrasonic.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5. 4: *Nannochloropsis oculata* - (a) Predicted vs internally studentized residuals – Microwave. (b) Predicted vs internally studentized residuals – HSH. (b) Predicted vs internally studentized residuals – Ultrasonic.

5.4 *Nannochloropsis oculata* 3D RSM graphical interpretation and the response values

5.4.1 Graphical RSM – Microwave

Figure 5. 5 and Figure 5. 6 illustrates the graphical RSM three-dimensional (3D) plots of the lipid extraction response (%) versus power. The effect of power and heating time was determined and presented in Figure 5. 5, the plot shows that the power ranges from 900 to 90w, with heating times ranging from 180 to 90 seconds. At a fixed factor of 3 hour extraction time, the lipid extraction (%) decreases from 29 to 6% with a final extraction rate of 77%. The decrement in lipid yield could also be attributed to the cell's inability to break down during the microwave treatment process, as it is difficult to break down the cell to extract lipids even at highest power and low heating time. The Figure 5. 6 shows the lipid extraction (%) decreases from 22.5 to 2.5% with a final lipid percentage of 88.88%. The difference in lipid extraction (%) has been explored, and it was determined that the elevated lipid yield concentration per cent was achieved due to an increase in power, as well as the quantity of pre-treated microalgae in relation to the increased heating time. Both factors are considered to be more important. Aside from extraction time, power and heating time are critical factors in the microwave-assisted lipid extraction process.

Figure 5. 5: *Nannochloropsis oculata* RSM plot in 3D for power and time for amount of lipid extracted (extraction time 3 hours)

Figure 5. 6: *Nannochloropsis oculata* RSM plot in 3D for power and time for amount of lipid extracted (extraction time 2 hours)

Figure 5. 7: *Nannochloropsis oculata* RSM plot in 3D for power and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (Heating time – 180 sec)

Figure 5. 8: *Nannochloropsis oculata* RSM plot in 3D for time and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (Microwave power – 90 w)

In Figure 5. 7, the power was viewed from 900 to 90W with 4 to 3 hours of extraction time at a fixed number of 180 secs microwave time. The lipid extraction (%) was found to decrease from 29.26 to 2.5%. At this extraction time, the final recovered lipid extraction (%) is 91.45%. The Figure 5. 8, with an actual factor of microwave power of 90 w and considering the microwave time from 180 to 90 secs, the lipid percentage decreases from 5% to 2.5% with a final product of 50%. This is because an increased heating rate may motivate the extraction method toward microalgae in order to increase lipid efficiency. According to the findings, increasing the power while decreasing the heating time and the extraction time may not affect the efficiency of the output lipid yield. In conclusion, for microalgae *Nannochloropsis oculata*, increasing the microwave power has an excellent ability to increase lipid extraction (%).

The findings of the study indicate a strong correlation between an increase in microwave power and enhanced lipid extraction (%). Specifically, the results demonstrate that applying a power level of 600W effectively disrupts cells and leads to a significant increase in lipid yield. These findings align with previous research conducted by referenced sources, further reinforcing the importance of microwave power in optimizing lipid extraction processes. references (Cheng, Huang, Li, *et al.*, 2014b, 2014c; Onumaegbu *et al.*, 2019a; Ashok *et al.*, 2021a; Qu *et al.*, 2021a; Prajapati, Kodgire and Singh Kachhwaha, 2022b). A different study with *Scenedesmus sp.* with microwave power of 100 W in microwave irradiation time of 2 mins saw a total increased lipid yield of 0.76% (Sivaramakrishnan *et al.*, 2020b). (Martinez-Guerra *et al.*, 2014), noted the reaction of extractive-transesterification process using microwave assisted method in dry microalgal *Chlorella sp.* biomass with microwave power of 700 W, reaction time 3 – 7

mins got a lipid enhancement of 20.1%. A study reported by (Rana *et al.*, 2020), using the microalgae *Chlorella pyrenoidosa* NCIM 2738 treated in microwave power 700 W and 5 minutes microwave heating time and optimised in RSM which found that the optimising conditions shown a 55.32% of lipid efficiency on comparing with the untreated conditions. A biodiesel analysis carried out in a study with ionic liquid catalysed esterification using 117.52 power, 17 min reaction time predicted a biodiesel yield of 97.92% (Yan *et al.*, 2020b). Future studies should try to focus on utilising the ionic liquid for biodiesel production. This study achieved efficient results by utilizing a microwave treatment approach that eliminated the need for drying or centrifuge techniques, resulting in energy and time savings. Specifically, a short treatment duration of 180 seconds with a power level of 600W, and a microwave time of 135 seconds, yielded a significant lipid extraction of 29.26% in *N.Oculata*. These findings demonstrate a higher productivity rate compared to other microalgae treatment methods using microwave technology. The outcomes of this study align with the previous studies.

5.4.2 Graphical RSM – High pressure homogeniser

The 3D surface plot was used to examine the relationship between speed, running time, and extraction time. The Figure 5. 9 and Figure 5. 10, indicated that when the speed of the homogeniser increases along with running time the lipid yield is enhanced. The Figure 5. 9 shows the actual factor of extraction time of 3 hrs and considering the homogenisation speed from 22000 rpm to 6000 rpm. The lipid yield decreases from 30 to 3% with a final lipid yield recovered at this point is 90%. According to the findings, raising running speed and decreasing running time appears to have no considerable effects on lipid efficiency. Overrunning time could sometimes impact cell destruction; this can be attributed to the cell wall, which is not thoroughly disrupted during pre-treatment techniques to increase lipid (%). In the Figure 5. 10, considering the homogenisation speed from 22000 rpm to 6000 rpm with a fixed running time of 10 mins, the lipid efficiency decreases from 29.2 to 5% with a final recovery yield of 82.87%. This analysis confirmed that low and high running speeds improve lipid yield, but longer extraction times and quick running speeds may reduce lipid efficiency.

The 3D plot in Figure 5. 11 and Figure 5. 12 represents the output responses of the lipid efficiency with homogenisation speed and extraction time. The Figure 5. 11 shows that with the fixed running time of 10 mins, and with the homogenisation speed of 22000 rpm and 6000 rpm the lipid percentage decreases from 25 to 10% and the final recovery yield of 60%. This

lowering may be heavily influenced by the increased running time due to cell wall disruption. In the Figure 5. 12, at a fixed speed factor of 6000 rpm, considering the running time from 15 to 5 mins with extraction time from 4 to 2 hrs, the lipid extraction (%) decreases from 7 to 5%. The final recovered lipid yield at this stage is 28.57%. There is also a possibility that the greater running speed will raise the temperature in the sample, which could affect the cell disruption rate.

Figure 5. 9: *Nannochloropsis oculata* RSM plot in 3D for speed and running time for amount of lipid extracted (extraction time 3 hours)

Figure 5. 10: *Nannochloropsis oculata* RSM plot in 3D for speed and running time for amount of lipid extracted (extraction time 2 hours)

Figure 5. 11: *Nannochloropsis oculata* RSM plot in 3D for speed and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (running time – 10 mins)

Figure 5. 12: *Nannochloropsis oculata* RSM plot in 3D for running time and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (Speed – 6000rpm)

The findings of this study provide evidence that applying a homogenisation speed of 22000 rpm for a duration of 10 minutes effectively disrupts algal cells, resulting in improved lipid efficiency (%). These results align with the conclusions drawn from the referenced research (Bernaerts *et al.*, 2017; Zhou *et al.*, 2017; Wang, Yin and Zeng, 2022a). The series of experiments conducted in this study clearly demonstrate that reducing the speed during the

homogenisation process negatively impacts lipid efficiency. When the speed is decreased, a significant number of algal cells remain untreated, leading to a decrease in the overall efficiency of lipid extraction. It is important to note that an extraction time of 3-3.5 hours proves to be optimal for achieving complete extraction, as supported by (Onumaegbu *et al.*, 2018b). The study emphasises the importance of maintaining an optimum speed during the homogenisation process. Exceeding the maximum speed and duration can result in cell damage, leading to lower efficiency during lipid extraction. The HSH treatment, specifically, demonstrates a high rate of cell disruption, leading to increased lipid efficiency. Several studies in the literature have also explored the effects of lipid extraction using the HSH method. For instance, Mengwai *et al.* investigated the effect of shear speed on *Synechococcus sp.* PCC 7002 and reported a lipid content of 8.82% using a shear speed of 10,000 rpm for 1 minute (5 cycles). The present research aligns well with these findings, indicating that higher lipid efficiency can be achieved through HSH pre-treatment. Moreover, the study highlights the positive correlation between increased shear rates and lipid extraction outcomes (Ginzberg, Korin and Arad, 2008)(Wang, Yin and Zeng, 2022a)(Zhou *et al.*, 2017). In a separate study conducted by (Bernaerts *et al.*, 2017), microalgal biomass *Porphyridium cruentum* was subjected to a homogenisation speed of 5500 rpm for a duration of 10 minutes. The results showed successful enrichment of ω 3-PUFA food products without causing any significant disruption to the structural characteristics of the final product. Similarly, (Malafronte *et al.*, 2021), conducted research on *Laminaria digitata* and employed a combination of thermal treatment (70 °C for 1 hour) followed by HSH at pressures ranging from 150 to 500 bar. This sequential treatment approach effectively disintegrated the algal cells and resulted in higher extraction yields of monosaccharides and polysaccharides. These studies provide additional evidence that different homogenisation approaches can be tailored to specific microalgal species to achieve desired outcomes. The careful selection of process parameters, such as speed, duration, and combination with other treatments, enables efficient cell disruption and extraction of valuable components from microalgae. In a separate study conducted by (Singh *et al.*, 2022b), the microalgae *Chlorella sp.* was subjected to a homogenisation speed of 12,000 rpm for a duration of 15 minutes, resulting in a lipid content of 13.05% . This finding aligns with similar results reported by referees (Huppertz, 2011; Guo *et al.*, 2014; Imatoukene *et al.*, 2020; Yildiz *et al.*, 2021; Singh *et al.*, 2022b), which collectively demonstrate that increasing the homogenisation speed, along with an appropriate running time, enhances the extraction of organic compounds from microalgae. These studies collectively support the notion that adjusting the speed and duration of homogenisation can effectively promote the extraction of valuable components

from microalgae. These studies provide additional evidence that different homogenisation approaches can be tailored to specific microalgal species to achieve desired outcomes. The careful selection of process parameters, such as speed, duration, and combination with other treatments, enables efficient cell disruption and extraction of valuable components from microalgae.

5.4.3 Graphical RSM – Ultrasonic

In this section, the graphical RSM contour plots displaying the regression equation with two factors in a graphical figure. The plot represents the ultrasonic time (A), Extraction time (B) and Frequency (C). Figure 5. 13 and Figure 5. 14 shows the graphical RSM three dimensional (3D) plots of the response in lipid extraction (%) over Frequency. The Figure 5. 13 shows at a fixed frequency 37 kHz, with the running time between 20 and 10 mins and extraction time between 4 to 2 hours, the recovered lipid efficiency falls from 9.8% to 5% with a final recovered lipid efficiency rate of 48%. Figure 5. 14 show the same extraction time and running time values consideration at a fixed frequency of 80 kHz, the efficiency decreases from 18% to 9%, 50% of final recovered lipid percentage was obtained.

Figure 5. 13: *Nannochloropsis oculata* RSM plot in 3D for ultrasonic time and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (Frequency – 37 kHz)

Figure 5. 14: *Nannochloropsis oculata* RSM plot in 3D for ultrasonic time and extraction time for amount of lipid extracted (Frequency – 80 kHz)

The ultrasound method employed in this study induces cavitation within the cell structure, leading to damage and altered membrane permeability, which facilitates the release of lipids. The frequency of ultrasound applied during the process plays a crucial role in lipid extraction, although only a limited number of experiments have investigated the specific effects on lipid

recovery. In our study, using a frequency of 80 kHz, we achieved a significantly higher lipid extraction of 17.91% for *Nannochloropsis oculata* compared to the 37 Hz frequency. Observations from the ultrasonic technique revealed some small droplets on the top layer after pre-treatment. These droplets, which are meant to be free of pre-treatment and dissolve in the surrounding solvent, such as hexane, were observed to contain lipids covered by the high polarity solvent. This enabled the lipids to be collected in the hexane layer. Previous studies conducted by (Converti *et al.*, 2009; Keris-Sen *et al.*, 2014; Zhang *et al.*, 2014, 2016; dos Santos *et al.*, 2015), and (Merouani *et al.*, 2016) investigated the effects of different frequencies in various applications, including hydrogen production. The duration of ultrasonication exposure demonstrated a significant correlation with extraction efficiency, regardless of the frequency and reaction time. Increased frequency and running time resulted in greater cell disruption in *C. Vulgaris* when subjected to ultrasonication. However, *N. Oculata* exhibited better tolerance to higher frequencies and longer exposure times. In a study conducted by (Khan, Park and Maeng, 2022b), *C. Vulgaris* strain was subjected to 20 minutes of ultrasonication, resulting in higher protein content. (Converti *et al.*, 2009) valuated *N. Oculata* using ultrasonic technique with a 6-hour extraction time and the Bligh and Dyer process, achieving a 24% lipid yield. (D'oca *et al.*, 2011) investigated *Chlorella pyrenoidosa* biomass with a 20-minute ultrasound pre-treatment and employed the same Bligh and Dyer extraction procedure, yielding a lipid content of 12.20%. Joyce *et al.* (Joyce, Wu and Mason, 2010) concluded from their experimental studies that increasing temperature and ultrasonic running time for 30 minutes did not significantly affect cell disruption. These studies have demonstrated the influence of frequencies and provided valuable insights into the relationship between ultrasound frequency and desired outcomes. In our study, a running time of 20 minutes showed an increased lipid recovery, indicating a substantial disruption of microalgal cells. It is important to note that prolonged extraction times may result in cell death during the reflux process. Therefore, it is advisable to maintain an extraction time range of 3 to 4 hours to achieve the desired lipid yield. Based on the findings of this study, a 4-hour extraction time with a 20-minute running time can be considered as favourable process parameter conditions for lipid extraction.

5.5: Validation of the experimental results - *Nannochloropsis oculata*

In general, the main concept underlying lipid extraction employing mechanical approaches is the breaking down of the cell wall. To validate this model, two sets of random tests in each technique (microwave, HSH, and ultrasonic) were chosen and validated with the predicted optimal parameters, and the results are shown in Table 5. 7.

Table 5. 7: Microalgal pre-treatment techniques and their experimental validation results - *Nannochloropsis oculata*

<u><i>Nannochloropsis oculata</i></u>				
Run	Microwave power (w)	Microwave time (Mins)	Extraction time (Hrs)	Lipid efficiency (%)
1	600	90	2	Predicted model: 18.35
				Validation model: 14.79
2	900	135	4	Predicted model: 24.26
				Validation model: 24.19
Run	Homogenising speed (rpm)	Running time (mins)	Extraction time (Hr)	Lipid efficiency (%)
1	14000	15	2	Predicted model: 14.04
				Validation model: 11.19
2	22000	10	4	Predicted model: 25.25
				Validation model: 28.26
Run	Ultrasonic frequency (rpm)	Ultrasonic time (mins)	Extraction time (Hr)	Lipid efficiency (%)
1	80	20	3	Predicted model: 5.64
				Validation model: 5.17
2	37	10	4	Predicted model: 9.79
				Validation model: 12.78

The reasonable correction between experimental and projected values demonstrates the model's accuracy. Furthermore, all of the pre-treatment procedures, as well as their regression models for and responses, had a high coefficient determination. As a result, establishing optimal

conditions will attempt to minimise total production costs while also providing a foundation for future investigations of the microalgae *Nannochloropsis oculata* in pre-treatment.

5.6 Optimisation of lipid extraction

The response values are obtained by determining the quadratic equation, and optimising this, will be able to predict the total processing and extraction cost. This helps to understand the influence of ideal values while processing a goal. The graphical optimisation images clearly show two different regions of yellow and grey. The yellow region indicates that the analysed parameters are feasible, whereas the responses with no goal are indicated in grey. From Figure 5. 15, lipid extraction of 24.61% was recovered from microwave power 600 w for 120 sec and extraction time of 2 hours. Figure 5. 16 shows that 33.17% was obtained from an HSH speed of 22000 rpm, 5 mins running time and extraction time of 2 hours. Figure 5. 17 shows that lipid extraction of 14.81% was acquired from 80 kHz frequency, 15 mins exposure time and 2 hours extraction time. These plots indicate the optimum conditions for a maximized lipid extraction percent obtained from the minimised input factors.

Figure 5. 15: *Nannochloropsis oculata* Graphical optimisation with minimising power, running time and extraction time with maximising lipid extraction - Microwave

Figure 5. 16: *Nannochloropsis oculata* Graphical optimisation with minimising speed, running time and extraction time with maximising lipid extraction – HSH

Figure 5. 17: *Nannochloropsis oculata* Graphical optimisation with minimising frequency, exposure time and extraction time with maximising lipid extraction - Ultrasonic

5.7 Effects of Pretreatment techniques on *Nannochloropsis oculata*

Extraction experiments were carried out on untreated algal species using hexane, methanol, and concentrated sulfuric acid to evaluate the impact of pre-treatment on lipid efficiency. A minimum reaction time of 2 hours was applied, and the results were then compared to the lipid efficiency obtained after pre-treatment. The untreated microalgae, *Nannochloropsis oculata*, showed a final lipid efficiency of 5.98%. Figure 5. 18 illustrates the maximum lipid extraction achieved through pre-treatment techniques in comparison to the untreated sample. The results of the pre-treatment techniques are presented in appendix B.2.

Figure 5. 18: Effect of lipid efficiency (%) for the untreated and pre-treated *Nannochloropsis oculata*

The effects of microwave radiation on the microalgae *N.Oculata* were thoroughly investigated. Through careful observation using a compound microscope, it was noted that when exposed to lower microwave power, the algal cells in *N.Oculata* experienced cell rupture. However, with the application of higher microwave power, the algal cells formed clusters, resulting in a significant enhancement of lipid yield. The main factors contributing to cell rupture can be attributed to the rapid and intense oscillation of polar molecules, such as liquids, within the algal cells under the influence of microwave radiation. This phenomenon generates internal pressure, ultimately leading to the disruption of cell walls and membranes. Additionally, the rise in temperature caused by microwave exposure facilitates cell breakdown and lipid release and these effects are discussed by refers, (Sivaramakrishnan *et al.*, 2020b) (Martinez-Guerra *et al.*, 2014). However, it is essential to be cautious of excessive exposure, as it may lead to undesired thermal degradation of lipids and other cellular components.

The HSH processing technique involves subjecting *N.Oculata* to a mechanical force, evenly blending them, and disrupting their cells. Higher processing speeds have shown to increase cell disruption efficiency and enhance lipid yield from untreated 5.68 to 40.56 with a final percentage of 85.96%. As the speed rises, microalgae tend to cluster together, further boosting lipid production as concluded by (Singh *et al.*, 2022b) in a study. Observations under a compound microscope revealed ruptured algal cell walls and cluster formation, driven by Vander walls forces (Ho *et al.*, 2022). Possible reasons for cell rupture using a homogeniser include shear forces that are causes with the sample and too much of force for a long-time exposure can also leads to oxidation or cavitation of the lipids.

The ultrasonic technique proves effective in disrupting algal cells and triggering the release of lipids. This study demonstrates that increasing the ultrasonic frequency leads to enhanced lipid yield, with the algae being subjected to ultrasonication at 37 and 80 kHz frequencies. The ultrasonic method induces cavitation within the cell structure, causing damage and altering membrane permeability, thus facilitating lipid release and this effect is discussed by (Khan, Park and Maeng, 2022b). The applied ultrasonic frequency plays a crucial role in lipid extraction. Notably, in this study, a frequency of 80 kHz resulted in a 17.91% lipid extraction from *N. Oculata*, significantly higher than the untreated yield of 5.68%.

5.8 Conclusion

In this study, the wet microalgal biomass of *Nannochloropsis oculata* was subjected to various pre-treatment techniques, resulting in enhanced lipid extraction efficiencies. The microwave-assisted treatment achieved a lipid extraction efficiency of 29%, while high-speed homogenization and ultrasonic treatment yielded efficiencies of 40% and 17% respectively. These results highlight the sustainability and effectiveness of the wet method for utilising algae biomass in lipid extraction processes. The implementation of response surface methodology (RSM) optimisation demonstrated the significant impact of varying the factors on the output response. The quadratic parameters exhibited notable effects, indicating the suitability of the design for Box-Behnken simulations. These optimised methods hold great potential for the production of biodiesel feedstock from microalgae, offering a sustainable alternative to fossil fuels and contributing to the development of environmentally friendly energy sources.

Chapter 6. Lipid characterisation

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis and discussion of the gas chromatography (GC) results obtained from the extracted lipid samples of two microalgal species, *Chlorella Vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis Oculata*. The analysis of lipid composition is an essential step in assessing the potential of microalgae as a biodiesel feedstock. By examining the fatty acid profile of the extracted lipids, valuable insights can be gained into their suitability for biodiesel production. The GC analysis provides a detailed characterisation of the fatty acid composition of the extracted lipids. Fatty acids are the key constituents of lipids and their profile plays a crucial role in determining the quality and properties of biodiesel. By quantifying and identifying the different fatty acids present in the lipid samples, valuable information can be obtained regarding their potential as a biodiesel feedstock. The fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) content is particularly important, as it is directly related to the biodiesel production process. The findings from this analysis will contribute to the understanding of the lipid composition of microalgal species and their potential as a sustainable biodiesel feedstock. By comparing the GC results with existing literature and established biodiesel standards, the potential of utilising *C.Vulgaris* and *N.Oculata* lipids for biodiesel production can be determined.

6.2 Transesterification analysis and Fatty acid quantification

While doing lipid extraction in this study, the algal biomass is exhibited to solvent extraction after pre-treatment. The most common extraction process in current studies in biodiesel production is employing solvents like methanol and chloroform for dry biomass. This study avoided drying and used wet algal biomass. Here in this study, concentrated sulphuric acid was used as a catalyst. This was considered the most effective catalyst for biodiesel production with a higher content of free fatty acids (Gebremariam and Marchetti, 2018). A solvent reflux process was carried out for extraction from methanol using a reflux condenser. This application in microalgal biodiesel production is very little in the literature and hasn't been published yet. As a result, it appears worthwhile to put this methodology and its operational parameters to the test lipid source from *C.Vulgaris* and *N.Oculata* for biodiesel production. To keep a steady reflux, the process works at a constant boiling temperature where the solvents methanol and the conc sulphuric acid in the algal biomass were contacted repeatedly, making a product formation, and the lipids were made easy to get extracted along with the formation of FAME.

The pH level was neutralised using sodium bicarbonate after reflux. The non-polar solvent hexane is used here for extraction after reflux. This solvent separates the lipid by creating a chemical bond between the hexane, methanol, and algal biomass after reflux. Also, these non-polar solvents penetrate the cell wall/membrane interacting with the lipids, and this reaction is suggested by the refers (Halim, Danquah and Webley, 2012b; Durak and Aysu, 2016; Catchpole *et al.*, 2018) and named van der Waals forces. Methanol is very fast in reaction rate forming triglycerides, and they contain pressurised carbon dioxide, which acts as a suitable solvent for extraction and transesterification. The organic solvent hexane was used to extract the oil from methanol. Most of the studies use chloroform to extract oil from the methanol. But the generated biodiesel yields from chloroform showed an excellent percentage of results from dry biomass. In contrast, the biodiesel yields from wet microalgae were significantly low compared with the yields achieved from dry biomass. And also, using chloroform conversion requires more reaction time of at least 6 hrs (Cheng, Huang, Li, *et al.*, 2014e). On considering the cost factors and reaction time, hexane was planned to replace instead of chloroform. Also, hexane is the most effective solvent for large-scale extractions due to its cost-effectiveness. Hexane is less hazardous than chloroform for recovering lipids and less attractive to non-lipid residuals. Applying hexane for high-yielding lipid extractions from microalgal species would provide a more cost-effective and eco-friendly method of producing biodiesel.

In this study, the polarity layer separation happened within 5 to 10 minutes after seeing the methanol and hexane interaction. And washing three times using hexane tried extracting the lipid as much as the broken microalgal residuals were carried over by the methanol, finally giving out a higher efficient lipid content after hexane evaporation in both the microalgal species (*C. Vulgaris* and *N. Oculata*). The extraction procedure and different reaction times used in this study found that the lipid percent was enhanced after 3 hrs of reaction time. In a study by Onumaegbu *et al.* (Onumaegbu *et al.*, 2019b), the results showed that the lipid content was improved after 3 hrs of reaction time, so in this study, the reaction time was planned to increase to a maximum time of 4 hrs and also with a minimum time of 2 hrs. But finally, the final results of the lipid efficiency concluded that the lipid efficiency could be increased with the increasing reaction time.

The Fame results produced by transesterification was analysed and the results of *C.Vulgaris* and *N.Oculata* are represented in Table 6. 1. In this GC process, Supelco 37 component Fame mix was used to detect the obtained FAME from microalgae lipids as indicated in Appendix C.1. To understand about the FAME yield, the fatty acids involved should be calculated and compared with the standard. In order to understand the obtained yields, the biodiesel sample from crude soya biodiesel mix was analysed by gas chromatography and their FAME analysis are shown in Appendix C.2. The FAME yields in the biodiesel mix were analysed for their FAME peak area, retention time, biodiesel mix and standard. The identified peaks and their concentrations were calculated by their peak area (pA) in the form of concentrations calculated in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (ppb) along with the total peak area (%). For the identified peaks, C14 - Methyl myristate, C15 - Methyl pentadecanoate, C16 - Methyl palmitate, C18 - Methyl stearate, C18:2 - Methyl linoleate, C20 - Methyl arachidate, C20:1 - Methyl eicosate, C20:2 - Methyl eicosadienoate, C22 - Methyl erucate.

Fatty acid composition in microalgae typically consists of a combination of structural unsaturated polar lipids and neutral lipids, primarily stored in the form of Triacylglycerol (TAG). In the context of biodiesel production, the fatty acids of utmost importance are saturated fatty acids (SFA), monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA), and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), which encompass the C14-C18 components (Thomas, Tornabene and Weissman, 1984). The G-C analysis in this study shows that the FAME evaluation clearly describes that the extracted lipid samples from both the microalgae is potential for biodiesel production. Furthermore, the resemblance of Soya biodiesel (80:20 mix), the standard used, and the fame sample shows that each of the concentration of the sample varies. The concentrations (C) were calculated by the eqn. (3.3) and the identified compounds, and their concentration are listed in Table 6. 1.

From the Table 6. 1, it is observed that the concentration of the different compounds and their comparison to commercial standard concentration. In the microalgae *C.Vulgaris* extracted lipids, C14 - Methyl myristate, C15 - Methyl pentadecenoate and C16 - Methyl palmitate has higher concentration levels for the extracted lipids. The GC analysis found in this study indicates that the biodiesel samples have a higher concentration of monounsaturated fatty acid methyl ester elements and said to be fully fit with the biodiesel mix basic requirements.

Table 6. 1: Comparison of extracted biodiesel sample

	C14	C15	C16	C18	C18:2	C20	C20:1	C20:2	C22	References
Commercial standard ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0	0	110.50	102.23	171.00	117.54	515.20	359.45	13.11	Current study
<i>C.Vulgaris</i> ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	65.17	92.76	32.07	8.871	2.45	2.81	0	0	0	Current study
<i>N.Oculata</i> ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	10.65	43.67	348.28	14.16	5.23	60.03	0.63	0	0	Current study
<i>Scenedesmus obtusus</i> ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1.16	2.98	25.29	2.21	22.90	18.98	N/A	N/A	N/A	(Nascimento <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
<i>Cyclotella</i> ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2.78	N/A	13.25	1.86	1.44	6.38	N/A	0	0.53	(Graham <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
<i>Aulacoseira</i> ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2.34	N/A	4.33	0	0.10	5.23	N/A	0	0	(Graham <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
<i>Ankistrodesmus falcatus</i> ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1.07	N/A	30.23	2.72	26.49	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	(Vinitha <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
<i>C.Vulgaris</i> ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.63	0.44	40.31	8.01	8.54	1.95	N/A	N/A	1.95	(Vinitha <i>et al.</i> , 2023)

The concentrations of the various compounds and their comparison to commercial standard concentrations are identified. In the microalgae *N.Oculata* extracted lipids, C15-Methyl pentadecenoate, C16 - Methyl palmitate and C20 - Methyl arachidate has higher concentration levels for the extracted lipids. These four fatty acids, namely C14, C15, C16, and C20, are consistently found as the predominant fatty acids across various algal groups as reported by (Hu *et al.*, 2008). In this present research work, C16 Methyl palmitate looks higher in *N. Oculata*, which is seen higher on other reported studies as shown in . This presence of higher concentration of Methyl palmitate favours biodiesel properties (Zhou *et al.*, 2023). An elevated proportion of saturated fatty acids (SFA) in biodiesel has been found to improve its stability, as unsaturated fatty acids are known to have lower oxidative stability. Biodiesel produced through the transesterification of common fatty acids (C16-C18) offers several advantages over petroleum-derived diesel fuel. It has been shown to reduce emissions of CO, hydrocarbons, CO₂, and particulate matter (Abomohra, Jin and El-Sheekh, 2016). The concentration of monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) (C16 + C18) in the obtained biodiesel samples was observed to be slightly higher compared to the values reported in previous studies. This elevated concentration has the potential to enhance the oxidative stability and overall performance of the biodiesel, especially under low temperature conditions (Knothe, 2009). The fatty acid composition of the extracted lipids played a crucial role in predicting the properties of the biodiesel. These predicted properties were found to align with the established commercial standards (Table 6. 1) for biodiesel produced from microalgae in the current study. According to reports, the ideal feedstock for biodiesel production consists of a high concentration of C16-C18 fatty acids, which are considered to be the most suitable for this analysing biodiesel characteristics which comprises of palmitic acid, stearic acid, oleic acid, linoleic acid, and linolenic acid. The percentage of C16 and C18 fatty acids in the total fatty acid content is often used as an indicator of biodiesel quality (Aslam *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, when comparing the findings of this study with those of other research studies in the literature (TABLE), the concentration of biodiesel obtained appears to be higher. This finding suggests a favourable and viable approach for biodiesel production from microalgae using the transesterification procedures implemented in this current study. The GC analysis found in this investigation suggests that the biodiesel samples have a higher proportion of monounsaturated fatty acid methyl ester elements and are said to completely meet the basic demands of the biodiesel mix.

6.3 Conclusion

The analysis of fatty acid composition in the extracted lipids from microalgae species *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis oculata* reveals their potential for biodiesel production. The gas chromatography (GC) analysis indicates that the extracted lipid samples exhibit high concentrations of fatty acid methyl esters, which are in line with the basic requirements of biodiesel. The concentrations of specific fatty acids, such as C14 - Methyl myristate, C15 - Methyl pentadecenoate, C16 - Methyl palmitate, and C20 - Methyl arachidate, vary in the extracted lipids, with C16 - Methyl palmitate showing higher levels in *N.Oculata*. The presence of high concentrations of C16 and C18 fatty acids, which are considered ideal feedstock for biodiesel production, indicates the suitability of the extracted lipids for biodiesel production. Furthermore, the concentration of biodiesel obtained in this study appears to be higher compared to previous research, suggesting the efficacy of the transesterification procedures implemented. The analysis of fatty acid composition provides valuable insights into the biodiesel properties and their alignment with established standards. This research contributes to the knowledge and understanding of biodiesel production from microalgae, paving the way for further advancements in renewable energy technologies.

7. Conclusions and recommendations

7.1 Introduction

The rise in the global population has increased global energy consumption. In this context, the innovation of alternative energy sources has accelerated over the last few years. All nations are working to find a long-term approach for transportation and commercial applications. Microalgae biofuel appears to be a promising feedstock for replacing fossil fuels, but advanced manufacturing large-scale industry is not yet fulfilled. Furthermore, ongoing actions and investment demand focus attention and market position on the aspirations of microalgae biodiesel production and outstanding production technologies. Microalgal biofuel production has the potential to be sustainable, but economic feasibility is a significant obstacle to commercial success. In this section, the efficiency of algal pre-treatment to improve lipid extraction yield for biodiesel production, as described in the literature, has been outweighed by this study. Even though several studies have found that high energy consumption is a major factor for mechanical and some non-mechanical pre-treatment, as explained, the pricing of enzymatic and chemical products remains a major barrier to the full-scale implementation of algal biofuel production. Based on this circumstance, the input variables for algal cell disruption must be evaluated using a multi-objective optimisation technique that maximises lipid extraction yield. Therefore, this study investigated the implementation of 3 different pre-treatment methods, namely microwave, high-speed homogeniser and ultrasonic, to enhance the lipid extraction from microalgal species *Chlorella Vulgaris* and *Nannochloropsis oculata*. The results indicate that for *Chlorella Vulgaris*, a maximum lipid yield of 14.84%, and *Nannochloropsis oculata*, a maximum yield of 40.56%, was recovered.

The rate (%) lipid recovered was effectively modelled using Box-Behnken Design (BBD) with the microalgal strains using Response Surface Methodology (RSM). The application of RSM plots in the experimental data demonstrated the correlations of input variables on the output parameters. An increase in spindle speed significantly affects the amount of lipid recovered during high-speed pre-treatment. Surprisingly, increasing the microwave heating time and power significantly improved the lipid yield. Again, the ultrasonic, increasing frequency with exposure time increased the lipid extraction efficiency for the algal species, as detailed for *Chlorella Vulgaris* in chapter 4 and *Nannochloropsis oculata* in chapter 5. Mathematical optimisation points and graphical optimisation regions were achieved for maximum lipid

extraction efficiency. The optimisation technique will aid in developing future commercial applications for biodiesel production from microalgal biomass.

According to the discussion above, optimising the percentage of lipid yield produced by microalgae cells is achieved successfully through biomass materials after pre-treatment. At the same time, it is concluded that high-speed homogeniser pre-treatment is the most effective pre-treatment technique for increasing lipid extraction efficiency compared to the microwave and ultrasonic used in this study. Furthermore, the favourable assessment clearly shows a suitable model conception for all statistical analyses in which an important model was obtained.

The study's findings will surely aid a variety of bioenergy, biotechnology, microalgae farming, and biorefinery businesses, including:

- Biorefinery sectors are keen to innovate microalgal pre-treatment techniques to attain sustainability.
- Existing pre-treatment facilities are keen to optimise their operational parameters and expenses.
- The biodiesel compound discovered in this research is suitable for industrial usage.
- The lipid output with the biodiesel concentration implies that it may be employed as a promising approach in biodiesel technology.
- The benefits of the suggested technology and the market importance of algal biodiesel will be realised through continuous industrial growth and the selection of a higher lipid-content algae species.
- Scale-up technology will be crucial for implementing the findings on a commercial scale, ensuring that the processes can be efficiently and effectively replicated in larger operations.
- Energy cost monitoring will play a significant role in assessing the economic viability of the biodiesel production process and optimizing energy consumption throughout the production chain.

7.2 Research contribution

After exploring the effectiveness of three different pre-treatment techniques, this research project has successfully and significantly contributed to our understanding in biofuel production. As a result of this research, the following points were established:

- When compared to HSH and ultrasonic technique, this study found that microwave pre-treatment effectively disrupts microalgae cell walls and enhances lipid recovery efficiency in a very short extraction time.
- This study clearly demonstrated that HSH modelling and optimisation using Design of experiment (DOE) resulted in an enhancement of maximised lipids.
- This study demonstrated that using wet microalgae cells for biodiesel production is more cost effective.
- The research also demonstrated that the optimisation technique used in this investigation, which employs Response Surface methodology (RSM), successfully maximises the operating and pre-treatment conditions, resulting in increased lipid extraction yield.

7.3 Recommendation for Future work

The following points are suggested for future research areas to improve the economic efficiency of biodiesel production from microalgal biomass.

- Investigating other microalgae species such as: *Scenedesmus dimorphus*, *Botryococcus braunii*, *Botryococcus sp.* for producing biofuel.
- Investigating and analysing advance pre-treatment methods like pulsed arch technology, Ionic liquids, focused ultrasonication and chemical techniques to increase lipid yield.
- The cost management process is used to determine the economic feasibility of new pre-treatment techniques (Optimisation process).
- Evaluating the specific energy consumption for the pre-treatment technique and implementation process for industrial scale application.
- Optimising microalgal cultivating parameters.

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Appendices A:

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A. 1 Supelco 37 FAME mix standard

Appendices B:

B.1 Experimental results of different pre-treatment techniques - *Chlorella vulgaris*.

Run	Microwave				High speed homogeniser				Ultrasonic			
	Power (W)	Time (sec)	Extraction time (hours)	Lipid efficiency (%)	Speed (rpm)	Running Time (Mins)	Extraction time (Hours)	Lipid efficiency (%)	Frequency (Hz)	Ultrasonic time (Mins)	Extraction time (Hours)	Lipid efficiency (%)
1	600	90	2	11.80	14000	15	2	7.67	80	10	2	5.65
2	900	90	3	13.76	22000	15	3	11.24	80	20	4	11.54
3	600	135	3	13.10	14000	10	3	14.76	37	10	2	2.65
4	900	135	4	14.01	14000	10	3	14.06	37	20	3	5.33
5	600	135	3	13.57	6000	15	3	4.32	37	20	2	4.89
6	600	180	4	14.84	22000	5	3	17.87	80	15	2	10.29
7	600	135	3	14.10	22000	10	4	9.55	80	15	3	11.07
8	90	180	3	10.87	14000	10	3	10.76	80	20	2	9.56
9	600	135	3	13.13	14000	15	4	7.35	37	15	3	4.88
10	600	135	3	13.64	14000	10	3	14.53	80	15	3	10.21
11	90	135	2	9.99	22000	10	2	18.65	37	15	4	6.38
12	600	135	2	13.55	6000	5	3	3.42	37	10	3	2.19
13	90	135	4	10.11	14000	10	3	14.89	80	20	3	11.41
14	600	180	3	15.24	14000	5	2	6.78	80	15	3	11.52
15	600	180	2	14.57	6000	10	4	3.99	37	15	2	2.69
16	90	90	3	9.98	14000	5	4	9.74	37	15	4	6.77
17	600	90	4	9.45	6000	10	2	3.67	80	10	4	6.87

B.2 Experimental results of different pre-treatment techniques - *Nannochloropsis Oculata*.

Microwave				High speed homogeniser				Ultrasonic				
Run	Power (W)	Time (sec)	Extraction time (hours)	Lipid efficiency (%)	Speed (rpm)	Running Time (Mins)	Extraction time (Hours)	Lipid efficiency (%)	Frequency (Hz)	Ultrasonic time (Mins)	Extraction time (Hours)	Lipid efficiency (%)
1	900	135	2	19.47	6000	15	3	7.44	80	10	2	8.67
2	600	135	3	29.76	14000	10	3	20.22	37	20	4	9.91
3	600	135	3	29.26	14000	5	2	14.26	80	15	2	14.87
4	90	135	4	8.29	6000	10	2	6.25	37	10	3	5.12
5	900	90	3	6.91	14000	15	4	10.35	37	15	2	6.03
6	900	135	4	24.76	6000	5	3	5.76	37	20	3	7.11
7	600	90	4	11.65	14000	5	4	13.34	80	15	3	15.77
8	600	180	4	28.45	22000	15	3	24.5	80	15	4	16.88
9	90	90	3	6.71	22000	5	3	31.21	80	20	4	17.91
10	600	135	3	17.38	6000	10	4	7.37	80	20	2	13.45
11	600	90	2	9.36	14000	15	2	12.78	80	10	4	9.65
12	900	180	3	27.28	14000	10	3	24.45	37	15	2	4.94
13	600	180	2	17.48	22000	10	4	25.45	37	15	4	9.21
14	90	135	2	6.44	14000	10	3	17.77	37	10	4	5.66
15	90	180	3	8.36	14000	10	3	16.53	80	20	3	15.54
16	600	135	3	22.45	14000	10	3	19.56	80	15	3	14.12
17	600	135	3	26.76	22000	10	2	40.56	80	15	3	14.54

B.3 Microwave - RSM Reaction conditions used in lipid extraction (*Chlorella vulgaris*)

Run	Factors Level code			Lipid extraction		
	Microwave power (w)	Microwave time (mins)	Extraction time (Hrs)	Actual (%)	Predicted (%)	Residual (%)
1	0	-1	-1	11.8	12.10	-0.3037
2	1	-1	0	13.76	13.43	0.3273
3	0	0	0	13.1	13.51	-0.4119
4	1	0	1	14.01	14.34	-0.3273
5	0	0	0	13.57	13.51	0.0581
6	0	1	1	14.84	14.55	0.2940
7	0	0	0	14.1	13.51	0.5881
8	-1	1	0	10.87	11.09	-0.2210
9	0	0	0	13.13	13.51	-0.3819
10	0	0	0	13.64	13.51	0.1281
11	-1	0	-1	9.99	9.77	0.2210
12	0	0	-1	13.55	13.45	0.0971
13	-1	0	1	10.11	10.08	0.0285
14	0	1	1	15.24	15.30	-0.0585
15	0	1	-1	14.57	14.58	-0.0145
16	-1	-1	0	9.98	10.01	-0.0285
17	0	-1	1	9.45	9.45	0.0048

B.4 HSH - RSM Reaction conditions used in lipid extraction (*Chlorella vulgaris*)

Run	Factors Level code			Lipid extraction		
	Speed (RPM)	Running time (mins)	Extraction time (Hrs)	Actual (%)	Predicted (%)	Residual (%)
1	0	1	-1	7.67	8.57	-0.8988
2	1	1	0	11.24	11.67	-0.4250
3	0	0	0	14.76	13.80	0.9600
4	0	0	0	14.06	13.80	0.2600
5	-1	1	0	4.32	4.95	-0.6325
6	1	-1	0	17.87	17.24	0.6325
7	1	0	1	9.55	11.08	-1.53
8	0	0	0	10.76	13.80	-3.04
9	0	1	1	7.35	5.39	1.96
10	0	0	0	14.53	13.80	0.7300
11	1	0	-1	18.65	17.33	1.32
12	-1	-1	0	3.42	3.00	0.4250
13	0	0	0	14.89	13.80	1.09
14	0	-1	-1	6.78	8.74	-1.96
15	-1	0	1	3.99	5.31	-1.32
16	0	-1	1	9.74	8.84	0.8987
17	-1	0	-1	3.67	2.14	1.53

B.5 Ultrasonic - RSM Reaction conditions used in lipid extraction (*Chlorella vulgaris*)

Run	Factors Level code			Lipid extraction		
	Ultrasonic time (mins)	Extraction time (Hr)	Frequency (kHz)	Actual (%)	Predicted (%)	Residual (%)
1	-1	-1	1	5.65	6.25	-0.6014
2	1	1	1	11.54	11.91	-0.3698
3	-1	-1	-1	2.65	1.50	1.15
4	1	0	-1	5.33	5.48	-0.1469
5	1	-1	-1	4.89	3.94	0.9466
6	0	-1	1	10.29	9.69	0.5983
7	0	0	1	11.07	10.60	0.4704
8	1	-1	1	9.56	10.12	-0.5650
9	0	0	-1	4.88	5.51	-0.6344
10	0	0	1	10.21	10.60	-0.3896
11	0	1	-1	6.38	6.29	0.0891
12	-1	0	-1	2.19	2.54	-0.3549
13	1	0	1	11.41	11.27	0.1351
14	0	0	1	11.52	10.60	0.9204
15	0	-1	-1	2.69	4.22	-1.53
16	0	1	-1	6.77	6.29	0.4791
17	-1	1	1	6.87	7.07	-0.1983

B.6 Microwave - RSM Reaction conditions used in lipid extraction (*Nannochloropsis oculata*)

Run	Factor level code			Lipid extraction (%)			
	Power (W)	Time (sec)	Extraction (hours)	time	Actual	Predicted	Residual
1	1	0	-1		19.47	17.38	2.09
2	0	0	0		29.76	25.12	4.64
3	0	0	0		29.26	25.12	4.14
4	-1	0	1		8.29	10.06	-1.77
5	1	-1	0		6.91	8.50	-1.59
6	1	0	1		24.76	24.26	0.5013
7	0	-1	1		11.65	10.78	0.8685
8	0	1	1		28.45	28.05	0.3960
9	-1	-1	0		6.71	5.59	1.12
10	0	0	0		17.38	25.12	-7.74
11	0	-1	-1		9.36	9.76	-0.3960
12	1	1	0		27.28	28.28	-1.00
13	0	1	-1		17.48	18.35	-0.8685
14	-1	0	-1		6.44	7.27	-0.8292
15	-1	1	0		8.36	6.89	1.47
16	0	0	0		22.45	25.12	-2.67
17	0	0	0		26.76	25.12	1.64

B.7 HSH - RSM Reaction conditions used in lipid extraction (*Nannochloropsis oculata*)

Run	Factor level code			Lipid extraction (%)			
	Speed (rpm)	Running Time (Mins)	Extraction (Hours)	time	Actual	Predicted	Residual
1	-1	1	0		7.44	6.27	1.17
2	0	0	0		20.22	19.71	0.5140
3	0	-1	-1		14.26	15.66	-1.40
4	-1	0	-1		6.25	6.15	0.0950
5	0	1	1		10.35	8.95	1.40
6	-1	-1	0		5.76	4.45	1.31
7	0	-1	1		13.34	12.08	1.26
8	1	1	0		24.5	25.80	-1.30
9	1	-1	0		31.21	32.38	-1.16
10	-1	0	1		7.37	9.94	-2.57
11	0	1	-1		12.78	14.04	-1.26
12	0	0	0		24.45	19.71	4.74
13	1	0	1		25.45	25.25	-0.0950
14	0	0	0		17.77	19.71	-1.94
15	0	0	0		16.53	19.71	-3.18
16	0	0	0		19.56	19.71	-0.1460
17	1	0	-1		40.56	38.00	2.56

B.8 Ultrasonic - RSM Reaction conditions used in lipid extraction (*Nannochloropsis oculata*)

Run	Factor level code			Lipid extraction (%)		
	Ultrasonic time (mins)	Extraction time (Hr)	Frequency (kHz)	Actual	Predicted	Residual
1	-1	-1	1	8.67	9.15	-0.4798
2	1	1	1	9.91	9.68	0.2305
3	0	-1	-1	14.87	13.70	1.17
4	-1	0	-1	5.12	4.52	0.5965
5	0	-1	-1	6.03	5.73	0.2988
6	1	-1	1	7.11	6.72	0.3885
7	0	0	1	15.75	15.01	0.7351
8	0	-1	1	16.88	16.18	0.6996
9	1	0	-1	17.91	17.98	-0.0680
10	1	0	1	13.45	13.65	-0.2006
11	-1	1	-1	9.65	9.79	-0.1391
12	0	0	-1	4.94	5.73	-0.7912
13	0	0	1	9.21	9.96	-0.7454
14	1	0	1	5.66	5.64	0.0225
15	1	-1	-1	15.54	15.89	-0.3504
16	0	1	-1	14.12	15.01	-0.8949
17	0	1	1	14.54	15.01	-0.4749

C.2 GC analysis of soya biodiesel (ASTM D6751)

C.3 Gas chromatography of *Chlorella vulgaris* lipid extraction

C.5 GC results of *Nannochloropsis oculata*

MV Power
 -90W, Running
 time - 180secs,
 Extraction time
 - 3 hrs

US Frequency
 -80kHz, Time -
 15mins,
 Extraction time
 - 4 hrs

